

Combined corrosion and fatigue strength of joined materials for body-in-white and structural automotive applications design (AUTOFATCOR)

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1 **Final summary**

1.1 **WP 1 Project management**

The objective of work package WP1 was to maintain communications with the European Commission and within the participants. Height meetings were performed during the project to ensure good progression of the tasks and find solutions concerning the delay in supplying metal sheets to prepare samples.

A summary of the work packages and the links between them is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Description of the tasks and links of the project.

1.2 **WP 2 Definition of fatigue loading and testing conditions**

The objectives of work package WP2 were to define the corrosion testing conditions, the fatigue parameters and the sample designs.

The accelerated corrosion test as per VDA 233-102 (called NVDA) was selected as reference corrosion test. Simpler corrosion tests were selected to study key environmental parameters on corrosion and fatigue-corrosion properties, based on a basic test at constant temperature with alternating drying and wetting phases. The different parameters that were investigated are listed hereafter:

- salt concentration SC (1 and 5 wt.%)
- salt spray frequency SF (2 and 7 times a week)
- temperature of the test T (30 and 45 °C)
- freezing phase F (one day at -25 °C)
- drying ratio D (1 and 3; Drying time at RH 50% over wetting time at RH 95%)

Conventional hydraulic fatigue machines were chosen to perform the fatigue tests in air at frequency of 30 Hz, load ratio of 0.1 until complete failure of the specimen, limited to 2 million cycles.

Two kinds of fatigue-corrosion tests were selected:

- Alternated fatigue-corrosion with fatigue test in air and exposure to NVDA test alternatively
- Simultaneous fatigue-corrosion with fatigue test within a climatic chamber of accelerated corrosion test.

Alternated fatigue-corrosion tests were performed following two different methods. For the first method, 6 NVDA cycles were conducted at 6 equal intervals during the fatigue life found in air,

beginning by fatigue cycles. For the second method, one NVDA cycle was performed after 300,000 cycles whatever the stress amplitude.

Specific pneumatic devices were designed to perform the simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests. The maximum applied load was limited to 3500 N and the frequency was imposed at 0.5 Hz to obtain synergetic effects from fatigue and corrosion.

Two different joining techniques were selected for the project, resistant spot welding and adhesive joining. Resistant spot weld with adhesive joining was also applied simultaneously for some assemblies. Single-spot-welded samples were preferred to multi-spot-welded ones due to the limitation of the pneumatic fatigue devices for simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests. Lap-shear and T-peel designs were selected to obtain two different mechanical states during the tensile and fatigue testing.

1.3 WP 3 Manufacturing of the samples and characterization

The main objectives of work package WP3 were to provide materials and join them, to characterize all materials and joint structures, to apply surface treatment and paint and to determine the mechanical properties of the assemblies.

Height different materials were supplied for the project, four cold rolled steels (CRS), two high strength steels (HSS) and two press hardened steels (PHS):

- DC04 steel without coating
- DX56 steel with ZF110 coating (galvannealed)
- DX56 steel with ZM coating (ZnAl₂Mg₂)
- DX56 steel with Z100 coating (hot dip galvanized)
- HC420LA with Z100 coating
- HCT780C with ZE coating (electro galvanized)
- 22MnB5 with AS150 coating (Usibor® AluSi coating)
- 22MnB5 with Z140 coating (hot dip galvanized)

These products are extensively used in the automotive industry. The thickness of each plate was in the range of what is classically used for manufacturing of car body: 0.8 mm for CRS, 1.2 mm for HSS and 1.5 mm for PHS.

Sixteen configurations were assembled with these materials. The list is given in Table 1.

Table 1: details of the 16 combinations

Combination code	Sample design	Joining techniques	Grade 1	Grade 2
1	LS	RSW	DC04	DC04
2	LS	RSW	DC04	DX56+Z100
3	LS	RSW	DX56+Z100	DX56+Z100
4	LS	RSW	DX56+ZF110	DX56+ZF110
5	LS	RSW	DX54+ZM100	DX54+ZM100
6	LS	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
7	TP	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
8	LS	RSW	22MnB5+AS150	22MnB5+AS150
9	LS	RSW	22MnB5+Z140	22MnB5+Z140
10	LS	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
11	TP	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
12	LS	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	HCT780C+ZE
13	TP	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	HCT780C+ZE
14	LS	Adhesive	22MnB5+Z140	22MnB5+Z140
15	LS	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
16	TP	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100

4480 panels were manufactured and 2240 specimens were assembled (140 for each of the 16 combinations). After the assembling procedure, all specimens were painting according to the BMW

e-coating process with degreasing, phosphating and passivation followed by cathodic dip coating with additional primary coat for outdoor exposure conditions (natural and vehicle expositions).

All materials and joined samples were characterized using chemical analysis, optical microscope, micro-hardness testing, tensile testing, differential scanning calorimetry and thermo-mechanical analysis. Properties of the materials were in accordance with their specifications. Characterization of the spot welds showed also that the minimum specified diameter was reached in all cases with correct hardness profiles. The properties of the Betamate 1460S adhesive were extensively investigated and both the physical and mechanical properties were determined.

Tensile testing for each combination was performed to measure the maximum tensile load and the tensile energy absorption. Spot welded specimens were tested at a constant displacement rate of around 10 +/- 2 mm/min. All measured values and failure modes for spot welded specimens corresponded with earlier studies on unalloyed and high strength steels. For adhesive specimens, tensile tests were performed at lower displacement rate, from 0.6 to 1.3 mm/min. The maximum tensile load was systematically higher than for spot welded specimens. However, the energy absorbed until failure of the assemblies was of the same order of magnitude. As expected, TP specimens, whatever the joining techniques, showed lower mechanical properties than LS ones.

To assess localization of the damage in adhesive bonded specimens under quasi-static load and fatigue conditions, the back-face strain technique was applied on some specimens. Results were used as entry parameters of the simulation of fatigue of adhesive bonded joints using cohesive elements.

1.4 WP 4 Long term corrosion properties of joined samples

The objectives of WP4 were to obtain reliable data on the corrosion and mechanical performance of joined materials in real conditions including on-vehicle exposures and exposure in stationary field sites, to assess the corrosion resistance and the mechanical properties of fatigue pre-loaded joined materials on vehicle and in marine atmosphere.

Specimens with and without fatigue preloading were exposed under a vehicle and at the marine station of Brest. The fatigue preloading prior to outdoor exposure consisted in 300,000 cycles performed at load amplitude corresponding to 50 % probable failure at 1 million cycles, determined from S-N curves in the WP5. This fatigue preloading was responsible of slight reduction of the tensile properties with higher scattering of the results with probable crack initiation and less adhesive.

The mobile exposure under an experimental vehicle from BMW, located in the Munich area, Germany, and driving most of the time in Southern Germany and North of Austria where deicing salt is used, has started in May 2013 and ended in January 2015. The duration of the test was 600 days, so that the samples experimented two winter periods with spreading of deicing salt on roads. The mileage of the vehicle was 50,000 km at the end of the exposure. Exposure at the marine station of Brest was conducted at the same period as vehicle exposure.

As a general trend, materials were less affected after 2 years outdoor exposure in marine atmosphere or on the vehicle than during accelerated tests (WP5 and WP6). No effect from the preloading could be observed. It is obvious that longer exposure durations should be conducted to induce more degradation. Moreover, for the vehicle exposure, winter 2013/2014 was rather warm and less salt have been used on roads in upper Austria and South Germany compared to other winters. On the contrary, 2014/2015 winter was normal considering the quantity of salt used in Austria.

Some adhesive bonded specimens showed important strength loss after tensile testing of samples exposed at the marine station, but not for specimens exposed under the vehicle. A cumulative effect of fatigue preloading and exposure to corrosive environments could be observed on the loss of mechanical properties of adhesive bonded assemblies. Relative humidity plays a key role in the degradation of the properties of these assemblies.

1.5 WP 5 Pure fatigue and corrosion testing

The objectives of WP5 were to evaluate the mechanical properties of the joints in pure fatigue conditions, to assess the mechanical properties and the corrosion resistance of the joined materials under accelerated corrosion testing condition, to study the effect of key parameters on the mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of joined samples and to obtain data for input into modeling as defined in WP7.

1.5.1 Fatigue tests in air

For the fatigue testing in air, the S/N curves allowed a classification of the different joining methods and geometry of joints. First, the lap-shear joints may be related to the endurance limit (number of load cycles $< 2 \cdot 10^6$) and classified in order of decreasing fatigue life, as summarized below for lap-shear configuration:

Adhesive bonding	>	Spot welding for mild and high-strength steels	>	Spot welding for press-hardened steels
$k \approx 7-9$		$k \approx 4 - 6$		$k \approx 3$

With the increase in strength of the material, the k-value (slope of the Wöhler curve) decreased slightly. Low k-values indicated a high notch sensitivity of the joint. Highest k-values were reached with adhesive-bonded joints.

For T-peel configurations the following classification was obtained:

Adhesive bonding	>	Spot welding
$k \approx 8 - 10$		$k \approx 3,5$

These fatigue tests give results corresponding with earlier studies and characterized by typical average scattering. This aspect provided a good reference point for the fatigue tests on samples with corrosion cycles in order to evaluate loss of performances in WP6 and for the Finite Element model calibration of WP7. Moreover, the characteristic S/N curves were the basis for determination of the fatigue preloading level for WP4.

1.5.2 Key climatic parameters in accelerated corrosion tests

Regarding the influence of key parameters on the corrosion performance of joined materials, 6 different conditions were proposed, and three replicates were tested for each combination. The tests were conducted at constant temperature (either 30 or 45°C) and included two cycles. Cycle A started by a salt spray at either 1 or 5 wt % NaCl, followed by a drying phase of 4 hours at 50% R.H. and 4 hours wetting at 95% R.H. A ramp of 2 hours was followed between the humidity changes. This cycle A was repeated either twice a week (SF2) on Monday and Friday or every day (SF7) so that the same salt load was applied during the week. In test conditions with two sprays per week, cycle A alternated with a wet and dry cycle (4h at 50% / 4h at 95%). In one test variant (SC1/SF2/T30/F1/D1), a daily wet/dry cycle was replaced by a freezing phase at -25°C (Wednesday). Finally, another test variant (SC1/SF2/T30/F0/D3) included a drying ratio of 3 which implied a longer drying phase e.g. 6h at 50% and a shorter wetting time at 95% of 2 h. The test duration was 12 weeks. Additional tests were also performed on few combinations (1, 3, 10 and 12) with a longer time of exposure in T45 condition (24 and 30 weeks, instead of 12 weeks).

An evaluation procedure was defined to characterize cosmetic corrosion, crevice corrosion, perforating corrosion and tensile strength loss after corrosion exposure.

Results from cosmetic corrosion showed that degradation was strongly linked to salt deposition and average temperature. The observations were quite similar for all configurations. The salt deposition was found to be the main parameter that controls the cosmetic corrosion rate.

The extent of red rust in the overlap and the perforating corrosion were particularly observed for the bare material DC04, with a large influence of the temperature. Salt spray frequency and salt spray concentrations showed only slight effect on zinc coating materials.

After corrosion exposure, the strength loss of spot welded specimens was quite low, meaning that exposure was not long or aggressive enough to reduce the tensile load. For adhesive bonded specimens, a decrease in tensile properties could be reached and was imputable to a loss of adhesion at the interface adhesive/coating by a delamination process in the presence of water, oxygen and chlorides. The degradation was enhanced by increasing salt frequency and salt concentration. Rising temperature to 45°C had also a deleterious impact on adhesive samples, increasing strength loss and adhesive failure. Results are summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Increase of adhesive failure in adhesive bonded samples after corrosion testing.

1.5.3 Performance of automotive corrosion tests

The standardized corrosion test VDA 233-102 (NVDA) was conducted on unloaded samples. As for tests in task 5.2, three replicates by combination were exposed in NVDA during 12 weeks. Crevice corrosion, perforating corrosion and the residual tensile strength were evaluated. As for other corrosion tests, the DC04 material was particularly affected by the test. Then, the mechanical properties of spot welded specimens remained similar as reference specimens. On the contrary, adhesive specimens were strongly affected with a strength loss correlated to increase of adhesive failure.

To conclude on pure corrosion exposure of spot weld specimens, the strength loss was very close in NVDA and T45 conditions. The temperature plays the most important role by increasing the corrosion rate of the steel (for uncoated materials at least). Concerning adhesive specimens, no exact correlation could be drawn compared to previous tests. Indeed, the mechanical strength of each combination seemed to be not sensitive to the same environmental parameters. As a result, the sensitivity in NVDA condition was in an intermediate range compared to previous climatic conditions, without very large strength loss as it can be observed in SC5SF7 or T45 conditions. Results are compared in Figure 3.

Compared to results on the vehicle or at the marine station (WP4) the strength loss was more important after 12 weeks in NVDA than almost 2 years in the real climatic conditions.

Figure 3: Comparison strength loss after some corrosion tests (1-9 spot welded specimens; 10-14 adhesive bonded specimens; 15-16 adhesive + spot weld).

1.6 WP 6 Combined fatigue corrosion testing

The objectives of WP6 were to evaluate the influence of combined fatigue loading and environmental exposure on the corrosion resistance of the joints, to study the effects of key environmental parameters on combined corrosion-fatigue, to obtain a database on corrosion-fatigue for materials with high potential applications in the automotive industry, to define a testing procedure and to obtain data for input into modeling as defined in WP7.

1.6.1 Key climatic parameters in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion

Simultaneous fatigue-corrosion testing was performed on a limited number of assemblies for a maximum of four extreme testing conditions defined in WP2 (Basic, SC5SF7, T45 and F1 but only for adhesive bonded specimens). The pneumatic corrosion-fatigue equipment developed for the project was used in climatic chambers.

From the results obtained on spot welded specimens, it was concluded that the fatigue in corrosive environment was decreased at high applied loads, whereas it was the contrary at lower load levels. No large effect of environmental parameters selected in the present study was established, salt frequency and concentration increase being slightly more deleterious to the fatigue life than temperature increase. The variation of fatigue in corrosive environment was explained by corrosion products formation around the spot-weld, which changed the local mean stress and then limits the stress and strain amplitudes at low applied load. The increase of the fatigue life could be also explained by the blunting of the micro-cracks formed at the notch tip, which reduced the local stress concentration.

For adhesive specimens, the results indicated an obvious sensitivity of adhesive bonding to the corrosive environment. The strongest influence was due to the temperature, followed by salt spray concentration and the frequency of salt spray. This is true in the selected range and parameters and for the tested configurations.

1.6.2 Simultaneous fatigue-corrosion

All combinations were tested by simultaneous fatigue-corrosion in NVDA conditions using the pneumatic devices.

For all spot-welded combinations, the fatigue behavior in corrosive environment was quite similar. Compared to tests in air, the fatigue life was decreased at high applied load and increased at lower load. As for combination tested in task 6.1, the variation of fatigue in corrosive environment can be explained either by corrosion products formation around the spot-weld, which changes and then limits the stress and strain amplitudes at low applied load, or/and by blunting of the crack tip.

For adhesive specimens the fatigue life was quite reduced compared to tests in air. This reduction was correlated with a large increase of the adhesive failure. Thus, the interface coating/adhesive is affected by the corrosive environment, which reduces the fatigue life. The diffusion of moisture in the overlap is probably a critical parameter.

Concerning specimens with adhesive and spot weld, the fatigue life was also fairly reduced during simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. The behavior was very close to adhesive specimens. Thus, the spot-weld seems to have no beneficial effect for the fatigue resistance of the assembly in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests as the primary fatigue strength is mainly brought by the adhesive.

1.6.3 Alternated fatigue-corrosion

Tests with sequential fatigue loading and corrosion exposure were performed on restricted number of combinations. Load levels were selected based on results from the fatigue testing in air (WP5).

For spot welded lap-shear specimens, no failure was reported in alternated fatigue-corrosion below the average number of cycles observed for fatigue testing in air. Thus, no deleterious effect of alternated fatigue-corrosion was noticed. For the tested spot welded T-peel configuration, despite the dispersion of the results due to low mechanical resistance of this assembly, it was observed that the fatigue life was reduced at high applied load and increased at low applied load. Corrosion at the notch tip of the spot weld could occur due to the residual gap opening obtained during the fatigue loading, confirmed by finite elements analysis.

For adhesive bonded lap-shear specimens, it was observed that the average fatigue failure occurred after 4 to 5 cycles (i.e. more or less 2/3 of the fatigue life in air). The embrittlement was to water diffusion in the overlap of the specimens during the NVDA cycle. Indeed, in the presence of moisture, the fracture energy of adhesive is reduced. However, simultaneous fatigue-corrosion was more aggressive than alternated fatigue-corrosion for lap-shear adhesive specimens also. For the adhesive bonding T-peel configurations, the fatigue failure occurred after more or less 2 to 3 corrosion cycles. Again, this is probably linked to moisture diffusion in the overlap, as no red rust was observed on the fracture surface. Moreover, T-peel with adhesive bonding failed before lap-shear specimens. This could be explained by the exposure of the specimens in the corrosion chamber. Indeed, lap-shear specimens were exposed with an angle of 20° with the normal direction, whereas T-peel specimens were exposed with an angle of 70° (20° with the floor of the cabinet). Thus, water can be more easily retained at the surface of the adhesive and increase moisture in the adhesive of T-peel assemblies. The mechanical state played also an important role in the fracture mechanism.

Finally, for the spot welded and adhesive bonded specimens, a very slight beneficial effect was reported compared to pure adhesive bonded specimens.

1.6.4 Conclusions of WP6

As a conclusion of the fatigue-corrosion investigation, the behaviors of specimens in alternated or simultaneous fatigue-corrosion modes were quite different, as illustrated in Figure 4. However, it is difficult to assess which one is more representative of the behavior of an automotive component.

For spot-weld specimens, even under severe conditions of simultaneous fatigue-corrosion, the loss of mechanical properties was not very important. In alternated fatigue-corrosion mode, variations were quite small and probably covered by security coefficient from design.

In the case of adhesive specimens, the diffusion of moisture seems the main degradation parameter, which depends upon exposure conditions and mechanical loadings. Protection should be applied to limit this diffusion.

Figure 4: Representative fatigue behavior of spot weld (configuration 6) and adhesive bonded (configuration 10) specimens in air, during alternated and simultaneous fatigue-corrosion loading.

1.7 WP 7 Modeling

The objectives of WP7 were to evaluate stress and strain fields in samples under fatigue loading, including effect of residual stresses and corrosion on fatigue life of spot-welded and adhesive bonded samples and to predict fatigue and corrosion-fatigue results using existing design rules and/or models. The modeling was based on all fatigue results compiled from WP5 and WP6.

1.7.1 Modeling spot welded specimens

Finite element computations was performed to evaluate stress/strain fields and load carrying capacities of spot weld joints as well as to determine quantitatively parameters representing fatigue performances of the spot welds. The notch stress approach was selected as it can take into account influence of local geometry. This analysis can only be performed using finite element analysis.

A parametric model was created to be run in batch mode using the Finite Element Software ANSYS™. This procedure was necessary because a very large number of linear and nonlinear analysis runs had to be calculated using the model for the different specimen and load levels. The stress convergence, accuracy and efficiency of the models for lap-shear and T-peel specimens were systematically checked and validated for further investigations. The effect from boundary conditions was also checked and demonstrated a strong influence on the notch stress.

Fatigue testing in air was simulated using the model. Analyses based on the principal stress and the von Mises equivalent stress were performed. Results were compared to the FAT630/3 (630 = allowable stress cycle for $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ and 3 = the slope exponent of the SN-curve) and FAT560/3 for the principal stress approach and the von Mises equivalent stress approach, respectively. From this investigation, it can be observed that the slope $m_1=3$ and scatter band do not show reasonable behavior. However, as a general trend, the S-N curves demonstrated high conservatism compared to the reference FAT classes. All notch stress values were above the recommended FAT-class for "moderately to thick" welds including an assumed slope exponent m_1 equal to 3. Large displacement analysis reduces notch stresses by about 3 to 12% for the specimen and loads investigated in this project. Differences were larger for smaller load levels (since all materials have the same modulus of elasticity). Conservatism with respect to the FAT-class seems to be less pronounced for large displacement results. Using large displacement results required a suitable large displacement FAT-class. Even though, notch stresses from large displacement analysis are little lower than obtained by linear geometric theory, those results were still higher than the allowable stress ranges for "moderately to thick" welds.

The same analysis was performed for the fatigue-corrosion tests. Reduction of fatigue life in the corrosive environments as experimentally obtained in WP6 was not important. Mainly simultaneous fatigue-corrosion testing reduced fatigue life under corrosive environments. This can be seen in the notch stress results as well. The results for corrosive environments were a little non conservative for few cases in low cycle range ($< 100,000$ cycles) but they still seemed conservative in high cycle range. The latter conclusion need to be used carefully though since further investigations at stress ranges below 1400 MPa (principal stress range) and 1200 MPa (von Mises equivalent stress range) would be required to check the behavior in those stress ranges as well. Since corrosion has a time depending effect, further reductions in fatigue life in those stress ranges could be expected. Corrosive environment required a specific FAT-class for the notch stress concept as developed in WP8.

As a conclusion, effective notch stresses for maximum principal stress range and von Mises equivalent stress range required the definition of specific FAT-classes compared to existing recommendations based on "moderately to thick" welds. The same holds true, if analyses differentiate between small and large displacements due to pronounced deformation behavior of thin walled structures (i.e. due to significant rotation of weld nugget for lap-shear specimen). Large displacement analyses of the specimen used within the present work are 3 to 12 % smaller than results from small displacements. Large displacement analyses in practice of body development would thus require also special FAT-classes to be used.

The effective notch stress approach has been demonstrated to be a suitable empirical approach to consider different environmental conditions in the assessment of fatigue life of thin walled spot-welded structures. All results are summarized in Figure 5. A unique formalism with parameters based on the IIW recommendations has been used for both the fatigue and the fatigue-corrosion results. However, different parameters can be chosen to fit fatigue and fatigue-corrosion experimental data as demonstrated later in WP8.

Figure 5: Von Mises notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$, small displacement analysis; specimen 1-9.

1.7.2 Modeling adhesive specimens

Tensile and fatigue properties of adhesive specimens were modeled using the cohesive zone model. This methodology is based on a traction-separation curve described by various parameters such as the initial stiffness, the tripping traction and the fracture energy. Such parameters must be obtained experimentally by monitoring tensile and fatigue tests, taking into consideration the fracture initiation phase.

In a first approach, it was planned to use a single set of parameter for all combinations as the same adhesive was used in all cases. However, from the inverse calibration of the tensile tests in air, it appears that the steel substrate played a role in the properties of the bond. Thus, 3 sets of parameters were obtained to simulate tensile properties of the 3 adhesively bonded steels, keeping the same parameters for the lap-shear or T-peel combinations assembled from the same steel.

The strain gauge technique was used to determine early adhesive failure. However, local numerical data was not in good agreement with local strain obtained by this technique. Thus, adhesive properties were fitted using only tensile tests. Then, a large effort was done to calibrate the fatigue parameters of the cohesive zone model. However, no practical methodology was finally obtained from the investigations. This method seemed to be not suitable for the development of a practical tool for the adhesive joints design. More development is required to take into account adhesive failure due to fatigue and corrosion by using cohesive element elimination procedure in the simulation. This was checked for one combination to prove that this approach is correct.

1.8 WP 8 Life prediction and application guidelines

The objectives of the WP8 were to determine the relevant data and methods that can be used for the life prediction of spot welded and adhesive bonded structures submitted to fatigue and corrosion, and to show the methodology to use them for the design of automotive joints.

For spot welded structures, it was shown that the notch stress approach was a suitable method to assess the fatigue life of spot welded steel. Moreover, a new FAT-class was determined, which showed better agreement with the fatigue and fatigue-corrosion data than the recommended usual parameters. Such method could be a response to the demand of improved methods that can take into consideration the effects of the atmospheric corrosion. Finally, the transfer of this concept from

a single spot weld to large automotive structures is possible and easy, because no "unusual" feature is required for the creation of the simulation model. Indeed, existing applications can be used.

For adhesive bonding, the methodology to obtain the correct parameters of the model remained quite complex and time consuming. This method was found not suitable for direct applications in the automotive design, even if tools for the end user can be developed based on finite elements simulations using 3D shell coarser elements as for automotive components. However, with the implementation of an additional subroutine that modeled element elimination, the model can reproduce quite accurately the fatigue damage during fatigue-corrosion.

2 Scientific and technical achievements

2.1 *Objective of the project*

Technological innovative aspects

- For the first time, fatigue tests under cyclic corrosion testing chamber that allows simultaneous fatigue loading in an accelerated corrosion test will be performed.
- The simultaneous corrosion and fatigue performance of high performance steels used for the body in white will be for the first time addressed in a systematic way.
- The corrosion performance and mechanical properties of joined specimens involving novel Zn-Al-Mg coated steel will be evaluated, which is of major importance for the acceptance of such new coating in the automotive industry.
- Models for predicting corrosion-fatigue life time of joined materials including advanced high strength steels will be established.
- Design guidelines including the corrosion behavior of joined steel products that could be incorporated in computer aided engineering (CAE) codes for the evaluation of fatigue performance will be developed. This will allow a reduction of engineering, development and validation time, costs for implementation of new materials, joining techniques and corrosion protection systems. This will obviously reduce the time to market for the steel industry.

Scientific aspects

- A systematic study on the influence of key environmental parameters on the corrosion-fatigue performance of joined steel based materials will be conducted in order to provide input data for modeling of corrosion-fatigue.
- Better understandings of the mechanisms of initiation and propagation of fatigue cracks/failure of joints in corrosive environments will be developed.
- The influence of different loading parameters such as load rate, frequency or load ratio, on the corrosion-fatigue strength will be evaluated and S/N curves (stress versus cycles to failure) will be generated.
- The Influence of residual stresses on corrosion fatigue properties of joints under elastic cyclic loads at corrosive environment will be evaluated.
- The Type of failure mode and crack path for corrosion fatigue will be defined.

2.2 Description of activities and discussion

2.2.1 WP1 Management

The objective of work package WP1 was to maintain communications with the European Commission, to ensure smooth progression of the project and to establish good communication strategies and enable effective sharing of information, rapid auditing of project performance and solving of problems. Six joint project meetings were planned and realized in addition to 2 phone meetings were organized (see Table 2). Minutes were provided as additional deliverables to the working group.

Table 2: list of meetings organized in Autofatcor project

Meeting Nr	Date	Location
1 (Kickoff)	10/07/2011	Munich
2	23-24/04/2012	Maizières Les Metz
3	29/05/2012	Phone meeting
4	29/10/2012	Phone meeting
5	14-15/01/2013	Rome
6	8-9/10/2013	Linz
7	18-19/02/2014	Munich
8	24-25/11/2014	Brest

2.2.2 WP2 Definition of fatigue loading and testing conditions

The objectives of the work package WP2 were to define the corrosion testing conditions, the fatigue parameters and the sample designs. All testing conditions were selected for tasks 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3 as well as sample designs and fatigue loading.

2.2.2.1 Task 2.1: Corrosion testing selection

N-VDA test (VDA 233-102) was proposed as the main standardized accelerated corrosion test for tasks 5.3, 6.2 and 6.3. N-VDA test has been developed by the German association of automotive industry (VDA) together with the German steel association (VDEh) in order to replace the standard test VDA 621-415. NVDA test has been selected for its much better correlation to field data. As shown in Figure 6, N-VDA test is based on 3 different cycles which alternate during a week. In particular, this test includes a freezing phase at -15°C (cycle C) and a lower salt concentration than in VDA 621-415 i.e. NaCl 1wt% instead of 5wt%. While the normal test duration is 6 weeks, the test was extended to 12 weeks for the present project as it was believed that 6 weeks will be too short to induce sufficient degradations that would further alter the mechanical properties of the joints.

Figure 6: Description of N-VDA (VDA233-102) test.

Regarding the influence of key parameters on the fatigue and corrosion performance of joined materials, a simple test conducted at a constant temperature with wet and dry cycles was proposed. Using a simple cycle test, it should indeed be easier to extract the influence of key parameters on the corrosion/fatigue resistance of materials. The key parameters summarized in Table 3 were

proposed. By varying these climatic parameters, the test matrix given in Table 4 was proposed. Figure 7 shows examples of test cycles for the influence of key parameters.

Table 3: list of selected key parameters and their levels.

Parameter	Level -	Level +	
Concentration of NaCl for salt spray, wt% [SC]	1 wt %	5 wt %	pH neutral (as in N-VDA test)
Frequency of salt spray application per week [SF]	2	7	Same total salt load per week
Temperature [T]	30 °C	45 °C	Constant unless in salt spray (=30 °C)
24-hour-long freezing phase [F]	0	1	-25°C (as in BMW SCAB test)
Drying ratio [D] = Drying time / wetting time	1	3	Drying level 50% RH Wetting level 95% RH D=1: 4h 50 %/4h 95 % D=3: 6h 50 %/2h 95 %

Table 4: Initial proposal of test matrix derived from the selected key climatic parameters.

Parameters	Salt concentration, (wt %) SC	Salt frequency per week - SF	Temp, °C - T	Freezing phase of 24h - F	Drying ratio - D	Label
SC1/SF2/T30/F0/D1	1	2	30	0	1	Basic test
SC5 /SF2/T30/F0/D1	5	2	30	0	1	SC5 test
SC1/ SF7 /T30/F0/D1	1	7	30	0	1	SF7 test
SC5/SF7 /T30/F0/D1	5	7	30	0	1	SC5-SF7 test
SC1/SF2/ T45 /F0/D1	1	2	45	0	1	T45 test
SC1/SF2/T30/ F1 /D1	1	2	30	1	1	F1 test
SC1/SF2/T30/F0/ D3	1	2	30	0	3	D3 test

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
SCx/SF2/T30/ F0 /D1	Cycle A	Cycle B	Cycle B	Cycle B	Cycle A	Cycle B	Cycle B
SCx/SF2/T30/ F1 /D1	Cycle A	Cycle B	-15 or -25°C	Cycle B	Cycle A	Cycle B	Cycle B

x = 1 or 5

Figure 7: basic test cycles of tests with a frequency of salt application SF2 and drying D1. For test cycles at 45°C (T45), similar test cycles are applied at 50°C unless during the salt spray phase (30°C).

Figure 8: Basic cycle for tests SF7 and SC5-SF7.

2.2.2.2 Task 2.2: Definition of fatigue loading parameters and sample design.

2.2.2.2.1 Fatigue parameters

The pneumatic fatigue devices for simultaneous corrosion fatigue (tasks 6.1 and 6.2) present some limitations in comparison to conventional fatigue machines, e.g. maximum frequency of 0.5 Hz and tensile load range of 0-3500 N. Fatigue tests in air (task 5.1) and in alternating corrosion fatigue conditions (task 6.3) were performed on conventional fatigue machines with higher load capacities and at higher frequencies.

The following parameters were selected:

- Loading ratio of 0.1, additional tests might be performed at another load ratio on adhesive samples;
- Stop criteria: complete failure of sample or 2 million cycles (i.e. about 7 weeks of test at 0.5 Hz).

Two methods of alternated fatigue and corrosion testing were adopted:

- Method 1: in total, 6 NVDA cycles were conducted at 6 equal intervals during the fatigue life found in air (between $3 \cdot 10^5$ and $1,8 \cdot 10^6$ cycles for four different load levels); this method allows to estimate the fatigue life in terms of VDA233-102 cycles prior to failure (6 cycles corresponding to the fatigue life in air); Example of tests following method 1 is provided in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Method 1 for alternated fatigue-corrosion.

- Method 2: it allows a comparison with task 6.2 (based on the same number of cycles for VDA233-102 cycle between combined and alternated fatigue tests): $3 \cdot 10^5$ load cycles are conducted between each VDA233-102 cycle at 2 different loads or at 3.5 kN the maximum loading capacity of the devices

used in tasks 6.1 and 6.2 (case of combinations n°10, 12 and 14). The load level leading to $1,8 \cdot 10^6$ cycles was common with the method 1.

Fatigue tests for alternated fatigue-corrosion or fatigue in air were performed on hydraulic fatigue machines at a frequency of 30 Hz and a load ratio of 0.1.

2.2.2.2.2 Sample design

Lap shear and T-peel designs of samples were selected as these designs of samples may be tested in the simultaneous fatigue/corrosion tests. Regarding joining techniques, resistance spot welding (RSW), adhesive bonding and a combination of RSW & adhesive bonding were proposed.

Since the pneumatic fatigue devices for simultaneous corrosion fatigue testing at IC has a load capacity limited to 3500 N, it was decided to select single-spot-welded samples rather than multi-spot-welded ones. Upon the joining technique, two widths of samples were selected i.e. 25 and 45 mm. In both cases, the overlapped width was 20 mm. Since the sample's width could have an effect on fatigue and corrosion-fatigue resistance of the samples, results from different joining techniques were compared. But comparisons were made between, corrosion, fatigue and corrosion fatigue in the different conditions for a given joining technique. Figure 10 presents schematic drawings of the different sample designs.

Figure 10: Schematic drawings of the samples.

2.2.3 WP3 Manufacturing of the samples and characterization

The main objectives of WP3 were to provide materials and join them, to characterize all materials and joint structures, to apply surface treatment and paint and to define the mechanical properties of the assemblies. Eight different materials were selected for further manufacturing of 16 different joined samples according to designs defined in task 2.2.

2.2.3.1 Task 3.1: Material selection

Table 5 summarizes the materials selected for the present project. They integrated cold rolled steel with different metallic coatings including a new metallic coating $ZnAl_2Mg_2$. Two variants of high strength steels both zinc coated and two press hardening steels also with a metallic coating were selected.

Table 5: list of the selected steel grades

Designation	Name	Grade code	Coating	Thickness (mm)	Supplier
Cold Rolled Steel (CRS)	DC04	1a	Bare	0.8	voestalpine
	DX56+ZF110	1b	ZF (7.5 μ m galvanized)	0.8	voestalpine
	DX54+ZM100	1c	ZM ($ZnAl_2Mg_2$ 7.5 μ m)	0.8	voestalpine
	DX56+Z100	1d	Z (7.5 μ m hot dip galvanized)	0.8	voestalpine
High Strength Steel (HSS)	HC420LA+Z100	2	Z (7.5 μ m hot dip galvanized)	1.2	ArcelorMittal
	HCT780C+ZE	3	ZE 75/75 (7.5 μ m electro galvanized)	1.2	ArcelorMittal
Press Hardened Steel (PHS)	22MnB5+AS150	4a	AluSi coated (25 μ m)	1.5	ArcelorMittal
	22MnB5+Z140	4b	Z (10 μ m hot dip galvanized)	1.5	voestalpine

The selected thicknesses for these steel based materials correspond to thicknesses that are classically used in the automotive industry. Since it would be difficult to compare results from materials with different thicknesses, results were compared only inside each family of steels i.e. CRS, HSS and PHS.

Cold rolled selected grades correspond to non-alloyed mild steels, ferritic microstructures, which are designed for deep drawing applications. These products are used extensively in the automotive industry both for visible and structural parts.

High Strength Low Alloy steel grade HC420LA (code 2) is cold rolled hardened by a combination of precipitation and grain size refining, resulting in high strength with low alloy content. This steel exhibits neither weld zone softening nor grain coarsening in resistance spot-welding. This grade is particularly suitable for structural components and reinforcement parts. For its yield strength level of 420 MPa, this steel exhibits good cold forming possibilities.

The complex phase cold rolled HCT780C grade (code 3) is a very high strength steel. This steel is cold formed to make lightweight structural simple shape components (slightly deformed). It offers high as-delivered yield strength and good bendability and stretch flangeability, particularly well-suited for automotive safety components requiring good impact strength.

In order to meet safety requirements in terms of crash performances and the environmental regulation about fuel efficiency and CO₂ emissions, the demand for very high strength steels for hot stamping, i.e. Press Hardened Steels, is increasing in the automotive industry. These materials permit to produce complex structural components devoid of springback with thicknesses much thinner (thus lighter) than other high strength steels for cold forming. For these applications, ArcelorMittal has developed an aluminized boron steel (based on a 22MnB5 chemistry) [1] commercialized under the trade name of Usibor® (further named 22MnB5+AS150). The final automotive part has a fully martensitic microstructure and exhibits a Tensile Strength of around 1500MPa. For additional cathodic protection, ArcelorMittal and voestalpine also developed zinc pre-coated steels for hot stamping. voestalpine phs-ultraform® galvanized PHS (further named 22MnB5+Z140) product is dedicated to the indirect hot stamping process. It involves a preliminary cold forming step, whose deformation rate is almost 100%. This is followed by the austenitizing heat treatment. The second transfer into the forming tool consists of calibration and hardening by die quenching. At the end of the hot stamping process, the component must be slightly shot or sand blasted in order to remove aluminum oxides from the surface and to ensure good paintability. For this project, flat tools were used in order to get flat samples.

2.2.3.2 Task 3.2: Joining techniques and manufacturing of the joined samples

Conventional joining techniques used by car manufacturers were selected: resistance spot-welding (RSW), adhesive bonding and combination of both techniques. Each combination corresponded to a type of specimen (Lap-Shear or T-Peel) joining 2 panels according to a defined technique. The details of the 16 combinations are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: details of the 16 combinations

Combination code	Sample design	Joining techniques	Grade 1	Grade 2	Joining responsible
1	LS	RSW	DC04	DC04	voestalpine
2	LS	RSW	DC04	DX56+Z100	voestalpine
3	LS	RSW	DX56+Z100	DX56+Z100	voestalpine
4	LS	RSW	DX56+ZF110	DX56+ZF110	voestalpine
5	LS	RSW	DX54+ZM100	DX54+ZM100	voestalpine
6	LS	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	ArcelorMittal
7	TP	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	ArcelorMittal
8	LS	RSW	22MnB5+AS150	22MnB5+AS150	ArcelorMittal
9	LS	RSW	22MnB5+Z140	22MnB5+Z140	voestalpine
10	LS	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	BMW
11	TP	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	BMW
12	LS	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	HCT780C+ZE	BMW
13	TP	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	HCT780C+ZE	BMW
14	LS	Adhesive	22MnB5+Z140	22MnB5+Z140	BMW
15	LS	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	BMW
16	TP	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100	BMW

All the 4480 panels for manufacturing the 2240 specimens (140 for each of the 16 combinations) were prepared by voestalpine and ArcelorMittal, following the following stages: recovering of steel sheets, heat treated for PHS grades, cutting of samples according the specimens dimensions (length and width, see Figure 10), drilling of samples extremities for holding during painting (e-coating), on-vehicle exposition and simultaneous corrosion-fatigue tests, 90° bending for T-peel specimens, joining as indicated in Table 6, painting by BMW on their e-coating process line. Caution was taken to get minimal burr height when shearing the samples. ArcelorMittal used a very precise guillotine shear for cutting the samples (configurations 6 to 8, 10 to 13 and 15 to 16) allowing a very fine and low cutting clearance and avoiding excessive burr on cut edge. Samples cut edges present a burr height below 50 µm.

2.2.3.2.1 Resistance spot welding

All the Resistance Spot-Welds (including the last configurations Adhesive+RSW) were made in order to reach a spot-weld diameter between 5 and 6mm. The welding conditions in terms of combinations (homogeneous or heterogeneous used grades), electrode type, electrode force, welding time, holding time, welding current and current type are provided in Table 7.

Table 7: Resistance Spot-Welding conditions of configurations 1 to 9 (RSW), 15 and 16 (Adhesive+RSW)

Configuration code	Electrode type	Electrode force (kN)	Welding time (ms)	Holding time (ms)	Current (kA)	I _{eff.}	DC AC
1	F16 5.5mm	2.1	140	120	7.5		DC
2	F16 5.5mm	2.3	200	120	8.5		DC
3	F16 5.5mm	2.3	200	120	8.7		DC
4	F16 5.5mm	2.3	200	120	8.1		DC
5	F16 5.5mm	2.3	200	120	8.1		DC
6&7	G0-16 6mm	4.0	320	320	7.6		AC 50Hz
8	F16 5.5mm	4.5	380	300	5.8		AC 50Hz
9	F16 5.5mm	3.5	350+400	200	5+6.8		DC
15&16	G0-16 6mm	4.0	320	320	7.6		AC 50Hz

2.2.3.2.2 Adhesive bonding

Both samples were re-oiled with Fuchs PL 3802-39S (3g/m²) and bonded together in an overlapping manner with adhesive Betamate 1460S from DOW. The bonding gap is 0.3mm. For fixing the bonding gap correspondingly, large glass pearls were used, which were scattered before the joining and squeezing on the applied adhesive on one side. The bonding was then cured in a laboratory oven during 25min at 175°C and, afterwards, stored for the simulation of the subsequent ovens another 1 hour at 160°C.

2.2.3.2.3 Painting

The painting was achieved by BMW on their e-coating line following an industrial process. The specimens were firstly surface treated (degreasing, phosphating and passivation), then cathodic dip coated followed by a primary coat (for natural or vehicle expositions). Table 8 provides the detailed information.

Table 8: Detailed information of the painting by e-coating at BMW (e-coat thickness adjusted by voltage and coating time)

Step	Supplier	Description
Surface treatment	Chemetall	Degreasing + Phosphating + Passivation
Cathodic dip coating	PPG	thickness 15 - 25µm
Primer coat	BASF	thickness 20 - 55µm

2.2.3.3 Task 3.3: Metallographic characterization

All joined samples were characterized including both the base material and the joints. On the base metal including metallic coating, the mechanical characteristics, the coating thickness and composition as well as the steel microstructure were evaluated according to conventional methods used by the steel industry. Regarding the joint, the integrity of the welded joints e.g. nugget diameter for spot weld and the microstructure of the joint (heat affected zone, melting zone); the micro-hardness was investigated on cross-sections. The properties of the adhesive were characterized

regarding the stiffness, the elastic behavior (glass transition temperature). The following techniques were used: optical microscope, micro-hardness machine, Differential Scanning Calorimetry or Thermo-Mechanical Analysis.

Characterization of materials and spot welded materials were carried out by the materials suppliers using conventional techniques (ArcelorMittal & voestalpine). CSM characterized the adhesive bonded materials.

2.2.3.3.1 Characterization of grades

This section provides all the information of selected grades:

- the chemical analysis,
- the mechanical properties in available directions (rolling, transverse, 45°): thickness, Yield Stress, Tensile Strength, Uniformed Elongation, Total Elongation and, when there is a yielding plateau, higher & lower elastic limit Re_H & Re_L , Yielding Plateau Elongation,
- the microstructure (microscopy with etching to reveal it),
- the coating information: type of coating, coating weight (designation and measured), chemistry and microscopy and, when relevant adding information on coating are provided.

The chemical compositions of the steel grades are reported in Table 9, while the mechanical properties of cold rolled steels, high strength steels and press hardened steels are reported in Table 10, Table 11 and Table 12, respectively.

Table 9: Chemical compositions of the steel grades (%weight)

code	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Al	Cr	Ni	Mo	Cu	V	Nb	Ti	B	N
1a	0.038	0	0.17	0.009	0.008	0.041	0.02	0.01	0.003	0.018	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.0002	0.0039
1b	0.002	0.09	0.06	0.003	0.006	0.041	0.02	0.01	0.003	0.011	0.004	0.002	0.063	0.0002	0.005
1c	0.002	0.01	0.11	0.009	0.006	0.037	0.03	0.02	0.002	0.02	0.003	0.002	0.051	0.0002	0.0027
1d	0.003	0.01	0.11	0.008	0.014	0.044	0.02	0.01	0.003	0.012	0.003	0.002	0.066	0.0002	0.0036
2	0.057	0.014	1.266	0.01	0.004	0.038	0.036	0.04	0.004	0.036	0.002	0.0448	0.003	0	0.0017
3	0.086	0.01	1.896	0.017	0.002	0.021	0.104	0.01	0.042	0.01	0.001	<0.0010	0.001	0	0.004
4a	0.225	0.292	1.159	0.015	0.001	0.16	0.183	0.03	0.002	0.025	0.003	<0.0010	0.035	0.0023	0.0033
4b	0.22	0.19	1.26	0.009	0.001	0.0564	0.21	0.01	0.002	0.01	0.004	0.002	0.037	0.0031	0.0051

Table 10: Mechanical properties of Cold Rolled Steels (RD: Rolling Direction)

Grade code	Dir.	Thickness (mm)	YS (MPa)	TS (MPa)	Uniform El. (%)	Total El. (%)
1a	RD	0.7	200	293	-	-
1b	RD	0.77	149	295	-	-
1c	RD	0.77	250	333	-	-
1d	RD	0.75	140	290	-	-

Table 11: Mechanical properties of High Strength Steels (RD: Rolling Direction, TD: Transverse Direction, 45: 45° Direction, YPE: Yield Plateau Elongation)

Grade code	Dir.	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Re_H (MPa)	Re_L (MPa)	YPE (%)	YS (MPa)	TS (MPa)	Uniform El. (%)	Total El. (%)
2	RD	1.16	20.02	413	409	1.4	-	498	14.8	24.9
	45	1.17	20.01	420	409	2.3	-	477	15.3	28.0
	TD	1.17	20.02	456	441	2.3	-	513	14.2	24.1
3	RD	1.21	20.05	-	-	-	637	886	8.2	13.1
	45	1.23	20.06	-	-	-	625	874	8.6	13.6
	TD	1.24	20.05	-	-	-	617	879	7.8	11.9

Table 12: Mechanical properties of Press Hardened Steels (RD: Rolling Direction, TD: Transverse Direction), Thermal Treatment: 900°C / 6min30s (4a) or 900°C / 6min (4b) + Die Quenching

Grade code	Dir.	Conditions	Thickness (mm)	YS (MPa)	TS (MPa)	Uniform El. (%)	Total El. (%)
4a	TD	Before Thermal Treatment	1.5	54	687	-	10.5
	RD	After Thermal Treatment	1.5	1200	1552	2.3	3.8
4b	RD	After Thermal Treatment	1.5	1202	1505	3,1	5,5

2.2.3.3.2 Cold Rolled Steels

Microstructures of cold rolled steels are shown in Figure 11. DC04 (code 1a) is bare steel (Figure 12-1a).

For DX56+ZF110 (code 1b), the coating was produced through a continuous galvannealing process inducing an alloying in iron of the zinc (ZF110, zinc hop dip galvanization followed by a continuous annealing treatment of the cold rolled grade). Due to this process, iron atoms from the substrate diffuse into the zinc layer. The coating contains approximately 10% of iron at the end. The coating weight was 55g/m² on each side which corresponds to thickness between 7.5µm and 8.5µm (Figure 12-1b).

For DX54+ZM100 (code 1c), the coating was produced by hot dip process in a bath of Zinc-Aluminum-Magnesium ZnAl₂Mg₂ (ZM+100, formulation belonging to voestalpine). Such sacrificial Zinc-Aluminum-Magnesium coating provides excellent corrosion resistance avoiding red rust even on unprotected cut edge due to high potential of protection. The coating weight is 50g/m² on each side which corresponds to 7.5µm (Figure 12-1c).

For DX56+Z100 (code 1d), the coating is produced by current continuous hot dip galvanization process in a bath of Zinc. The coating weight is 50g/m² on each side which corresponds to 7.5µm (Figure 12-1d).

Figure 11: Microstructure (ferrite) of Cold Rolled Steels: 1a) DC04; 1b) DX56+ZF110; 1c) DX54+ZM100; 1d) DX56+Z100

Figure 12: Coatings on cold rolled steels: 1a) DC04 bare steel surface, no corrosion protection; 1b) DX56 + Galvanized ZF110; 1c) DX54 + Zinc-Aluminum-Magnesium $ZnAl_2Mg_2$ ZM100; 1d) DX56 + Hot Dip Galvanized Z100

2.2.3.3.3 High Strength Steels

The microstructure of HC420LA+Z100 (code 2) is presented in Figure 13. The coating weight on HC420LA+Z100 was 50g/m^2 on each side, that leads to a coating thickness of about $7.5\mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 14). Coating weight, determined by dissolution, was found to be $52.5\text{g/m}^2 \pm 1.2$ on HC420LA+Z100 (mean value \pm standard deviation evaluated on 6 positions of the sheet). This corresponds to an average of coating thickness of $7.3\mu\text{m}$. The chemical analysis of the coating (same positions) leads to $0.47\% \pm 0.01$ of Al, and is classically composed of a $\sim 150\text{-}200\text{nm}$ intermetallic Fe_2Al_5 interface layer with steel substrate, and with a top Al_2O_3 layer of $\sim 5\text{nm}$.

The microstructure of HCT780C+ZE (code 3) is presented on Figure 15. The coating weight on HCT780C+ZE (obtained by electro-galvanization process) was controlled by the process to reach a coating thickness more or less equal to $7.5\mu\text{m}$ on both sides (Figure 16). Coating weights, determined by dissolution, was found to be $58.2\text{g/m}^2 \pm 1.3$ on HCT780C+ZE (mean value \pm standard deviation evaluated on 6 positions of the sheet). This corresponds to an average of coating thickness of $8.1\mu\text{m}$. The chemical analysis of the coating (same positions) showed less than 0.005% of aluminum in average, which is in line with Electro-Galvanization process specification (pure zinc coating).

Figure 13: Microstructure (micro-alloyed ferrite) of HC420LA (code 2)

Figure 14: HC420LA Hot Dip Galvanized coating Z100

Figure 15: Microstructure (ferrite in white with martensite in grey) of HCT780C (code 3)

Figure 16: HCT780C+ZE, electro-Galvanized coating ZE 75/75

2.2.3.3.4 Press Hardened Steels

The microstructure of 22MnB5+AS150 (code 4a) is fully martensite with few residual ferrite (see Figure 17). The 150g/m² double-sided Al-Si10% pre-coating (AS150, more or less 25µm by side) which partially diffuses in the base 22MnB5 steel during the austenitizing heat treatment, prevents scaling and decarburization.

The coating after heat treatment had a thickness in the range of 33-41µm (see Figure 18) and consists of five sub-layers, in which Al concentrations are approximately 50, 30, 50, 30 and 10%, respectively, from the surface to the substrate. The last inter-diffusion layer had a maximal thickness of 8µm (see Figure 19). Cracks might be present in the Al-Si-Fe resulting coating until the last inter-diffusion layer and the base steel surface after the forming process, but not propagating in the base material.

The microstructure (fully martensitic) of 22MnB5+Z140 is presented on Figure 20. Initially, the substrate was coated by 140g/m² (Z140) double-sided (70g/m² or about 10 µm by side) zinc hot dip. During austenitization at 900°C (furnace temperature), the metallic zinc coating forms a zinc-iron layer consisting of zinc-ferrite (alpha iron with zinc in solid solution) and sometimes other zinc rich phases like Gamma-zinc.

Figure 17: Microstructure (fully martensite with few residual ferrite in white on disulfite etching) of 22MnB5+AS150 (code 4a)

Figure 18: 22MnB5+AS150 coating (AlSi) after heat-treatment (austenitizing+die quenching)

Figure 19: 22MnB5+AS150 coating after heat-treatment (micro-alloying): Al-Fe-Si multi-layers coating 33-41 μm microstructure

Figure 20: 22MnB5+Z140 (code 4b): a) Microstructure (fully martensitic - Nital etching); b) Coating after thermal treatment (22 μm Fe-Zn-phases, zinc-ferrite & Gamma-phase)

2.2.3.4 Resistance Spot Welds

Cross section of RSW specimens were made to measure the spot-welds diameters, the melting zone diameters as well as the hardness from the Base Metal, through the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) and the Melting Zone, see Figure 21. All specimens of configurations 1 to 5 and 9 were welded in the upper welding range. Therefore, for these configurations, more than the minimum specified diameter (defined by $4\sqrt{t}$, t being the thickness) has always been reached. The configuration 8 exhibited a melting zone diameter of 4.7mm lower than expected (expected 5mm) even if the spot-weld diameter is measured at 6mm. A corona zone was observed between both diameters with a risk of lower strength (diffusive welding). Both configurations 6 & 7 should lead to a spot-weld diameter higher than 5mm, even if the configuration 6 showed higher value than the configuration 7.

Figure 21: Cross sections of the spot-welding for the configurations 1 to 9 (RSW), 15 and 16 (Adhesive+RSW), spot-weld and melting zone diameters

Regarding the failure types using the chisel-test, plug failure were obtained for all the configurations except the configurations 8 and 9 showing partial interfacial failures as expected (see Table 33 in appendix). The hardness distributions showed typical evolutions (see Figure 22 and Figure 23). A progressive increase of the hardness was observed in the HAZ of configurations 1 to 7, as well as configurations 15&16, from the Base Metal hardness 80-170Hv up to the nugget Melting Zone 150-370Hv. The evolution follows a typical trend for these products with hardness in the nugget more or less 2 to 3 times higher than the one of the base material. This is explained by the short welding time. Regarding the configurations 8 and 9 (Press Hardened Steels products), the hardness of the Base Metal 480-500Hv decreases in the HAZ up to 300-335Hv (softening of the HAZ) and increases again to reach 500-550Hv in the nugget Melting Zone.

(a) configuration 1 1a+1a

(b) configuration 2 1a+1d

(c) configuration 3 1d+1d

(d) configuration 4 1b+1b

Figure 22: Hardness of the spot-welding for the configurations 1 to 4 (RSW), base metal (BM), heat affected zone (HAZ), melting zone, HAZ, BM

(e) configuration 5 1c+1c

(f) configuration 6&7 2+2

(g) configuration 8 4a+4a

(h) configuration 9 4b+4b

(i) configuration 15&16 2+2

Figure 23: Hardness of the spot-welding for the configurations 5 to 9 (RSW), 15 and 16 (Adhesive+RSW), base metal (BM), heat affected zone (HAZ), melting zone, HAZ, BM

2.2.3.5 Adhesives

The glass transition temperature was approximately between 78-85°C, depending on method of measurement: Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) or Dynamic Module Thermal Analysis (DMTA). Mechanical testing and metallographic characterization of the adhesive specimen have been carried out.

Adhesive specimens were characterized with different methods:

1. Basic evaluation of hardness and density
2. Evaluation of thermo-mechanical properties by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Dynamic Module Thermal Analysis (DMTA),
3. Measurement of Poisson ratio, Elongation at failure, Young Modulus by tensile tests.

2.2.3.5.1 Hardness and density measurements

The density measurements were done using a pycnometer (relative density measurement) according to EN ISO 1183-1 [2], by evaluating 5 different specimens. The obtained average density was $1.25 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/cm}^3$.

Hardness was measured by "Shore D" durometer (specific for rubber hardness measurement) consisting of a steel indenter acting on the plastic surface. 5 different measurements on 3 different samples were done. The hardness was read after 1s (D1) and 15s (D15) from the positioning of the indenter on the surface. The results of Shore D hardness were 78 ± 1 and 75 ± 1 for D1 and D15 respectively.

2.2.3.5.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is a thermo-analytical technique in which the difference in the amount of heat required to increase the temperature of a sample and reference is measured as a function of temperature. The basic principle underlying this technique is that when the sample undergoes a physical transformation such as phase transitions or others, more or less heat will need to flow to it than the reference to maintain both at the same temperature.

Measurements on cured Betamate 1460S samples were taken in the temperature range 30-350°C, with a heating rate of 10°C/min under inert gas. Two samples were analyzed by DSC.

The results indicated at least two types of transformation, probably of glass transition type:

- the first one, of lower importance, occurs approximately in the range 60-75°C,
- the second one in the range 90-130°C.

Transformations occurring at high temperature are clearly related to polymer degradation.

2.2.3.5.3 Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis is a technique where a small deformation was applied to a sample in a cyclic manner. This allows the materials response to stress, temperature, frequency and other values to be studied. Data measured were material stiffness and damping, reported as modulus and the defined tangent $\tan(\delta)$ versus the temperature. The modulus was given as an in-phase component (the storage modulus E') and an out of phase component (the loss modulus E''). The storage modulus E' is the measure of the sample's elastic behavior. The ratio of the loss to the storage is the $\tan(\delta)$, δ being the phase shift between the stress and the deformation; it measures the energy dissipation of a material (internal damping).

DMTA analysis on cured Betamate 1460S samples was performed in the thermal range 30-300°C, with a heating rate of 2°C/min, at a fixed frequency of 1Hz. The results in terms of maximum $\tan(\delta)$ are summarized for both samples in the following Table 13. These data give information on the variation of the material stiffness with the temperature. For the identification of the main glass transition temperature, different criteria are commonly used: peak of $\tan(\delta)$, peak of loss modulus and onset of decrease in storage modulus.

Table 13: Value of maximum measured $\tan(\delta)$ for both samples

Sample	Temperature@max($\tan(\delta)$) (°C)	Max $\tan(\delta)$
1 st	102	0,416
2 nd	101	0,406

2.2.3.5.4 Tensile tests of adhesive

"Dog bone" shaped specimens of the reference adhesive Betamate 1460S were supplied for testing as defined by ISO 527-2 [3] in order to be ready for the tensile tests, and were cured by a thermal

process simulating that one occurring during actual production. It must be noted that along the thickness of many samples, some porosity was observed. Specimens for the tests were selected among those that seem not to be affected (at least externally) by this porosity.

For the tensile tests, the specimens were properly prepared by application of extensometer (longitudinal and transversal) and extensometers in order to acquire data on adhesive Poisson ratio (μ), Elastic modulus (E), elongation at failure (A%) and stress strain curve. A total of 7 specimens were tested. Two of them broke outside the testing area, mainly due to void and cavities inside the material. 5 specimens were correctly tensile tested (E, A, D, F and G) and all the results have been collected in the Table 14 (the last column provides the average values – AVG – on the 5 specimens). The true stress-strain curves tested on the adhesive Betamate 1460S are provided in the Figure 24

Table 14: Tensile test results on 5 specimens with the average value (AVG)

	Spec. ID	E	A	D	F	G	AVG
Velocità	crosshead speed	0.0975	0.0975	0.0975	0.0975	0.0975	
T (°C)	test temperature	RT	RT	RT	RT	RT	
ti (mm)	Original Thickness	4.18	4.38	4.33	4.33	4.16	
wi (mm)	Original Width	10.15	10.20	10.15	10.18	10.20	
S0 (mm2)	Original Cross Area	42.43	44.68	43.95	44.08	42.43	
L0(mm)	Gage Length	60	60	60	60	60	
Le(mm)	Estensom. Gage Length	50	50	50	50	50	
Fp 0,2 % (N)	Load Yield Strength	558	699	629	586	548	604.1
Fmax (N)	Load Maximum	986	964	995	921	910	966.9
Lu (mm)	Total Elongation	61.00	60.60	60.65	60.40	60.65	60.6
tu(mm)	Smallest Thickness	4.10	4.30	4.27	4.32	4.15	
wu (mm)	Smallest Width	10.06	10.18	10.10	10.10	10.16	
Su (mm2)	Smallest Cross Section	41.25	43.77	43.13	43.63	42.16	
Rp 0,2 % (MPa)	Yield Strength	13.2	15.6	14.3	13.3	12.9	13.8
Rm (MPa)	Tensile Strength	23.2	21.6	22.6	20.9	21.4	22.1
A (%)	Elongation	1.7	1.0	1.1	0.7	1.1	1.0
Z (%)	Reduction Of Area	2.8	2.0	1.9	1.0	0.6	1.7
v [.]	Poisson Modulus	-	0.24	0.27	-	-	0.26
E (GPa)	Young Modulus	1.70	1.22	1.60	1.45	1.35	1.46

Figure 24: True tensile stress-strain curves of the adhesive Betamate 1460S

2.2.3.6 Task 3.4: Mechanical testing under static loading

The mechanical properties of the joined materials were tested by means of tensile tests. The tensile strength was used as a reference in order to evaluate further possible strength loss due to exposure in accelerated corrosion tests, on-vehicle exposures and exposures at field station. The spot welded and weld-bonded specimens were tested by GSI. The adhesive bonded specimens were tested by CSM. Moreover, the results could also be used for FE model calibration. Three replicates of each

combination were tested. The tensile tests carried out on all the combinations gave results characterized by little average scattering.

2.2.3.6.1 Testing conditions

For the determination of the tensile strength, different tensile testing machines were used as detailed in Table 15.

Due to the low expected tensile strength of the bonded T-Peel configurations 11 and 13, the adopted clamping device was a fork with a pin that locks the sample at the pre-existing hole, because the self-tightening clamping device caused a pretension load, which can be difficultly controlled from one test to another. For the bonded Lap shear configurations 10, 12, and 14 self-tightening clamping device was used. The distance between grips was 112.5mm.

Table 15: Characteristics of tensile testing machines

Reference / Brand	Hegewald & Peschke Inspect 50-1	MTS 318.10	MTS 311.11
Max load, kN	50	100	250
Distance between jaws, mm	112,5	215 +/- 2	292.5
Tensile speed, mm/min	10 +/- 2	1.3	0.6
Combinations	1 to 9, 15, 16	10, 12, 14	11, 13

2.2.3.6.2 Results of tensile tests

For the validation of the results, three specimens of each configuration were tested with a constant tensile speed of 10 +/- 2 mm/min till complete cracking. During the test, the values of force and displacement were recorded. The measured plots of load and displacement were used to determine the maximum force and the tensile energy absorption.

Figure 25 shows the static force of resistance-spot weld/adhesive bonded joints under quasi-static tension load.

For the adhesive bonded samples 10 and 12, two specimens of each combination have been tested, for combination 14, three specimens and for 11 and 13 four specimens. Three samples were used for the remaining combinations.

The little differences in the tensile force and the energy were caused by variations in the weld diameter and mechanical properties of the base material. The shear force of the combinations 1 to 5 was in the range of 3.7 and 4.1 kN (~50 J). The spot welding of HC420LA+Z100 reached a shear tensile force of 10.7 kN in the lap-shear design (combination 6), while in T-peel configuration (combination 7) the force was reduced to 1.5 kN (14% of shear force). The spot welding of 22MnB5+Z140 (combination 9) reached a maximum tensile force up to 24.5 kN (mean weld diameter $d_p = 6.1$ mm). Lower values of 17.7 kN were reached with 22MnB5+AS150 (combination 8). These lower values were caused by a smaller weld diameter of 4.9 mm.

For the adhesive bonded lap-shear combinations, the average maximum load for combination 10 (HC420LA+Z100, 1.2 mm) was 20.5 kN. The combination 12 (HCT780C+ZE, 1.2 mm) reached an average maximum load of 24.5 kN. The adhesive bonded combination 14 with 22MnB5+Z140 had a tensile force of 21.3 kN. For the T-Peel combinations, the average maximum load for combination 11 was 2.0 kN and the average maximum load for combination 13 was 2.5 kN.

The combinations 1 to 7 showed a pull-out mode. If we compare the combination 8 (22MnB5+AS150) with 9 (22MnB5+Z140) we recognize a different fracture behavior. The combination 8 showed interfacial fracture mode while combination 9 showed a combination fracture (partial interfacial mode). The reason was a smaller weld diameter for combination 8. The weld bonded combinations 15 and 16 (T-peel) also showed a pull-out mode. The failure was cohesive near the substrate and partially adhesive at the end of the overlap.

All measured values of weld diameter, tensile force and energy, corresponded with results of earlier studies of spot welds with unalloyed and high strength steels (AHSS and UHSS) [4–6]. The fracture modes were typical for these types of steel.

Figure 25: Static strength of resistance-spot weld/adhesive bonded joints under quasi-static shear/T-peel tension load

The fracture observed on the adhesively joined samples subjected to TP and LS tests was substantially cohesive, i.e. internal to the adhesive line for material: HCT780C+Z100 (combinations 12 of LS and 13 of TP) and 22MnB5+Z140 (combinations 14 for LS tests). Material HC420LA+Z100 (combinations 10 of LS and 11 of TP) exhibited a mixed adhesive/cohesive fracture in both LS and TP tests, with the presence of large areas of delamination of the epoxy adhesive from the substrate. This was particularly evident for sample N°11-80, which indeed showed a lower value of maximum peeling force

2.2.3.6.3 Description of back-face strain technique

In order to obtain useful data for bonded joints model calibration, the back face technique has been applied on tensile tests for combinations 10, 12 and 14.

Basically the back-face strain technique is a reliable localized damage assessment technique which consists in the application of a couple of strain gauges at the sample backface (exposed surface) near a site of anticipated damage. The strain measurements during the quasi-static load increasing and also during fatigue test will highlight crack initiation due to much localized phenomena. It is proved that the global overall stiffness is not able to monitor fatigue damage in detail [7]. The strain gauges (grid dimension 1x1 mm) were installed on both sides of the sample. Position A was more far from the clamping and Position B was closer to the clamping as shown in Figure 26. From strain gauges, a bending effect can be derived interpreting the compression values for the strain gauges in position B. This behavior was also observed on a FEM check model, where a very small area in compression was found yet at early stages of the test.

Figure 26: Position of strain gauges on adhesive bonded specimen.

2.2.4 WP4 Long term corrosion properties of joined samples

The objectives of WP4 were to obtain reliable data on the corrosion and mechanical performance of joined materials in real conditions including on-vehicle exposures and exposure in stationary field sites, to assess the corrosion resistance and the mechanical properties of fatigue pre-loaded joined materials on vehicle and in marine atmosphere.

2.2.4.1 Samples preloading

Half the samples were preloaded during 300 000 cycles at a load level corresponding to an average number of cycles to failure of 1 million cycles observed in air (S/N curves from task 5.1). Table 16 presents the selected load levels for each combination.

Table 16: Load levels selected for the fatigue pre-loading from the results of fatigue tests in air (Task 5.1).

Combination	Sample design	Joining technique	Materials	Load level Fmax (N)
1	LS	RSW	DC04	860
2	LS	RSW	DC04 / DX56+Z100	860
3	LS	RSW	DX56+Z100	860
4	LS	RSW	DX56+ZF110	860
5	LS	RSW	DX54+ZM100	860
6	LS	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	1420
7	TP	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	120
8	LS	RSW	22MnB5+AS150	1750
9	LS	RSW	22MnB5+Z140	1420
10	LS	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	5990
11	TP	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	770
12	LS	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	8530
13	TP	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	1340
14	LS	Adhesive	22MnB5+Z140	9250
15	LS	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	5390
16	TP	Adhesive+RSW	HC420LA+Z100	690

For each combination, an additional set of 3 samples have been submitted to fatigue preloading. Tensile tests on these samples was performed afterwards in order to evaluate the possible influence of the fatigue preloading on the tensile strength of the samples before any exposure to corrosive environments. The tensile test results after fatigue preloading are illustrated in Figure 27. Results without fatigue preloading (from task 3.4) are also reminded.

After preloading, scattering of the results increases. Possible sources of deviation are a lack of adhesive, a problem of geometrical nature (flatness issue, bending during loading, ...), notch effect on particular steel grades, fatigue crack initiation during preloading, paint bake hardening effect, etc. Taking into account the scatter in these results, only lap-shear combinations n°6, 12, 14 and 15 were notably weakened by fatigue preloading. The decrease of the mechanical properties after fatigue preloading in the spot-welded combination n°6 (HC420LA+Z100) can be explained by the probable initiation of cracks.

For the bonded combinations n° 12 and 14 (HCT780C+ZE and 22MnB5+Z140 respectively), it must be pointed out that the failure was fully cohesive without fatigue preloading, whereas it was 95% cohesive and 5% adhesive with fatigue preloading, which reflects a degradation at the interface and thus can explicate the decrease of the mechanical properties of these combinations due to fatigue preloading.

In order to understand the results obtained on combination n°15 (HC420LA+Z100), it is important to compare the results of combinations n°6 and n°10, that represent the welded only and the adhesive only joining technique for the same material combination. As shown in Figure 27, tensile tests for combinations 10 and 15 have revealed that two dimensional bonded joints and bonded-welded joints showed similar mechanical results when unloaded, and better in both case than spot-welded joints of combination n°6. As already discussed, the decrease in mechanical properties of combination n°6 was explained by the initiation of cracks. In a similar way, the decrease in mechanical properties for combination n°15 is due to the combined effect of less adhesive coverage compared to combination n°10 and the initiation of cracks as for combination n°6.

Figure 27: Static strength of resistance-spot welded and adhesive-bonded joints under quasi-static shear/T-peel tension load without and with fatigue preloading.

2.2.4.2 Task 4.1: Exposure on-vehicle

The outdoor exposure under an experimental vehicle from BMW, located in the Munich area, Germany, and driving most of the time in Southern Germany and North of Austria where deicing salt is used, has started in May 2013 and ended in January 2015. The duration of the test was 600 days, so that the samples experimented two winter periods with spreading of deicing salt on roads. The mileage of the vehicle was 50,000 km at the end of the exposure.

Due to limited installation space, only six specimens of each combination were mounted on the underbody panel of the vehicle: three with fatigue preloading (according to Table 16) and three without. The specimens were exposed under the vehicle behind the wheels, e.g. at locations which are sprayed with road salt and mud from wheels. Figure 28 shows how the specimens are mounted under vehicle. For space and security reasons, all specimens were mounted parallel to the road direction. Unpainted reference materials made of carbon steel (DC01) and pure zinc (99.8%) were also exposed in order to measure the corrosiveness of the environment. Furthermore, the humidity and temperature are measured continuously in a position close to the specimens using a sensor Hobo Pro V2. The corrosivity measured on the reference panels shows a metal loss of about 100 and 14 μm on steel and zinc respectively for the full period (see Appendix 3: Environmental data - vehicle and field exposure). These results are in good agreement with previous data obtained for other on-vehicle exposures [8].

The assessment of cosmetic corrosion (edge creep) did not reveal much degradation after exposure. Indeed, less than 1 mm of creepage from the vertical edge and the overlap was reported, except for configuration 1 (C-Steel) which presented about 2 mm of creepage from the overlap.

Specimens were also submitted to tensile testing after exposure (as done in task 5.1 and 5.2). Results are shown in Figure 29. The strength loss after the exposure, defined as the residual load after corrosion exposure divided by the strength of unexposed specimens, was rather low whatever the combination and significant dispersion of the results from one sample to another was observed. No deleterious effect of corrosion could be observed on the specimens, strength loss being mainly related to fatigue preloading. The percentage of adhesive failure after tensile testing was assessed and reported in Figure 30. No relevant increase of the adhesive failure was noticed after exposure on the vehicle for specimens with or without preloading.

Figure 28: Photographs of specimens exposed under the vehicle.

Figure 29: Strength loss of specimens with or without preloading after on-vehicle exposure.

Figure 30: Adhesive failure after 2 years of mobile exposure.

As a conclusion, specimens were almost not affected after exposure under the vehicle driving in Munich area. Longer time of exposure is certainly required to generate sufficient corrosion degradation of the specimens and thus observe modifications of the mechanical behavior of the specimens.

2.2.4.3 Task 4.2: Testing at field station

Similar samples as those exposed under the vehicle i.e. with and without fatigue pre-loading have been also exposed in the marine field station of IC in Brest, France. The samples have been exposed with an angle of 45°, facing the south. Photograph of exposed specimens is presented in Figure 31. This site is characterized according to ISO 9223 and classified C5M for steel. Corrosivity and climatic data of the marine site for years of exposure are given in Appendix 3: Environmental data - vehicle and field exposure. The exposure started in early 2013 and ended in December 2014, thus after about two years of exposure.

Figure 31: Photographs of the samples in the marine field site of Brest.

As for samples exposed under the driving vehicle, cosmetic corrosion was assessed at the end of the exposure, regarding the creep from vertical edge and from overlap edge. From the results no major degradations were observed unless on combination 1 (C-steel, no preloading) which showed more edge creep than the other samples. Obviously, zinc coated samples were not much affected after 2 years of exposure with less than 2 mm of creepage from the edges or the overlap.

As a general trend, materials were less affected after 2 years outdoor exposure in marine atmosphere than during accelerated tests (WP5 and WP6). No effect from the preloading could be observed. It is obvious that longer exposure durations should be conducted to induce more degradation.

After exposure, the specimens were submitted to tensile tests in order to measure the strength loss due to corrosion. The strength loss potentially induced by field exposure was then calculated versus the reference specimens with and without fatigue preloading (see Figure 32). The results indicated that the mechanical properties of spot welded specimens (combination 1 to 9) were not much affected by 2 years exposure in marine atmosphere. This is however not true for combination 1 (RSW C-steel) which showed between 10 to 20 % of mechanical loss e.g. twice more than what was observed after on-vehicle exposure. The strength loss with fatigue preloading was slightly higher for combinations 2 to 6 (lap-shear and lower grade materials) but this is more related to the preloading and not to the effects from corrosion degradation.

Tensile properties of adhesive bonded lap shear combination 10 (HC420LA + Z100) were not affected by the exposure, while in T-peel configuration (combination 11), an effect of the exposure could be observed. However, preloading effect was not so conclusive due to the high deviation of the peak load of reference unexposed specimens.

Adhesive bonded combinations 12 and 13 (HCT780C + ZE) and 14 (22MnB5 + Z140) were sensitive to the exposure and to the preloading. Indeed, the strength loss increased with a fatigue preloading prior to field exposure. However, the strength loss of lap shear specimens 12 and 14 was almost the same for specimens without preloading vs. reference specimens without preloading as for specimens with preloading vs. reference specimens with preloading.

Concerning adhesive and spot welded assemblies, lap shear specimens from combination 15 (HC410LS + Z100) were not affected, whereas similar materials in T-peel design (combination 16) showed similar strength loss with or without preloading, with however a high dispersion of the results after preloading.

Figure 32: Strength loss (SL) of specimens with or without preloading and after 2 years exposure at marine station.

The percentage of adhesive failure after tensile testing was measured and plotted in Figure 33. No significant evolution was observed for configurations 10, 11, 15 and 16 compared to reference specimens tested without exposure. A slight increase was noticed for configurations 12 to 14, with a combined effect of corrosion and preloading.

The extent of red rust in the overlap was rather low, except for configuration 1 (C-Steel) as shown in Figure 33. A slight increase of the red rust coverage was observed for preloaded specimens.

As a conclusion, spot welded specimens with zinc coating were not much affected by corrosion after 2 years of outdoor exposure at the marine station of Brest. On the contrary, some adhesive bonded specimens showed important strength loss after tensile testing. A cumulative effect of fatigue preloading and exposure to corrosive environments is observed leading to a loss of mechanical properties of adhesive bonded assemblies.

Figure 33: Adhesive failure after 2 years exposure at marine station.

Figure 34: extent of red rust in the overlap after 2 years exposure at marine station.

2.2.4.4 Comparison of mobile and stationary exposures

Data from mobile and field exposure showed that materials were in general less affected by exposure under a vehicle than at the marine station. The corrosivity of mobile exposure in Munich area toward unpainted carbon steel was indeed lower than one-year exposure in marine atmosphere of Brest. However, the situation was opposite when considering which zinc showed more metal loss than at the marine station. Such results have already been observed in a previous study [8]. This could be related to the salt composition, which has a great impact on the corrosivity of materials. For instance, calcium chloride CaCl_2 is known to be used on road for deicing salt, and magnesium chloride MgCl_2 is the second salt in natural seawater after sodium chloride NaCl . It is indeed known that zinc is much more sensitive to CaCl_2 than MgCl_2 , which is not the case for steel [9]. Road mud may also cause permanent wetness for the mobile exposure leading to a decrease of the corrosion rate of steel and an increase of the metal loss on zinc.

In addition, mobile exposure and marine exposure presented differences in climatic conditions as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Comparison of climatic conditions on the vehicle and at the marine station. Curves are obtained by averaging data for each month.

The temperature was more stable at the marine station, without negative values while mobile exposure in Munich showed negative value during winter time. Moreover, the average relative humidity was low during spring and summer periods for the vehicle (around 60%) whereas the average relative humidity was rather constant at the marine station and above 80%. The time of wetness (time during which the temperature is over 0°C and relative humidity above 78% R.H.) is

clearly more important at the marine site than on the present vehicle. High humidity was indeed found to be deleterious for the mechanical properties of adhesive bonded specimens, as shown in WP6. This would explain why the marine station is probably more aggressive for adhesive bonded specimens than on-vehicle conditions: a high average humidity in the atmosphere favors ingress of moisture in the overlap at the substrate/adhesive interface. This is confirmed by the slight increase of adhesive failure in specimens exposed at the marine station, which has not been observed for specimens on the vehicle.

Concerning spot welded specimens, no deleterious effect has been reported for both the marine and the vehicle exposures. Moreover, no or very little red rust has been observed in the overlap of specimens with Zn coating. Duration was definitively not sufficient to induce sufficient degradation of the specimens that would affect such materials.

2.2.4.5 Conclusions of long term exposure

The aim of this work package was to collect reliable data on the corrosion and mechanical properties of joined materials exposed in real conditions including exposure on-vehicle (Munich area) and at a marine stationary site (Brest). 16 different combinations were tested, half of them after a pre-loading step of 300 000 cycle at a given load level. The exposure duration was limited to two years.

From the results, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Spot welded specimens with zinc coating were not much affected by corrosion after outdoor exposure at the marine station of Brest and under vehicle in service (around 600 days).
- Some adhesive bonded specimens showed important strength loss after tensile testing of samples exposed at the marine station, but not for specimens exposed under the vehicle. A cumulative effect of fatigue preloading and exposure to corrosive environments could be observed on the loss of mechanical properties of adhesive bonded assemblies. Relative humidity plays a key role in the degradation of the properties of these assemblies.

These results will be compared to laboratory tests (WP5 and WP6) to assess any correlation regarding corrosion and strength loss of specimens.

It is obvious that longer exposure durations should have been conducted to induce more degradation, in particular for the mobile exposure. This was however not possible in the frame of such RFCS project. Moreover, for the vehicle exposure, winter 2013/2014 was rather warm and less salt have been used on roads in upper Austria and South Germany compare to other winters. On the contrary, 2014/2015 winter was normal considering the quantity of salt used in Austria.

2.2.5 WP5 Pure fatigue and corrosion testing

The objectives of WP5 were to evaluate the mechanical properties of the joints in pure fatigue conditions, to assess the mechanical properties and the corrosion resistance of the joined materials in accelerated corrosion testing condition, to study the effect of key parameters on the mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of joined samples and to obtain data for input into modeling as defined in WP7.

2.2.5.1 Task 5.1: Fatigue tests in air

The S/N curves allow a classification of the different joining methods and geometry of joints. First, the lap-shear joints may be related to the endurance limit (number of load cycles $< 2 \cdot 10^6$) and classified in order of decreasing fatigue life as illustrated in Figure 36 and summarized below for lap-shear configuration:

Adhesive bonding	>	Spot welding for mild and high-strength steels	>	Spot welding for press-hardened steels
$k \approx 7-9$		$k \approx 4 - 6$		$k \approx 3$

With the increase in strength of the material, the k-value (slope of the Wöhler curve) decreases slightly. Low k-values indicate a high notch sensitivity of the joint. Highest k-values were reached with adhesive-bonded joints.

For T-peel configurations, see Figure 37, the following classification was obtained:

Adhesive bonding > Spot welding
 $k \approx 8 - 10$ $k \approx 3,5$

Figure 36: Comparison of the fatigue curves of lap-shear joints (F_{max} : Maximum load, N : number of load cycles).

Figure 37: Comparison of the fatigue curves of T-peel joints (F_{max} : Maximum load, N : number of load cycles).

These results, and those regarding HC420LA only which are illustrated in Figure 38, show that two dimensional joints (like adhesive-bonded joints) get better values on fatigue strength than isolated joints like spot welds. Two dimensional joints with low notch sensitivity have a homogeneous load transmission with low stress peaks. They also have a better stiffness whereby unfavorable peel and cross tension forces of the alternating stress would be reduced.

Figure 38: Comparison of the fatigue curves of HC420LA+Z100 in lap-shear configuration (F_{max} : Maximum load, N : number of load cycles).

One can observe from Figure 38 the advantage of the adhesive bonding for the HC420LA steel in lap-shear configuration: the k -values are more important and the fatigue force is about 5 times higher in comparison with the spot-welded combination. The behavior was the same in T-peel configuration as illustrated in Figure 37. However, for each configuration (lap-shear and T-peel), the width of the spot-welded samples was lower than that of the bonded ones: 25 mm and 45 mm, respectively.

Typical failure modes are presented in Figure 39. The adhesive-bonded lap-shear combinations n°10, 12 and 14 showed a mixed-failure type (adhesive and cohesive). The fracture type of the bonded T-Peel specimen depended on the material (substrate): the complex phase steel HCT780C+ZE showed a fully cohesive failure while the micro-alloyed HC420LA+Z100 presented a mixed-failure type (adhesive and cohesive). The different fracture behavior was probably due to the different strength of the material and coating (hot-dip galvanized Z100, electrogalvanized ZE, and press-hardened and sand-blasted Z140) on which the adhesion of the adhesive could differ.

All welded combinations showed a pull-out mode. On the mild steels DC04, DX54 and DX56, the crack occurred by high load levels (short-cycle fatigue) outside of the heat-affected-zone, starting in the base material. Fatigue cracks starting at the notch are typical for creep fatigue. For high strength steels like HC420LA+Z100, mostly cracks starting at the notch were observed.

Nr. 1: LS-DC04
Shear force max 0,9 kN
Peel fracture, load cycles 695800

Nr. 6: LS-HC420LAD+Z100
Shear force max 1,4 kN
Peel fracture, load cycles 1060241

Nr. 8: LS-22MnB5+AS150
Shear force max 1,9 kN
Peel fracture, load cycles 626304

Nr. 10: LP-HC420LAD+Z100
Shear force max 8,0 kN
Mostly adhesive, in the middle cohesive near the substrate,
load cycles 116741

Nr. 14: LS-22MnB5+Z140
Shear force max 9,0 kN
Combination fracture, mostly adhesive, in the middle cohesive near the substrate,
load cycles 1117916

Nr. 15: LS-HC420LAD+Z100
Shear force max 5,5 kN
RSW: Peel fracture, ADH: adhesive
load cycles 1942123

Figure 39: Typical fracture types for various configurations.

Regarding the position of the crack initiation between sheets of spot-welded combinations, at the vicinity of the notch, several comments could be provided to justify its variation, i.e. in the base metal or in the heat affected zone.

Depending on the type of current used (Alternative Current or Direct Current) as well as the other parameters such as electrode types, applied load, welding pattern and final applied welding current, the results in terms of geometry of the notch, dimension and properties of nugget and heat affected area could vary from a joint configuration to another.

As the objective was to obtain a nugget diameter being at least equal or greater than $4\sqrt{t}$ (where t is the sheet thickness), and considering that the welding was achieved according to more or less equivalent protocol follow finally different validation criteria (nugget measurement vs. reference standard, as well as human factor), variations are observed in terms of dimension of the nugget and notch geometry. Then, the different nugget diameters were achieved in the upper or lower values of the welding current ranges inducing different notch geometries and metallurgical transformations or location.

An illustration of these variations could be found in the literature like in the works of Rossillon who investigated the fatigue behavior of spot-welded assemblies made of a dual phase high strength steel [10]. In this work, it was observed the same fatigue strength of the assembly all along the welding range, following exactly the same conditions except obviously the welding current. Figure 40 extracted from the reference [10] exposes the different location of the crack initiation with different notch shapes but finally the fatigue results in terms of life under constant amplitude loading were equivalent.

This illustration highlights the competition that occurs at the vicinity of the notch where the following parameters take place:

- The geometry of the notch and at the notch (including the nugget diameter).
- The local mechanical properties and the corresponding microstructures (grain size variation, micro-structural phases, and consequently hardness profiles) as well as their relative position and size.
- The occurrence of residual stresses issued from all these events occurring in very short time at a very local scale during solidification of the molten area (spot-welding process is known to produce high cooling rate as a quench).
- The stress distribution that depends on the thickness and the load level at the scale of the specimen (then the specimen corresponds more to a structure) in a cyclic loading configuration inducing fatigue.

Thus, the location of the crack initiation from one configuration to another is affected by these different conditions. However, the project objectives focused more on fatigue/corrosion interactions than a deep explanation of the fatigue behavior of each configuration.

Figure 40: optical micrographs of the main initiation zones for (I) low (6.0 kA), (II) middle (6.8 kA) and (III) high (7.9 kA) level of current of the welding range [10].

It is well-known that in the field of welded joints [11], and of spot-welded joints [12], for a same configuration, the steel grade used is not of first order in the fatigue strength. In other words, the fatigue strength of a spot-welded assembly for a same configuration does not depend on the steel grade. This case is described in [13] as well. The reason for the same fatigue strength of HSS and AHSS steel grade in comparison to mild steel is that the failure of the spot weld is determined under cycle load primarily by the notch effect and not by the steel strength.

The first order for the considered specimen is the thickness. If a part of fatigue life is consumed up to the crack initiation, a remaining important part of the life is also spent in the crack propagation. Then, for the same criterion used to stop the fatigue test (same specimen), a relationship between the thickness and the fatigue resistance could be found at different fixed lives as it corresponds more or less to the number of cycles spent for the crack to cross the thickness.

Figure 41 shows that the generated results are in good agreement with linear relationships according to the thickness at different fatigue lives.

Figure 41: Fatigue force at different load cycles vs. thickness of the sheets of spot-welded lap-shear combinations (n°1, 3 and 5: ~0.8mm ; n°6: ~1.2mm ; n°8: ~1.5mm).

To conclude, the fatigue tests carried out on all the combinations in air gave results corresponding with earlier studies and are characterized by typical average scattering. This aspect provided a good reference point for the next fatigue tests on samples with corrosion cycles in order to evaluate loss of performances in WP6. Moreover, the results yielded useful information for Finite Element (FE) model calibration. The characteristic S/N curves were the basis for determination of the fatigue preloading level for WP4.

2.2.5.2 Task 5.2: Influence of key climatic parameters in accelerated corrosion tests

In this task, accelerated corrosion tests were performed in climatic chambers and residual tensile strengths and failure modes were assessed. Cosmetic corrosion and corrosion in the overlap were also evaluated.

2.2.5.2.1 Experimental conditions

Regarding the influence of key parameters on the corrosion performance of joined materials, it was originally planned to investigate those listed in WP2 (see Table 3). By varying selected climatic parameters, a test matrix provided with 6 different conditions was proposed, as shown previously in Table 4. The tests were conducted at constant temperature (either 30 or 45°C) and included two cycles. Cycle A started by a salt spray at either 1 or 5 wt % NaCl, followed by a drying phase of 4 hours at 50% R.H. and 4 hours wetting at 95% R.H. A ramp of 2 hours was followed between the humidity changes. This cycle A was repeated either twice a week (SF2) on Monday and Friday or every day (SF7) so that the same salt load was applied during the week. In test conditions with two sprays per week, cycle A alternated with a wet and dry cycle (4h at 50% / 4h at 95%). In one test variant (SC1/SF2/T30/F1/D1), a daily wet/dry cycle was replaced by a freezing phase at -25°C (Wednesday). Finally, another test variant (SC1/SF2/T30/F0/D3) included a drying ratio of 3 which implied a longer drying phase e.g. 6h at 50% and a shorter wetting time at 95 % of 2 h. The test duration was 12 weeks.

Additional tests were also performed on few combinations (1, 3, 10 and 12) with a longer time of exposure in T45 condition (24 and 30 weeks, instead of 12 weeks). These results are discussed separately.

2.2.5.2.2 Evaluation procedure

After 12 weeks of exposure to corrosion and before mechanical testing, the cosmetic corrosion resistance was evaluated in terms of maximal vertical edge creepage and maximal overlap creepage schematically shown in appendix in Figure 131 and Figure 132.

For lap-shear samples, delamination of the paint occurring on upper panels at less than 30 mm from the top horizontal edge and 10 mm from the overlap opening was not considered for the vertical edge creepage. On lower panels, 30 mm from both overlap opening and bottom horizontal edge were excluded.

For T-peel samples, on upper panels as on lower panels, 10 mm from the overlap opening and 30 mm from the horizontal edge were not considered.

For each panel, the maximal vertical edge creepage corresponds to the mean of the 2 maximal vertical edge creeps of the panel. Besides, overlap creepage was measured excluding 5 mm from both vertical edges.

After mechanical testing, the extent of red rust inside the whole overlap area was evaluated using the image analysis software (Lucia). This was performed from pictures of the disassembled panels. The corrosion products from the lapped regions were thereafter removed by intermittent brushing and the use of Clarke solution (20 g of Sb₂O₃ and 60 g of SnCl₂, 2H₂O in 1000 mL of HCl at $\rho = 1.19$ g/mL).

After removal of corrosion products, the 5 deepest pits were visually identified in the center of the overlap in order to exclude edge corrosion, and they were measured using a Mitutoyo micrometre gauge equipped with a sharp tip.

Before and after exposure to the accelerated corrosion tests, the samples were mechanically tested in order to evaluate the influence of the climatic parameters on the mechanical properties of the joints. Tensile testing was performed by GSI on combinations 1 to 9, 15 and 16, and by CSM on combinations 10 to 14 in the same experimental conditions as in Task 3.4. Photographs of fracture

surfaces were thereafter taken for visual examination. The fracture mode of the spot welds was characterized as pull out or interfacial. The failure mode of the Betamate 1460S adhesive was determined as cohesive or adhesive with the percentage of each mode.

Figure 42: Cosmetic corrosion inspection – lap-shear samples on the left, T-peel samples on the right.

2.2.5.2.3 Cosmetic corrosion results

The maximal creepage from the vertical edges of all combinations and the creepage from the overlap are illustrated in appendix (Figure 131 and Figure 132). A direct comparison of the cosmetic corrosion of the combinations has to be taken with care as the thicknesses of the steel substrates and of the metallic coatings was not similar; the samples were also not prepared by the same operator with same tools (especially for shear-cutting). So, it was decided to calculate an acceleration ratio of the cosmetic corrosion (vertical and overlap edge creep) for each combination in each corrosive condition vs. the basic test. All results are gathered and shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Acceleration of the cosmetic corrosion vs. Basic test for all combinations.

The dispersion of the results was rather low considering that the acceleration ratio was calculated for all specimens tested within this task. It can be concluded that the drying ratio and the freezing phase have no influence on the cosmetic corrosion, even slightly beneficial for F1 condition. On the contrary, the salt frequency (SF7), the salt concentration (SF5) and ultimately frequency + concentration (SC5SF7) have increasing influence on the creepage rate. These results are in line with the literature on the subject [14,15]. Finally, increasing the temperature accelerated also the cosmetic corrosion.

The salt deposition was calculated for each accelerated test and the ratio of the salt deposition vs. the basic test was obtained. The evolution of the acceleration of the cosmetic corrosion was then plotted as a function of the salt deposition (for basic, SF7, SC5 and SC5SF7 tests) in Figure 44, from which a power law could be used to fit the data, with an excellent correlation ($R^2=0.9986$).

Figure 44: Acceleration of the cosmetic corrosion vs. salt deposition ratio.

2.2.5.2.4 Perforating corrosion results

The extent of red rust in the overlaps is presented in appendix for all combinations (Figure 133). Due to the presence of the adhesive, no or very little red rust (lower than 5%) was observed on bonded combinations 10 to 16. Thus, no conclusions concerning the influence of the climatic parameters on perforating corrosion could be drawn on these samples.

Unlike bonded samples, significant amounts of red rust were found on pure spot-welded samples. Yet, due to penetration of the e-coat during the painting process, the attributed extent of red rust were underestimated compared to what they should be if no e-coat had penetrated.

Combinations Nr1 and 2 involving bare DC04 were the most covered by red rust as expected. Temperature seemed to increase the extent of red rust for these two combinations and the extent of red rust was systematically more important in the case of SC5SF7 condition.

The observations are summarized in Table 17. As a general tendency, SC5SF7 condition seems to be the most deleterious condition regarding red rust extension for combinations 3 to 9.

Table 17: influence of climatic parameters on the extent of red rust in the overlaps of spot-welded specimens.

Materials	Significant factors
DC04	Temperature +
DX56+Z100	Salt frequency +
DX56+ZF110	Salt conc. and freq. +
DX54+ZM100	n.d.
HC420LA+Z100	Salt conc. and freq. + RSW ++
22MnB5+AS150	n.d.
22MnB5+Z140	n.d.
HCT780C+ZE	n.d.

(+ : increase; n.d.: not determined)

The corresponding attack depths are given in appendix (Figure 134). As values were only significant for bare DC04 (combinations n°1 and 2), it was not possible to establish any obvious influence of

climatic parameters. However, the temperature seemed to have a large influence on the perforating corrosion and the effect of galvanic coupling, beneficial to bare DC04 and detrimental to DX56+Z100, was also noticed.

2.2.5.2.5 Tensile strength results

Tensile test results before and after corrosion and strength loss are provided in appendix (Figure 135 and Figure 136). The mechanical properties were not notably decreased by corrosion for samples n°1 to 9, for which the maximum loss of performances found was 10% (except for T-peel combination 7 and combination 1 in T45 condition). On the contrary, for the adhesive bonded combinations n°10 to 16, the strength loss was important after the tests with high salt condition, especially in SC5SF7 test.

Concerning bonded samples (n°10 to 16), the percentage of adhesive failure is illustrated in Figure 45. Compared to uncorroded references, an increase of the adhesive failure part, limited in general to 20% only, was noticed (except for T-peel combination 13). The most aggressive conditions for the loss of cohesive properties, hence tensile strength, were met with tests involving important salt loads. Compared to references, adhesive failure could increase by 30% and tensile strength decrease by 50%. As a general trend, the strength loss is related to the increase of adhesive failure as shown in Figure 46.

All these results tend to indicate that the exposure to corrosion was not long or aggressive enough to damage the spot-welds substantially, while for some bonded combinations, a decrease in tensile properties could be reached and was imputable to a loss of adhesion at the interface adhesive/coating by a delamination process in the presence of water, oxygen and chlorides.

Figure 45: Percentage of adhesive failure in bonded samples of tasks 3.4 (uncorroded references) and 5.2 (after corrosion testing).

Figure 46: Increase of adhesive failure in bonded samples due to corrosion testing.

2.2.5.2.6 Longer exposure duration in T45 conditions

Exposition in T45 conditions has been extended for specimens in configurations 1, 3, 10 and 12. Specimens were inspected and submitted to tensile testing after 24 and 30 weeks (compared to 12 weeks for other exposure conditions).

Results from cosmetic degradation from the edges are shown in Figure 47. For all configurations, the corrosion creepage increased with time of exposure as expected. For configuration 1, after 24 weeks, specimens were almost fully covered by corrosion as presented in Figure 48. Moreover, specimens broke easily due to corrosion. It can be noticed rather similar creep from vertical edge on configurations 3, 10 and 12.

Figure 47: Corrosion from the vertical edge after exposure in T45 condition for 12, 24 and 30 weeks.

Figure 48: Specimens from configuration 1 after 24 weeks in T45 condition (no tensile testing).

The corrosion from the overlap is shown in Figure 49. Due to high corrosion extent for samples of configuration 1, specimens were fully corroded after 30 weeks.

For spot weld specimens from configuration 3, the creep from the overlap edge significantly increased after 30 weeks. However, the measurement was probably disturbed by the creepback from the vertical edges. For specimens 10 and 12, which were larger than specimens 3 (45 mm instead of 25 mm), there was no influence of the vertical edge creep-back, and corrosion spread less from the overlap after 30 weeks.

Spot-welded specimens exhibited also spacing between the two plates, which facilitated corrosion spreading. This was not the case for adhesive specimens which could explain the lower sensitivity to corrosion creepage from the overlap for adhesive compared to spot welded samples.

Figure 49: Corrosion from the overlap after exposure in T45 condition for 12, 24 and 30 weeks.

The strength loss has been calculated after tensile testing and the results are shown in Figure 50 (left). Due to high corrosion rate for configuration 1, the strength loss was around 100% after 24 weeks of exposure. The strength loss increased with time of exposure for all combinations. However, adhesive specimens 10 and 12 were more sensitive than spot-weld specimens from configuration 3.

The adhesive failure of configuration 10 and 12 is plotted in Figure 50 (right). Obviously, the increase of adhesive failure was correlated with strength loss. Thus, in T45 condition, degradation of the interface metal/adhesive was particularly important. Indeed, moisture can diffuse quite quickly at 45°C, which decreases the fracture energy of the adhesive. Corrosion rate of the coating is also promoted, which changes the adhesion properties.

Figure 50: Strength loss after exposure in T45 condition for 12, 24 and 30 weeks (left) and adhesive failure of configuration 10 and 12 (right)

2.2.5.2.7 Conclusions from Task 5.2

Results from cosmetic corrosion showed that degradation was strongly linked to salt deposition and average temperature. Observations were quite similar for all configurations. A power law has been established with the results from this study to link the salt deposition and the cosmetic corrosion.

The mechanical properties of spot welded specimens were only slightly affected by the exposure to the corrosive environment, except for configuration 1 without Zn coating which was highly altered at higher temperature. However, large extent of red rust was observed in the overlap, with some perforating corrosion, particularly at 45°C. In fact, red rust started from the edge of the specimen and spread to the notch-tip. But, the time of exposure was probably too short to affect the properties of the spot weld, which explained the low sensitivity of the spot weld specimens. After longer time of exposure in T45 condition, spot-weld specimens from configurations 1 and 3 were more affected by corrosion.

Adhesive specimens were highly affected by exposure to corrosive environment. Strength loss after tensile testing was related to the increase of adhesive failure, as a result of the degradation of interface metal-adhesive. The degradation was enhanced by increasing salt frequency and salt concentration. Rising temperature to 45°C had also a deleterious impact on adhesive samples, increasing strength loss and adhesive failure.

As for specimens exposed in marine atmosphere, the strength loss of spot-welded specimens was rather low. However, in accelerated tests, the extent of red rust was much more important, particularly in SC5SF7 condition. For adhesive bonded specimens, both strength loss and adhesive failure were of the same order of magnitude for accelerated tests (12 weeks) and exposure at the marine station (almost 2 years).

2.2.5.3 Task 5.3: Performance of automotive corrosion tests

The standardized corrosion test VDA 233-102 (NVDA) was conducted on unloaded samples. As for tests in task 5.2, three replicates were exposed in N-VDA during 12 weeks. The residual tensile strength was afterwards evaluated by GSI and CSM using similar procedure as in tasks 3.4 and 5.2.

The extent of red rust in the overlap and maximal attack depth in steel substrate are provided in Figure 51. No red rust has been observed in the overlap of specimens with adhesive. In spite of the human factor for the evaluation of perforating corrosion, NVDA results were fully consistent with the previous results from task 5.2, i.e. a significant corrosion (around 100% coverage in the case of NVDA) in the overlap for the combinations n°1 and 2 with bare DC04. Then, less red rust extent was reported for other combinations, with higher value for the combination 8. This is linked to the difference in the protective coating composition. For the maximal attack depth, only uncoated specimens showed significant perforating corrosion. It was also the case previously, at the exception of the T45 condition.

Figure 51: crevice corrosion results – extent of red rust and maximal attack depth in overlaps of RSW specimens after NVDA testing.

All the tensile strength results and the part of adhesive failure in the bonded combinations can be seen in Figure 52 to Figure 54. By comparing the combinations n°1 and 2 with bare DC04 to other spot-welded combinations, it is obvious that corrosion has a major impact on joints. In case of uncoated materials the base material is weakened to such an amount to fail before the spot weld, which is not the case with better protected systems. That also tends to indicate that the NVDA test was more aggressive than the tests conducted so far in task 5.2 as fracture in the substrate of bare DC04 did not occur, except after very long exposure in T45 condition.

Figure 52: tensile strength results – peak load before and after NVDA test.

Figure 53: tensile strength results – strength loss after NVDA test.

Figure 54: Percentage of adhesive failure in bonded samples of tasks 3.4 (uncorrodred references) and 5.3 (after NVDA).

As previously, adhesive exhibited good protection against the development of corrosion in the overlaps as all samples with this joining technique showed hardly any corrosion of steel. The strength loss after NVDA exposure observed in adhesive bonded combinations can be connected to the delamination of the adhesive which led to a loss of cohesive properties. Indeed, as a general trend, percentage of adhesive failure increased compared to unexposed specimens. This phenomenon is discussed in the next chapter based on the modification of the mechanical properties of the adhesive with the moisture content.

As a conclusion, the behavior of bonded specimens in NVDA conditions was close to previous case with simpler corrosion cycles. The strength loss in NVDA conditions was compared to previous Basic, SC5SF7 and T45 conditions in Figure 55. For spot weld specimens, the strength loss was very close in NVDA and T45 conditions. The temperature obviously plays the most important role by increasing the corrosion rate of the steel (for uncoated materials at least). Concerning adhesive specimens, no exact correlation can be drawn compared to previous tests. Indeed, the mechanical strength of each combination seems to be not sensitive to the same environmental parameters. As a result, the sensitivity in NVDA condition is in an intermediate range compared to previous climatic conditions, without very large strength loss as it can be observed in SC5SF7 or T45 conditions.

Finally, as shown in Figure 55, compared to results on the vehicle or at the marine station (WP4) the strength loss was more important after 12 weeks in NVDA than almost 2 years in the real climatic conditions.

Figure 55: tensile strength results – strength loss after various tests.

2.2.6 WP6 Combined corrosion-fatigue testing

The objectives of WP6 were to evaluate the influence of combined fatigue loading and environmental exposure on the corrosion resistance of the joints, to study the effects of key environmental parameters on combined corrosion-fatigue, to obtain a database on corrosion-fatigue for materials with high potential applications in the automotive industry and to define a testing procedure and to obtain data for input into modeling as defined in WP7.

2.2.6.1 Task 6.1: Influence of key climatic parameters on simultaneous corrosion-fatigue

2.2.6.1.1 Experimental procedure

Simultaneous fatigue-corrosion testing has been performed on a limited number of assemblies (see Table 18) in a maximum of four extreme testing conditions defined in WP2 (Basic, SC5SF7, T45 and F1 but only for adhesive bonded specimens – see Table 19). The pneumatic corrosion-fatigue equipment shown in Figure 56 has been used.

Table 18: List of combinations tested task 6.1

Combination code	Specimen	Joining techniques	Grade 1	Grade 2
1	LS	RSW	DC04	DC04
3	LS	RSW	DX56+Z100	DX56+Z100
5	LS	RSW	DX54+ZM100	DX54+ZM100
6	LS	RSW	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
10	LS	Adhesive	HC420LA+Z100	HC420LA+Z100
12	LS	Adhesive	HCT780C+ZE	HCT780C+ZE

Table 19: Climatic conditions for task 6.1.

Parameters	SC	SF	T	F	D	Label
SC1/SF2/T30/F0/D1	1 wt %	2	30°C	0	1	Basic test
SC5/SF7/T30/F0/D1	5 wt %	7	30°C	0	1	SC5SF7 test
SC1/SF2/T45/F0/D1	1 wt %	2	45°C	0	1	T45 test
SC1/SF2/T30/F1/D1	1 wt %	2	30°C	1	1	F1 test

Figure 56: Photographs of the equipment for simultaneous corrosion-fatigue

The samples were exposed with an angle of 160° from the horizontal axis and with the overlap entrance towards the top in order to promote the penetration of salt solution. In addition to this, prior to exposure, e-coat was carefully removed with a cutter at the opening of the overlap in order to promote the penetration of salt solution.

In principle, two or three replicates per combination were tested at two load levels for which fatigue failure was foreseen at 10^6 and 1.8×10^6 load cycles. The load levels were defined from the fatigue tests in air (task 5.1) and from the results of the simultaneous fatigue-NVDA testing (task 6.2) which were performed in parallel. However, practically, as testing conditions were very different from one test to another, some deviations may be expected.

2.2.6.1.2 Analysis of the results

Fatigue life during combined corrosion-fatigue tests are presented for each combination. Results were compared to tests in air (task 5.1) and in N-VDA condition (task 6.2). The Basquin's law (see Eq.1) was used to estimate the Whöler curve.

$$N \times \sigma_a^p = C \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where N is the number of cycles, σ_a is the stress amplitude and p and C are materials parameters. The same kind of law (Eq.2) was established with the maximum applied load (F_{\max}):

$$N \times F_{\max}^p = A \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

A is a constant dependent on the material and the geometry.

The strength loss, SL (see Eq.3), was measured for each un-failed sample after 2×10^6 cycles in the climatic chamber.

$$SL = \left(1 - \frac{F}{F_{ref}} \right) \times 100 (\%) \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

Where F is the peak load of the specimen by tensile testing, and F_{ref} is the peak load of un-exposed samples.

To be able to compare each condition, the parameter b was kept constant within a configuration for all fatigue-corrosion tests. It was obtained from tests in N-VDA condition (task 6-2) with higher number of specimens than in task 6-1. Thus, the parameter A was fitted by least square method. All un-failed specimens were not taken into account for the determination of parameter A , only un-failed specimens at the highest load that did not lead to failure.

Finally, joint failure was characterized by interfacial or pull-out type for spot welded samples, and percentage of adhesive failure for adhesive joints. Both the fatigue loading and the corrosion lead to adhesive failure of the joint.

2.2.6.1.3 Spot welded specimens

The number of cycles to failure for configuration 1 (spot welded uncoated steel) is given in Figure 57. Dispersion of the results was quite large for this configuration. Thus, comparison between different climatic conditions is not obvious. However, basic condition seemed to be more deleterious for the fatigue resistance of this configuration compared to SC5SF7 or T45 conditions. This could be explained by the blunting of the crack tip, limiting the crack growth in highly corrosive environment, when the corrosion rate is increased.

This first configuration was very sensitive to generalized corrosion. Failure during combined corrosion-fatigue was characterized by full button pull-out. After 2×10^6 cycles in basic condition at a maximum applied load of 890 N, the strength loss during tensile testing was about 48% and the failure occurred in the base material, not close to the spot weld (see Figure 58), as it was observed for pure corrosion testing in NVDA condition (task 5.3).

Figure 57: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 1.

Figure 58: Sample from configuration 1 after tensile testing following 2×10^6 of fatigue cycles in basic test

The number of cycles to failure for configuration 3 (spot welded Z100), 5 (spot welded ZM100) and 6 (spot welded zinc coated high strength steel) are given in Figure 59, Figure 60 and Figure 61, respectively. The Basquin's laws were quite similar in all accelerated test conditions. It should be noticed that compared to tests in air, the fatigue life in corrosive environment decreased slightly at high applied load and increased somewhat at low applied load. Without considering the NVDA condition (task 6.2), the following ranking can be established from the least to the most aggressive condition:

$$T45 < \text{Basic} < \text{SC5SF7}$$

From the results obtained on spot welded specimens, it can be concluded that the fatigue in corrosive environment is decreased at high applied loads, whereas it is the contrary at lower load levels. No large effect of environmental parameters selected in the present study has been established, salt frequency and concentration increase being slightly more deleterious to the fatigue life than temperature increase. The variation of fatigue in corrosive environment can be explained by the corrosion products formation around the spot-weld, which changed the local mean stress and then limited the stress and strain amplitudes at low applied load. The increase of the fatigue life could be also explained by the blunting of the micro-cracks formed at the notch tip, which reduced the local stress concentration.

Figure 59: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 3

Figure 60: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 5

Figure 61: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 6

The cross-sections of some specimens from combination 6 have been observed using optical microscope and SEM. Reference specimens unexposed and specimens tested in T45 condition at maximum loads of 1350 and 1550 N (2,000,000 fatigue cycles) have been investigated as described in paragraph 3. For the reference specimen, the initial notch near the weld nugget can be clearly seen in Figure 62. The initial aspect of the surface in the overlap area is also shown in this picture. The metal surface was smooth and covered by a fine layer of zinc, not shown at this magnification.

Figure 62: Cross-section observation by optical microscope of reference specimen from combination 6 not exposed to corrosion environment or fatigue loading.

For the specimen tested at 1550N in T45 conditions during $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles, the main crack was observed in the heat affected zone (HAZ), with secondary cracks near the weld nugget (see Figure 63). This kind of crack, in the HAZ, typically led to plug failure of the assembly, which was observed for this combination. It is very probable that this specimen would have failed with few more cycles. It can be seen that the main crack initiates out the sharp notch, maybe at the location where the notch is enlarged (the probable location of the initial notch is drawn in Figure 63a). A high amount of corrosion products was observed in the crack and at the initiation site. In the crack, iron-rich corrosion products were detected, whereas zinc-rich corrosion products were analyzed in the overlap.

Figure 63: Cross-section observation of specimen from combination 6 tested 2,000,000 fatigue cycles at 1550N in T45 condition by a) optical microscope and b) SEM and c) EDS spectrum of the corrosion products in the main crack.

For the specimen tested at 1350N under the same conditions as before, a short crack was detected at the notch tip with no propagation in the HAZ or in the weld nugget (see Figure 64a). As shown in Figure 64b, the steel surface was highly attacked by corrosion, with an accumulation of corrosion products in the overlap. Near the notch, iron-rich and zinc-rich corrosion products were again detected as illustrated in Figure 64c, d and e. All these observations are compatible with the two

scenarios of stress amplitude limitation by corrosion products accumulation and local stress decrease by crack blunting.

Figure 64: Cross-section observations of specimen from combination 6 tested 2,000,000 fatigue cycles at 1350N in T45 condition a) sharp notch by optical microscope, b) corroded overlap area, c) sharp notch by SEM, d) and e) EDS spectra of corrosion products.

2.2.6.1.4 Adhesive bonded specimens

Two configurations of adhesive bonded specimens were selected for this task e.g. configuration 10 (adhesive bonded Z100) and 12 (adhesive bonded ZE). Results were compared to tasks 6.2 and 6.3 that have been performed in NVDA condition under simultaneous and alternated fatigue-corrosion respectively.

The number of cycles to failure for configuration 10 is given in Figure 65. Compared to tests in air or in alternated fatigue-corrosion, the fatigue life decreased in all corrosive environments. At one million cycles, the loss of fatigue resistance was around 40 to 60%. The drop of fatigue resistance was higher in T45 condition. Similar results were observed in N-VDA test (task 6-2) which operates at temperature up to 50°C in some phase of the test cycle.

Figure 66 presents the number of cycles to failure for configuration 12. The tests were performed up to the limiting load level of the fatigue device, i.e. 3500 N. Thus, failure occurred only after around one million cycles. It can be observed that the fatigue life was obviously reduced in all combined corrosion-fatigue tests compared to tests in air. Interestingly, it was possible to rank the aggressiveness of the different testing conditions toward fatigue resistance of combination 12 in the following order (from the least to the most aggressive conditions):

$$F1 < \text{Basic} < \text{SC5SF7} < \text{T45} < \text{N-VDA}$$

This ranking was more or less the same as for combination 10, even if the ranking from Basic and SC5SF7 conditions were inverted.

The results indicated an obvious sensitivity of adhesive bonded specimens to the corrosive environment. The fatigue life decreased to a maximum of 60% compared to tests in air (at 1 million of cycles). The strongest influence was due to the temperature, followed by salt spray concentration and the frequency of salt spray. This is true in the selected range of parameters.

Figure 65: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 10

Figure 66: Fatigue life of samples from configuration 12

2.2.6.1.5 Conclusion of task 6.1

Concerning the different climatic conditions, configuration 1 was less sensitive to fatigue loading in T45 climatic conditions than in basic and SC5SF7 ones. From results of task 5.2, tensile testing of similar configuration after an exposure of 12 weeks to corrosive environments only showed that the strength loss after an exposure in T45 conditions was about 8 times higher than after exposure in basic or SC5SF7 test conditions. This indicates that the corrosion rate was much more important under this particular condition for this material. Thus, the fatigue crack was probably blunted which may decrease stress concentration and crack growth rate and led to an increase of the fatigue life.

For the 3 others spot weld configurations (3, 5 and 6), no important evolution of the fatigue life was noticed in the investigated corrosive environments, the fatigue was slightly more affected by SC5SF7 condition, i.e. salt spray concentration and frequency, than temperature (T45 condition). However, at higher load level, the fatigue life was systematically lower than in air, whereas it was the contrary at lower load level. At high load level, the overlap was opened and corrosion could occur easily near the notch-tip. However, there was no strong limitation of the stress/strain amplitudes due to corrosion products. On the contrary, at low applied loads, the overlap was less opened. Thus, corrosion products could accumulate near the spot weld and limit the stress/strain amplitudes at the notch tip. This would explain the increase of fatigue life because local strain and stress amplitudes were limited by corrosion products.

Another explanation could be made based on blunting of the crack tip. Indeed, the decrease of the stress concentration by blunting of the crack tip is supported by the fact that the strength loss after pure corrosion tests (task 5.2) is more important in T45 than SC5SF7 condition. Then, corrosion near the spot weld is enhanced in T45 condition. That would finally decrease the crack growth rate under fatigue loading at lower applied load and enhanced the fatigue strength. At higher applied load, the corrosion rate was not sufficient to blunt the crack tip as soon as a critical fatigue crack was mechanically initiated. In this case, corrosion would be deleterious for the fatigue strength as a promoter of crack initiation by creation of corrosion defects.

Adhesive specimens were found to be much more sensitive to the corrosive environment than spot welded ones. The largest influence was observed at increasing temperature, followed by higher salt spray concentration and frequency.

2.2.6.2 Task 6.2: Simultaneous corrosion-fatigue tests

In this task, simultaneous fatigue-corrosion testing was performed on all combinations. The corrosion test NVDA was conducted in a ControlArt Type 2 corrosion cabinet, in which four home-made pneumatic fatigue-corrosion devices work, allowing testing twelve samples in parallel. Except the nature of the corrosion test, test conditions were the same as for task 6.1. Likewise, unfailed samples after 2 million cycles were then mechanically tested by tensile testing. In the same way as for task 6.1, the load levels were first defined from the fatigue tests in air (task 5.1). However, more specimens were tested for each combination than in task 6.1. All results from simultaneous fatigue-corrosion are shown in Appendix 4: Simultaneous Fatigue-corrosion results (task 6.2). Some representative behaviors of spot welded and adhesive bonded specimens in lap-shear and T-peel configurations are shown in Figure 67 and Figure 68.

For combinations 1 to 5, the fatigue behavior in corrosive environment was quite similar. Thus, an average Basquin's law was established with all results. Compared to tests in air, the fatigue life was decreased at high applied load and increased at lower load. As for combination tested in task 6.1, the variation of fatigue in corrosive environment can be explained either by corrosion products formation at the spot-weld (see Figure 69), which changed and then limited the stress and strain amplitudes at low applied load, or/and by blunting of the crack tip. It should be noticed that configuration 3 (Z100) was slightly more resistant than configuration 4 (ZF), with the same steel but different zinc coating.

Figure 67: Representative fatigue-corrosion behavior of spot welded specimens.

Figure 68: Representative fatigue-corrosion behavior of adhesive bonded specimens.

Figure 69: Fracture surface after fatigue-corrosion for spot weld combinations 1 to 5.

For spot weld specimens 6 to 9, the same conclusion as before can be drawn: corrosion near spot weld changed and limited local stress at the notch for low load, leading to an increase of the fatigue life compared to tests in air.

For adhesive specimens (10 to 13), the fatigue life was quite reduced compared to tests in air. This reduction was correlated with a large increase of the adhesive failure, up to 80% for configuration 10 to 12, and around 20% for configuration 13. Relevant examples of fracture surfaces are shown in Figure 70. Thus, the interface coating/adhesive was affected by the corrosive environment, which reduced the fatigue life. The diffusion of moisture in the overlap is probably a critical parameter.

No failure has been observed for configuration 14 at 3.5 kN which was the highest load for fatigue device used to perform simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests.

Concerning specimens with adhesive and spot weld e.g. configurations 15 and 16, the fatigue life was also fairly reduced during simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. The behavior was very close to adhesive specimens (10 and 11). Thus, the spot-weld seems to have no beneficial effect for the fatigue resistance of the assembly in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests as the primary fatigue strength was mainly brought by the adhesive.

Figure 70: Fracture surface for adhesive bonded combinations 10 to 13.

2.2.6.3 Task 6.3: Alternated corrosion-fatigue tests

Tests with sequential fatigue loading and corrosion exposure have been performed as indicated in WP2 on a restricted number of combinations. The load levels for each tested combination are given in Table 20

Table 20: Load levels and numbers of fatigue cycles to apply between exposures in NVDA for each combination.

Combinations	Load level (Newton) corresponding to N cycles						
	300 000	600 000	900 000	1 200 000	1 800 000	> 2 000 000	
1 LS - RSW - DC04	1 130				770		
3 LS - RSW - DX56+Z100	1 130				770		
5 LS - RSW - DX54+ZM100	1 130				770		
6 LS - RSW - HC420LA+Z100	1 775				1 125		
7 TP - RSW - HC420LA+Z100	170		125	115	100		
10 LS - Adh - HC420LA+Z100		6 425	6 075	5 825	5 525	3 500	
11 TP - Adh - HC420LA+Z100		820	780	755	720		
12 LS - Adh - HCT780C+ZE		9 100	8 650	8 325	7 900	3 500	
13 TP - Adh - HCT780C+ZE		1 325	1 280	1 250	1 210		
14 LS - Adh - 22MnB5+Z140		9 175	8 575	8 175	7 625	3 500	
16 TP - Adh+RSW - HC420LA+Z100		765	705	665	615		
Nb cycles to apply between each week of exposure in NVDA	Method 1 Method 2	50 000	100 000	150 000 300 000	200 000	300 000	300 000

2.2.6.3.1 Results on lap shear specimens

For spot-weld specimens of configurations 1, 3 and 5, no failure has been reported in alternated fatigue-corrosion below the average number of cycles observed for fatigue testing in air. Thus, no deleterious effect of alternated fatigue-corrosion was noticed. As presented in Figure 71 for configuration 6, failure occurred in VDA233-102 test slightly before tests in air. However, the effect of corrosive environment was quite different than tests in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. Thus, the mechanisms involved in the failure of alternated or simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests must be different. Failure during alternated fatigue-corrosion was probably the same mechanism as during fatigue testing in air, whereas in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion, as already explained the effect of corrosion products seemed limited the strain and stress amplitudes at the notch tip for low applied load. In fact, the difference between both simultaneous and alternated results was that:

- During the alternated fatigue tests, the assemblies were loaded in a non-corrosive conditions (at ambient conditions) leading to no corrosion product formation during pure fatigue. Whatever the loads, even under gap opening load condition, no additional corrosion was initiated. After that, the joints returned in a NVDA corrosion cycle.
- During the simultaneous fatigue tests, the corrosion cycles were continuously acting, especially for gap opening loads, i.e. high load, degrading the fatigue strength in this condition. Note that the load cycle at 0.5Hz in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion condition was more close to a square than a sine signal. It means that the opening of the gap, if there is, was maintained during a certain time relatively to the whole cycle.

For adhesive bonded lap-shear specimens, results from method 1 are shown in Figure 151 to Figure 153 in Appendix 5: Alternated Fatigue-corrosion results (task 5.3). For configuration 14, the experimental plan was based on a wrong fatigue curve in air. Thus, the number of NVDA cycle was finally not in accordance with method 1 of alternated fatigue-corrosion. However, thanks to this error, it highlighted more the following analysis: it can be seen from the results that the average fatigue failure occurred after 4 to 5 cycles (i.e. more or less 2/3 of the fatigue life in air focused on specimens 10 and 12). As shown in Figure 72, no red rust (corrosion degradation) was observed on the fracture surface. Thus, the embrittlement was probably linked to water diffusion in the overlap of the specimens during the NVDA cycle. In the presence of moisture, the fracture energy of adhesive was reduced [16].

Figure 71: Alternated fatigue-corrosion for configuration 6. Comparison with fatigue in air and simultaneous fatigue-corrosion data.

Figure 72: Fracture surface after alternated fatigue-corrosion for specimens 10 (left), 12 (middle) and 14 (right).

The 3 previous configurations (10, 12 and 14) have been tested with the second method of alternated fatigue-corrosion (method 2 – NVDA exposure every 300,000 fatigue cycles), at the highest level that could be reached at IC (3.5 kN). No failure was observed after 2 millions of cycles. These results confirmed that simultaneous fatigue-corrosion was more aggressive than alternated fatigue-corrosion for adhesive specimens.

2.2.6.3.2 Results on T-peel specimens

Results for spot-weld specimen 7 are shown in Figure 154 of appendix. Dispersion of the results was quite important. However, as for spot-weld specimens tested in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion, the fatigue life decreased at high load and increased at low load. For high loading, the finite element analysis showed that residual opening of the gap after fatigue cycles was higher compared to lower loading, thus corrosion at the notch could occur easily during exposure in NVDA.

For adhesive configurations 11 and 13, the results are shown in Figure 155 and Figure 156 in appendix. As for configuration 14, the experimental plan for configuration 13 was based on wrong fatigue curve in air; the right fatigue curve in air was however reported on the figures. However, for the 2 specimens, the fatigue failure occurred after more or less 2 to 3 corrosion cycles. Again, this is probably linked to moisture diffusion in the overlap, as no red rust was observed on the fracture surface (see Figure 73).

The conclusion was more or less the same for T-peel specimens than the lap-shear adhesive specimens expected that T-peel with adhesive bonding failed before lap-shear specimens. This could be explained by the exposure of the specimens in the corrosion chamber. Indeed, lap-shear specimens were exposed with an angle of 20° with the normal direction, whereas T-peel specimens were exposed with an angle of 70° (20° with the floor of the cabinet). Thus, water can be more easily retained at the surface of the adhesive and increase moisture in the adhesive of T-peel assemblies.

Figure 73: Fracture surface after alternated fatigue-corrosion for specimens 11 (left) and 13 (right).

The difference between the behavior of lap-shear and T-peel specimens could be also linked to the mechanical state of the adhesive under load and the failure mechanism. Indeed, during tensile

testing, the peel stress for TP specimens was maximum at the outer surface of the overlap with high stress concentration in direct contact with the environment (see Figure 74). Failure occurred by peeling of the adhesive. For lap-shear samples, the stress was distributed in the adhesive bonding (shear and peel stress) and peel stress concentration was lower in contact with the environment, see [17] for instance. The failure of the adhesive in tension was mainly obtained by shearing of the adhesive. However, during fatigue testing, crack initiated at the outer surface of the overlap due to the cyclic peeling stress and propagated at the interface metal/adhesive. Thus, any modification of the critical peeling stress for crack initiation would influence the fatigue resistance of LS and TP specimens.

The behavior of spot-welded and adhesive bonded specimens from configuration 16 is shown in Figure 157 in appendix, with an example of fracture surface in Figure 75. Fatigue failure occurred at more or less 2/3 of the fatigue life in air, after around 4 VDA233-102 cycles. The fatigue resistance in air of RSW+adh T-peel specimens 16 was very closed to the adhesive bonding T-peel specimens 11 of the same steel, and significantly more important than spot weld specimens 7. It can be considered that the mechanical strength of the assembly was mainly supported by the adhesive. However, the failure did not occur after 2 cycles as for adhesive specimens. Thus, the spot-weld took at least partially the load and finally delayed the failure of the adhesive. In this case, spot-weld exhibited a positive interest on the fatigue behavior during alternated fatigue-corrosion, whereas no effect (neither positive, nor negative) was observed during fatigue in air or in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion.

Figure 74: Modeling of stress distribution in T-peel specimen

Figure 75: Red-rust around spot weld after alternated fatigue-corrosion

2.2.6.3.3 Comparison of method 1 and 2

All results from the second method of alternated fatigue-corrosion are shown in Appendix 5: Alternated Fatigue-corrosion results (task 5.3). Excepted combination 7, which showed high scattering on the results, the fatigue life was systematically increased in method 2 compared to

method 1 for other tested combinations (10 to 14 and 16). Thus, increasing intervals between two corrosion exposures was beneficial for the fatigue resistance of the assembly, which was expected.

However, contrary to the method 1, the failure did not occur for the same number of NVDA cycles for the lap-shear specimens (4-5 cycles in method 1 and 2-3 cycles in method 2). Mechanical damaging plays also an important role on the fatigue resistance of the assembly, probably decreasing the critical moisture content in the adhesive.

Concerning T-peel specimens, the number of NVDA cycles before failure was more or less the same for methods 1 and 2. T-peel specimens were very sensitive to the environment. Thus, moisture diffusion was probably the main parameter that controls the fatigue life of this configuration.

2.2.6.4 Conclusions of WP6

Fatigue tests have been performed in simultaneous and alternated modes on spot welded and adhesive bonded specimens. From these results, the fatigue life has been characterized with Basquin's laws and compared to fatigue tests in air. Two representative examples of the behavior of spot weld and adhesive specimens are presented in Figure 76.

For spot weld specimens, the fatigue life was rather close in air and during alternated fatigue-corrosion tests. Thus, the fatigue mechanisms were probably the same, without deleterious effects from corrosion. On the contrary, the fatigue life in simultaneous mode decreased at high applied load and increased at lower load. The assumption was that corrosion products applied a local mean stress effect leading to reduction of the local effective stress amplitude. Moreover, the load cycle at 0.5 Hz in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion condition was more close to a square than a sine signal. It means that the opening of the gap was maintained during a certain time relatively to the whole cycle.

For adhesive specimens, some reduction of fatigue life has been observed in alternated fatigue-corrosion mode, after 2 to 4 NVDA test cycles, depending upon the type of configuration (T-peel or lap-shear). However, the reduction of fatigue life was much less important than in the case of simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. In this case, the reduction has been correlated with an increase of the adhesive failure, up to 80% for configurations 10 and 12.

The behavior of specimens with spot weld and adhesive (configurations 15 and 16) was very close to specimens with adhesive only in the case of simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. For the T-peel configuration 16 during alternated fatigue-corrosion, a delay of the failure compared to configuration 11 has been observed, which indicated a slightly beneficial effect of the assembly RSW+adh under this condition.

Figure 76: Examples of the fatigue behavior of spot weld (configuration 6) and adhesive bonded (configuration 10) specimens in air, during alternated and simultaneous fatigue-corrosion loading.

To conclude, the behaviors of specimens in alternated or simultaneous fatigue-corrosion modes were quite different. However, it is difficult to assess which one is more representative of the behavior of an automotive component.

For spot-weld specimens, even under severe conditions of simultaneous fatigue-corrosion, the loss of mechanical properties was not very important. In alternated fatigue-corrosion mode, variations were quite small and probably covered by security coefficient from design.

In the case of adhesive specimens, the diffusion of moisture seems the main degradation parameter, which depends upon exposure conditions and mechanical loadings. Protection should be applied to limit this diffusion.

2.2.7 WP7 Modeling

The objectives of WP7 were to evaluate stress and strain fields in samples under fatigue loading, including effect of residual stresses and corrosion on fatigue life of spot-welded samples and to predict fatigue and corrosion-fatigue results using existing design rules and/or models. The modeling was based on all fatigue results compiled from WP5 and WP6.

2.2.7.1 Task 7.1: Modeling corrosion-fatigue of spots welds

Finite element computations have been performed to evaluate stress/strain fields and load carrying capacities of spot joints as well as to determine quantitatively parameters representing fatigue performances of the spot joints. The different steps for this task were depicted in the following workflow for structural integrity assessment of spot welded automotive structures.

Originally, coupled simulation of the spot-welding process including complex considerations as phase change of material in the vicinity of the weld nugget, pressure contact effect of electrodes with different natures of coating (electrical and thermal resistance) and then impact on residual stresses was envisaged but it was found that the data requested to be able to perform all those simulations could not be supplied within the duration of the project.

The second consideration was that such full coupled “multiphysics” process simulation and all necessary steps for a simulation on high quality demands were not suitable for improvement of car body design where it was considered as not fully and then really applicable.

A common empirical approach to assess fatigue behavior of welded joints as suggested by the International Institute of Welding (IIW) was selected as more promising and thus followed in the further project. Using the effective notch stress approach, it was expected results which directly can be used to simulate fatigue life of components cyclically loaded in air or corrosive environment. Obtaining the results from this method during the project could directly be taken to improve existing guidelines for fatigue assessment of spot-welded joints.

Based on the experimental results from the tests made in air condition (ambient atmosphere) and in corrosive environments, a simulation based methodology to assess fatigue behavior of non-corroded and corroded spot-weld joints have been developed using simulation models.

2.2.7.1.1 Effective notch stress approach

The basic concept of the fatigue design using an effective notch stress approach is described in the IIW recommendations [18,19].

Using the effective notch stress approach, the local stress state was derived directly at the failure critical location of a spot weld which is the notch along the edge of the weld spot between the welded sheets. Compared to the nominal stress approach or structural stress approach, the effective notch stress approach can also capture the influence by the local geometry. Analysis of the notch stresses need to be done using Finite-Element-Analysis and linear-elastic material behavior. Originally, this method was applied to thick walled and moderately thick walled structures where small deflection theory usually is sufficient. Effects of nonlinear geometry (large deformation) might also be considered which will be described in the further text for the simulations on the spot weld specimens.

Based on the concept of micro structural support by Neuber, Radaj suggested considering the geometric notch radius by using a worst case condition of $r = 0$ mm and increase this radius by a fictitious and material dependent radius leading to an effective notch radius of $r_{ref} = 1.0$ mm. This geometric representation led to stresses which already contained the fatigue notch effect [20].

Due to the observation that all welds will excessively show scatter in all geometry parameters and thus also in fatigue life, Seeger et al. have used the idea of an idealized geometry to model the weld geometry and calculate fictitious allowable stress as well as existing fictitious stress due to loading based on this modeling directive [21–24]. Theoretical considerations have led to the same radius for metallic structures of $r_{ref} = 1.0$ mm like in Radaj's concept but should not be confused.

Using such standardized models, nominal stresses obtained experimentally can be recalculated to effective notch stresses. Using distribution functions of cycles to failure from the experiments, a fatigue class for a distinct probability of failure could be derived.

The approach has been demonstrated to work well for seam welds with a thickness of sheets $t > 5$ mm [25,26]. For thinner sheet, a radius of 1mm weakens the cross sections at the weld significantly. In such cases, smaller notch radii have been suggested, i.e. $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm [27].

For stress analysis, characteristic values for strength have been suggested on the basis of applying $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm for thick and moderately thick welded structure (see Table 21). There is strong evidence though that for thin sheets application those FAT values are too conservative [27–30]. See also some comments taken from the conclusions of a recent German cluster research project [31]:

„Accuracy can be improved and scatter decreased if specific SN-curves will be used (holds true especially valid for $r_{ref} = 0,05$ mm) Investigations demonstrate that using existing recommendations, the fatigue life of welded components will be heavily underestimated in some cases. Using the notch stress approach welded components made of steel can be optimized and reliably dimensioned.“

For that reason AutoFatCor results for non-corroded specimen will also be very valuable to gain improved knowledge on suitable FAT-classes for spot welded connections.

Stress quantities for the effective notch stresses are usually maximum principal stress or von Mises equivalent stress. Different FAT classes have to be applied for the two cases.

Figure 77: Derivation of fictitious effective notch stresses using nominal stresses from fatigue tests and a notch factor from numerical analysis using a standardized model and a notch radius of $r = r_{ref} = 1$ mm [19].

For stress relieved (moderately to thick) welds showing low residual stress, there is a large mean stress sensitivity as can be seen in Figure 78. This means stress sensitivity vanished with increasing residual stress in the welds. Mean stress sensitivity can be derived from Figure 78 as well. Usually the FAT-class was obtained for $R = 0.5$ since larger R -values usually gave the same fatigue strength no matter of the state of residual stresses. Fat-classes were defined as FAT XXX/Y, where XXX corresponds to the allowable stress cycle for $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ and Y is the slope exponent of the SN-curve.

Figure 78: Derivation of fatigue class for effective notch stresses for transversely loaded seam welds in probability paper for different stress ratios (R -ratios) of the applied stress cycles and low residual stresses in the welds as derived by Seeger et al. [24].

To derive characteristic values for the allowable stress range for constant amplitude loading, the following assumptions apply:

- The back-calculated pseudo notch stresses follow a log-normal distribution.
- From a sufficient large number of tests on different specimen derived for R -ratio $R = 0.5$, the FAT-class can thus be obtained from the probability paper for log-normal distributions of the stress cycles to failure valid for $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles.
- The FAT-class (= allowable stress cycle for $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$) needs to be derived from probability paper for a large R -ratio and high probability of surveillance with is usually $P_{\bar{U}} = 97.5\%$.
- The FAT-class needs to be modified for lower R -ratios because of the R -dependency for welds with low residual stresses.

This approach has been used analogously using smaller radii for seam welds, i.e. using $r_{ref} = 0,05$ mm, for which the following FAT-classes have been derived in such case for seam welds: Extension of notch stress concept for $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm and multiaxial stress states yields FAT-classes as shown in [27]. These values have been obtained using seam welds. Application to spot welds will be checked in the current project. Analysis can be done using either maximum principal stress σ_1 or equivalent stress σ_{eqv} (von Mises) by taken the appropriate FAT-classes from the following table. In this table m_1 represents the slope exponent of the SN-curve (in this case for seam welds with moderately to thick weld throats). The slope is an important second parameter of the SN-curve for effective notch stresses as can be seen later for the results of spot welded thin walled joints.

Table 21: FAT-class and slope of SN-curve valid for $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm, $R > 0.5$, $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$, $P_{\bar{U}} = 97.5\%$.

r [mm]	0,05	0,05	m_1
Hypotheses	$\Delta\sigma_1$	$\Delta\sigma_{v,Mises}$	
Steel	630	560	3,0

Correction for joints with low residual stress (which can be assumed for spot welded thin sheets) can be obtained by the following equation:

$$f(R) = -0.4 + 1.2R \quad -1 \leq R \leq 0.5 \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

Applied to an R-ratio of $R = 0.1$ as in the tests done for AutoFatCor yields:

$$f(R = 0.1) = 1.16 \quad \text{Eq.5}$$

To be able to compare the effective notch stresses with results from the fatigue testing from AutoFatCor, those FAT-classes further need to be transferred for a probability of failure of 50%.

Correction for $P_{\bar{U}} = 50\%$ using an assumed (lower bound) scatter factor $T_S = 1:1.3$ can be obtained by:

$$s = \frac{1}{2,56} \log \frac{1}{T_N} = 0,045$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{97,5\%} = 10^{\log(\Delta\sigma_{50\%}) - 2*s} \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

this leads to a factor of $\frac{\Delta\sigma_{50\%}}{\Delta\sigma_{97,5\%}} = 1,23 \approx \underline{\underline{1,3}}$

Applying those factors to the FAT-classes from Table 21, modified FAT-classes valid for $R = 0.1$, $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$, $P_{\bar{U}} = 50\%$, were obtained. Using those values, a comparison of the actual notch stresses as back calculated from the AutoFatCor fatigue testing was done. In case of deviations, modified FAT-classes was derived from the AutoFatCor testing results for non-corroded and corroded specimen since we expected that the FAT classes from Table 22, as derived for thicker welds were too conservative for spot welds. Former tests on spot weld fatigue failure or fatigue life of laser welded specimen of thin sheet have given some indication to this.

Table 22: FAT-class and slope of SN-curve valid for $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm, $R > 0.1$, $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$, $P_{\bar{U}} = 50\%$ for moderately to thick welds.

r [mm]	0,05	0,05	
Hypotheses	$\Delta\sigma_1$	$\Delta\sigma_{v,Mises}$	
Steel	950	844	

The usage of these FAT-classes will give an answer if they can be used for spot welds as well. Deviations of these results will give sign for modified FAT-classes to be used for spot welds. The same hold true to assess FAT-classes for corroded spot welds.

Derivation of appropriate new FAT-classes for spot welded specimen is the primary basis to account for corrosion effects in the numerical fatigue assessment procedure as selected and followed within the AutoFatCor project.

Additionally, FAT classes to be used for spot welded specimen in air will be derived as well since the experimental basis supply sufficient data to do so.

With this approach, existing methods used in industry to assess fatigue life of spot welded thin walled structures will be enhanced for better prediction accuracy.

The following steps are presented in the following chapters:

- *Creation of a parametric FEM-Model for the effective notch stress approach using $r = 0.05$ mm to assess the effective notch stress for any sample tested (Lap-shear and T-Peel specimen).*
- *Checking proper meshing by sensitivity studies of meshing parameters on σ_1 and σ_{eqv} -behavior for maximum notch stresses*
- *Checking different clamping conditions of the simulation model.*
- *Calculating the elastic fictitious notch stresses using the parameters for specimens 1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9 and different loadings applied for the experiments using small and as well as large displacement analysis. For T-Peel specimen also, the nonlinear contact condition was implemented as an analysis option. The elastic fictitious notch stresses have been calculated for experiments in air as well as the tests involving corrosion.*
- *Derivation of FAT-classes and comparison of "new" FAT-class with literature values from the IIW community (Table 22) for tests in air and for corrosive environments will be presented in next chapter (task 8.1).*

2.2.7.1.2 Simulation models

2.2.7.1.2.1 Simulation model for lap-shear specimen

For effective notch stress analysis, a parametric model was created to be run in batch mode using the Finite Element Software ANSYS™. This procedure was necessary because a very large number of linear and nonlinear analysis runs had to be calculated using the model for the different specimen and load levels.

➤ *Uncertainty of input data*

The model was based on the following assumptions of the input data because further information was not available:

- i) The spot weld was located in the center of the overlapping region. Lateral or axial displacement of the spot weld might yield in higher stresses*
- ii) Weld electrodes might produce indentations. In the following input file, those plastic deformations were not contained but might increase the notch root stress.*
- iii) Inhomogeneous material properties were not known and thus not contained in the finite-element-model.*
- iv) Stress resultants at both ends of the specimen in the testing machine might be off line in reality. Input data did not supply any information on that. Also tolerances for the dimensions were not covered by the input data provided. The effect of possible geometric deviations might lead to significant deviations of stress results.*

For the following model, an input file for interactive use for single runs *geometry_notch.txt* or activation in batch mode (which requires an additional batch control file *batchrun.inp*) was created. Details of model, analysis and post-processing as programmed in the input file are described in [32].

➤ *Geometry, idealization and discretization*

Parameters and dimensions of the basic geometry are given in Figure 79. Only half of the specimen was contained in the simulation model due to symmetry. Parameters had to be inserted by the dimensions of the full model though.

A parametric geometric model for the specimen has been generated using the ANSYS parametric design language APDL. The volume has been partitioned to enable:

- *a local fine mesh in a toroidal volume around the notch*
- *a medium size mesh in the transition volume adjacent to the volume having the fine mesh size*
- *the remaining volumes for coarse meshing*

This strategy enabled a very detailed stress resolution in the notch of the weld nugget and a reasonable limitation of the total number of elements in the model. The availability of a full parametric

geometric model enabled quick analysis of the different specimens having different dimensions like the weld nugget diameter.

Figure 79: Basic geometrical data of specimen.

Figure 80: Schematic of parameterized geometry and area partitioning (blue lines and circular areas around notch).

To separate the model in the overlapping region of the two strips outside the diameter of the weld nugget, a small gap could be considered in the model. This gap did not lead to a reduction of the sheet thicknesses. The bending moment in the weld nugget would be a little higher due to the definition of this gap. The gap value should be set to a very low value (i.e. $gap = 0.01$ mm or less).

For the notch, a toroid surface with a notch radius r_1 was contained in the model. The diameter of the spot weld started/ended in the root of the toroid notch surface.

In the vicinity of the notch root, different areas were created for obtaining a smooth mesh transition in this section. SHELL281 was used to coat the notch root surface with a thin membrane (thickness = 10^{-5} mm) for easy postprocessing of those surfaces.

The stiffness of those elements had no significant influence on the overall structural behavior of the model. The advantage of those elements was the ability to process plane stress states easily on those surfaces. Also, the elements reflected the stresses directly on the surface but values from the integration points extrapolated to the nodes of the solid elements.

For all solid elements SOLID186, a higher-order 20-node solid element with quadratic shape functions was used. The element supported plasticity, hyperelasticity, creep, stress stiffening, large deflection, and large strain capabilities. It also has mixed formulation capability for simulating deformations of nearly incompressible elastoplastic materials, and fully incompressible hyperelastic materials.

➤ Material properties

Notch stress analysis had to be performed using linear elastic material properties. The following properties are chosen:

$E = 210$ GPa : Modulus of elasticity
 $\nu = 0.3$: Poisson ratio

➤ *Uncertainties*

Input data had some uncertainties (see above) which in consequence are embedded in the resulting model. The results obtained by using the model had to be judged carefully with respect to those uncertainties.

The overlapping sheets were modeled without contact elements. Deformation of the displacements under loading revealed that no contact occurred due to loading but gapping between both metal strips. Figure 81 shows an example displacement plot (scaled displacements) to demonstrate this effect.

Figure 81: Example of (scaled) displacement.

➤ *Load cases and boundary conditions*

Figure 82: Boundary conditions and loading.

Loading was applied by uniform pressure on the front face. The pressure was calculated using the total maximum force on the specimen by:

$$PRES = - \frac{\quad}{2} \quad \text{Eq.7}$$

To achieve tension in the specimen, a negative pressure needed to be applied.

➤ *Analysis type(s)*

The input file considers two analysis types, small and large displacement static analysis. For nonlinear analysis, two loadsteps are defined: loadstep 1 to define zero load and a second loadstep 2 to apply the force. For nonlinear solution control standard settings are taken, i.e. solution control is on, predictor is activated, load is fully applied in a single substep, between 15 and 26 equilibrium iterations.

➤ *Results processing*

The input file was prepared to automatically create a sequence of plots and listings with standard settings for views, style and titles.

➤ *Model checking and validation*

The model geometry has been checked by the resulting finite element mesh for specimen 1. Stresses and reaction forces have been checked for plausibility in comparison with previous results from a different model.

2.2.7.1.2.2 *Study on boundary conditions for lap-shear specimens*

To get an understanding of the importance of boundary conditions for the thin walled specimen, different boundary conditions have been studied as can be seen in Figure 83.

Figure 83: Boundary conditions.

- BC1: fixation of the upper specimen completely in y-direction, and allow it to move only in x-direction along in line with the force applied. This boundary condition complies best with the situation used for the experiments.
- BC2: free to move upper end in y-direction. The lateral displacement of the upper end will tend to move laterally to get in line with the force direction of the lower fixation. Due to linear geometric analysis the resulting lateral movement will usually not be exact in line with the lower reaction force.
- BC3: at first lateral displacement by amount $u_y = \frac{1}{2}(t_1 + t_2)$ of the upper end and then application of load F to enforce alignment of the applied force exactly in line with the lower restraint force.

The difference of local stresses upon selection of the boundary conditions can be seen in the following table for a single type of specimen using some preliminary data for dimensions. The other specimen has been analyzed accordingly but do not show additional information and thus are not presented here.

Table 23: Results of different boundary conditions BC1, BC2, BC3 for linear and nonlinear geometric analysis of specimen material #1.

Linear solution $p = 1 \text{ MPa} \cong 17,5 \text{ N}$, scaled for $F_{\text{max,exp}} = 733\text{N}$

location	s1 maximum	location	seqv maximum	t1	t2	d1	uy		
63001	1559,4	63001	1385,5	0,7	0,7	5,1	0		BC1
196	2748,3	196	2438,2	0,7	0,7	5,1	131,04		BC2
196	1684,9	196	1496,9	0,7	0,7	5,1	0,7		BC3

Nonlinear solution $F_{\text{max,exp}} = 733\text{N}$

location	s1 maximum	location	seqv maximum	t1	t2	d1	uy		
198	1394,4	198	1238,9	0,7	0,7	5,1	0		BC1
									BC2
198	1467,8	198	1304,1	0,7	0,7	5,1	0,7		BC3

Some important findings from the stress analyses using different boundary conditions were:

- For linear geometric analysis, the lateral displacements were far off realistic values which can be seen in Table 23. For that reason, BC2 was skipped for the other materials in this study on boundary conditions.

- *Nonlinear geometric analysis (with linear material behavior) resulted in lower maximum effective notch stresses of at least -10%. This effect is due to the rotation of the weld nugget because of the little stiffness of the sheet straps above and below the spot weld. This gives sign to handle realistic large scale spot welded structures by including the effect of low stiffness behavior of the sheets joined by spot welding. Some authors argued (for example see [25]), that sheet structures with low stiffness resulted in SN-curves having higher slope exponents. This effect might be the same as due to stress reduction due to large deformation. This effect was not yet fully understood and it was reasonable to follow this in the upcoming investigations.*
- *The location of maximum stress changed if the boundary condition differed but also in case of small or large displacement analysis.*
- *With respect to the experiments of AUTOFATCOR, BC1 was the most realistic one since at both ends spacers have been aligned to the clamped sheets to keep the line of the two clamping forces in a straight line.*

2.2.7.1.2.3 Simulation model for T-peel specimen

Similar to the Lap-shear specimen, a parametric model was created to be run in batch mode using the Finite Element Software ANSYS™ for the T-Peel specimen as well. For more details, see [33].

Figure 84: Solid Model for T-Peel specimen and origin and orientation of global coordinate system.

➤ Uncertainty of input data

The model was based on the following assumptions of the input data because further information was not available:

- The spot weld was located in the center of the overlapping region. Lateral (z) or axial displacement (x) of the spot weld might yield in higher stresses*
- Weld electrodes might produce indentations. In the following input file, those plastic deformations were not contained but might increase the notch root stress.*
- Inhomogeneous material properties were not known and thus not contained in the finite-element-model.*
- Stress resultants at both ends of the specimen in the testing machine might be off line in reality. Input data did not supply any information on that. Also tolerances for the dimensions were not covered by the input data provided. The effect of possible geometric deviations might lead to significant deviations of stress results.*

➤ Geometry, idealization and discretization

Parameters and dimensions of the basic geometry are contained in Figure 85. Only half of the specimen was contained in the simulation model due to symmetry.

Figure 85: Basic geometrical data of specimen.

Figure 86: Schematic of parameterized geometry and area partitioning (blue lines and circular areas around notch).

To separate the model in the overlapping region of the two strips outside the diameter of the weld nugget, a small gap was considered in the model. This gap did not lead to a reduction of the sheet thicknesses. The bending moment in the weld nugget was a little higher due to the definition of this gap. The gap value should be set to a very low value (i.e. $gap = 0.001$ mm or less). Also, in case of nonlinear contact, the gap had some minor effect on the distribution of contact pressure.

For the notch, a toroid surface with a notch radius r_1 was contained in the model. The diameter of the spot weld started/ended in the root of the toroid notch surface.

In the vicinity of the notch root, different areas were created for obtaining a smooth mesh transition in this section. SHELL281 elements were used to coat the notch root surface with a thin membrane (thickness = 10^{-5} mm) for easy postprocessing of those surfaces.

The stiffness of those elements had no significant influence on the overall structural behavior of the model. The advantage of those elements was the ability to process plane stress states easily on those surfaces. Also, the elements reflected the stresses directly on the surface but values from the integration points extrapolated to the nodes of the solid elements.

For all solid elements SOLID186, a higher-order 20-node solid element with quadratic shape functions was used. Reduced integration was selected. The element supported plasticity, hyperelasticity, creep, stress stiffening, large deflection, and large strain capabilities. It also has mixed formulation capability for simulating deformations of nearly incompressible elastoplastic materials, and fully incompressible hyperelastic materials.

If nonlinear contact was selected, the following elements and settings were used:

TARGET170 with Keyopt,2,1,1 (Higher-Order Elements at target)

CONTACT174 with

Keyopt,3,5,4 (Auto ICONT adjustment)

Keyopt,3,10,0 (Contact stiffness update: Each load step if FKN is redefined during load step (pair based).

r,2,,,,,0001,,,,-3.0 (FKN for bending dominant deformation (no bulk deformation))

➤ Material properties

Notch stress analysis had to be performed using linear elastic material properties. The following properties were chosen:

$E = 210 \text{ GPa}$: Modulus of elasticity
 $\nu = 0.3$: Poisson ratio

➤ *Uncertainties*

Input data had some uncertainties (see above) which in consequence were embedded in the resulting model. The results obtained by using the model had to be judged carefully with respect to those uncertainties.

The overlapping sheets were modeled with or without contact elements. Deformation of the displacements under loading revealed that no contact occurred due to loading but gapping between both metal strips. Figure 87 shows an example displacement plot (scaled displacements) to demonstrate this effect.

Figure 87: Example of (scaled) displacement.

In the following figures, the effect of nonlinear contact in the interface between the bonded sheets was demonstrated. Including nonlinear contact, the notch stress ($\Delta\sigma_1$ or $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$) reduced about 6% compared to an analysis without contact elements. In the following results, analyses without contact elements were mainly shown.

Figure 88: Deformation in contact zone without (left) and with (right) nonlinear contact.

Figure 89: Notch stress distribution σ_1 for $F = 99 \text{ N}$, specimen #7 without (left) and with (right) nonlinear contact.

2.2.7.1.2.4 Specifications of analysis of the simulation of T-peel specimens

➤ Load cases and boundary conditions

Loading was applied by uniform pressure on the top face. The pressure was calculated using the total maximum force on the specimen by:

$$\text{PRES} = - \frac{\text{---}}{1} \quad \text{Eq.8}$$

To achieve tension in the specimen, a negative pressure needed to be applied.

Figure 90: Boundary conditions and loading.

➤ Analysis type(s)

The input file considered two analysis types, small and large displacement static analysis.

For nonlinear analysis, two load steps were defined: loadstep 1 to define zero load and a second loadstep 2 to apply the force. For nonlinear solution, control standard settings were taken, i.e. solution control was on, predictor was activated, load was fully applied in a single substep, between 15 and 26 equilibrium iterations.

➤ Results processing

The input file was prepared to automatically create a sequence of plots and listings with standard settings for views, style and titles.

➤ Model checking and validation

The model geometry has been checked for plausibility using the resulting model dimension. No further checking has been made, i.e. for mesh density. The contact penetrations and the distribution of contact pressure have been checked and both show reasonable values. Especially the maximum penetration has given small values to ensure proper contact representation for bulk deformations of large surface contact.

Stresses and reaction forces have been checked for plausibility. For further application, additional checking of results is strongly recommended before using any results.

The influence of the thickness of the dummy shell elements in the notch root on resulting maximum stresses should also be checked before using the file for further analyses. In case of larger differences with/without the shell elements, the thickness should be further reduced to reduce the influence of the shell elements on the total stiffness of the structure.

Mesh densities investigated for the lap-shear model to obtain sufficient numerical accuracy were used for the T-Peel model as well.

2.2.7.1.3 Simulation results for fatigue tests in air

The results based on the notch stress ranges (effective notch stress concept with a reference radius at the notch tip of spot-weld) are presented in Figure 91 to Figure 93 for maximum principal stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$. The same method was also developed based on the von Mises equivalent stress range $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$. S-N curve using the slope and FAT-class according to Table 24 is also plotted in these diagrams. Two different numerical methods were considered, small and large displacement:

- *Small displacement uses linear elastic and ideal plastic material, without hardening. Displacement of 8 mm is imposed as boundary condition. Arclength-method is used for solving.*
- *Large displacement considers linear elastic material with isotropic hardening. The load is imposed at the boundary of the model. Solving is performed with the Newton-Raphson method.*

Table 24: FAT-class and slope of S-N curve valid a reference notch radius $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm, a loading ratio $R \geq 0.1$, a fatigue life $N = 2 \times 10^6$ cycles and a probability $P = 50\%$.

r [mm]	0,05	0,05	m_1
Hypotheses	$\Delta\sigma_1$	$\Delta\sigma_{v,Mises}$	
Steel	950	844	3,0

Note that the Table 24 comes out from the value of FAT-class and slope of SN-curve valid for a reference notch radius $r_{ref} = 0.05$ mm, a loading ratio $R \geq 0.5$, a fatigue life $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles and a probability $P = 97.5\%$. The calculation from $R \geq 0.5$ to $R \geq 0.1$ was based on the mean stress correction with an assumption of low residual stress for joints (which can be assumed for spot-welded made of thin sheets). After that, a second correction was applied to those FAT-classes to transfer the probability of failure $P = 97.5\%$ to $P = 50\%$. This enabled to compare the effective notch stresses with all results from the fatigue testing performed in the project. FAT-classes were given for 2 million of cycles.

Figure 91: Fatigue capacity $\log C$ as calculated using maximum principal stress $\Delta\sigma_1$, plotted in a normal probability diagram.

Regression curves for mean probability of failure and ± 2 times the standard deviation are also contained in the following S-N curves (Figure 92 and Figure 93) to represent 2.5 and 97.5% failure probabilities.

Figure 92: Maximum principal notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_I$, small displacement analysis; specimen 1-9.

Figure 93: Maximum principal notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_I$, large displacement analysis; specimens 1-9.

To get an understanding about the correlation on the distribution of the notch stresses, log-values of fatigue capacity values C were plotted in a normal probability diagram. Since most of those values showed good correlation with log-normal behavior, all results were kept and assumed following a log-normal distribution for further data processing.

The fatigue capacity coefficient C was calculated for each specimen using an assumed slope exponent $m_1 = 3.0$ in the following equation:

$$C = \Delta\sigma_1^{m_1} \cdot N \quad \text{Eq.9}$$

The probability was calculated using Rossow's formula for assumed lognormal distributed quantities:

$$P = \frac{3i-1}{3n+1} \quad \text{Eq.10}$$

where i is the order number over n values.

Important findings from the notch stress analyses for fatigue in air tests can be summarized as follows:

- *Figure 92 and Figure 93 also presented curves for mean probability of failure $P=50\%$ but also curves for 2.5 and 97.5 % probability of failure derived from all specimen results. Those lines did not represent reasonable behavior. Slope and scatter band obviously did not represent the cloud of data points suitably. This will be discussed in WP8 in more detail.*
- *In general but especially in high cycle, all of these S-N curves demonstrated high conservatism. This indicated the strong need for specific FAT-classes for thin sheet spot-welds using the notch stress approach.*
- *All notch stress values were above the recommended FAT-class taken from reference [27] (for "moderately to thick" welds including an assumed slope exponent m_1 equal to 3.0 which are also contained as blue lines in the above figures. Large displacement analysis reduced notch stresses by about 3 to 12% for the specimen and loads investigated in this project. Differences were larger for smaller load levels (since all materials have the same modulus of elasticity). Conservatism with respect to the FAT-class in Table 24 seems to be less pronounced for large displacement results. Using large displacement, results required a suitable large displacement FAT-class though which would be below the one contained in the diagram.*
- *Even though, notch stresses from large displacement analysis were little lower than obtained by linear geometric theory, those results were still higher than the allowable stress ranges for "moderately to thick" welds from reference [27].*

2.2.7.1.4 Simulation results for fatigue-corrosion tests

The results for notch stress ranges are presented in Figure 94 and Figure 95 for maximum principal stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$. For comparison, the results in air were also marked with grey symbols. SN-curve using slope and FAT-class according to Table 24 was also plotted in the diagram. Again, the same method was also developed based on the von Mises equivalent stress range $\Delta\sigma_{\text{eqv}}$.

As for the previous section, to get an understanding about the correlation on the distribution of the notch stresses, log of fatigue capacity values C were plotted in normal probability diagram. Since most of those values showed good correlation with lognormal behavior, all results were again kept for further data processing.

The fatigue capacity was calculated for each specimen using an assumed slope exponent $m_1 = 3.0$ according to Eq. 9 and the probability according to Eq. 10.

Figure 94: Fatigue capacity $\log C$ as calculated using maximum principal stress $\Delta\sigma_1$, plotted in normal probability diagram (small displacement analysis); results for experiments in air and corrosive environments separately (left) and combined (right).

Figure 95: Maximum principal notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$, small displacement analysis; specimens 1-9.

From the notch stress analyses for fatigue in corrosive environments, the following comments may be drawn:

- Reduction of fatigue life in the corrosive environments as experimentally obtained in task 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3 was not severe as it can be seen in Figure 94.

- Mainly simultaneous fatigue/corrosion testing reduced fatigue life under corrosive environments. This can be seen in the notch stress results as well.
- Using the FAT-class from Table 24, the results for corrosive environment were a little non conservative for few cases in low cycle range (< 100,000 cycles) but they still seemed conservative in high cycle range. The latter conclusion needed to be used carefully though since further investigations at stress ranges below 1400 MPa ($\Delta\sigma_1$) and 1200 MPa ($\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$) would be required to check the behavior in those stress ranges as well. Since corrosion is a time depending effect, further reductions in fatigue life in those stress ranges would be expected.
- Corrosive environment required as specific FAT-class for the notch stress concept as developed in task 8.1.

2.2.7.1.5 Conclusions for Task 7-1

Parametric Finite-Element-Models to derive notch stresses for a reference radius $r_{ref} = 0,05$ mm for lap shear and T-peel specimens were created and tested for stress convergence, accuracy and efficiency. The model has been used for small and large displacement analysis and can be used for the effective notch stress approach.

Effect of boundary conditions have been checked and have shown a great influence on the notch stresses. Since no experimental stresses have been obtained during testing, stresses from simulation cannot be compared for validation purposes. Based on the experience, the selected boundary conditions of the models should provide results with sufficient accuracy though.

Effective notch stresses for maximum principal stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$ and von Mises equivalent stress range $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$ required the definition of specific FAT-classes compared to existing recommendations based on "moderately to thick" welds.

This holds true for experiments in air and corrosive environments. Different SN-curves to be used for design assessment for air and corrosive environments seem to be necessary.

The same hold true, if analyses differentiate between small and large displacements due to pronounced deformation behavior of thin walled structures (i.e. due to significant rotation of weld nugget for lap-shear specimen). Large displacement analyses of the specimen used within the present work were 3 to 12 % smaller than results from small displacements. Large displacement analyses in practice of body development would thus require also special FAT-classes to be used.

The effective notch stress approach has been demonstrated to be a suitable empirical approach to consider different environmental conditions in the assessment of fatigue life of thin walled spot-welded structures. A unique formalism with parameters based on the IIW recommendations [27,34] has been used for both the fatigue and the fatigue-corrosion results. However, as detailed in section 2.2.8.1 Task 8.1: Life prediction, different parameters can be adopted to fit fatigue and fatigue-corrosion experimental data.

2.2.7.2 Task 7.2: Modeling corrosion-fatigue of adhesive bonded joints

The objective of this task was to develop a tool to evaluate fatigue life of adhesively bonded structures. A simulation method was developed to model tensile and fatigue properties of adhesive bonded specimens based on cohesive zone model. All data from WP5 and WP6 were necessary to develop the model.

The model was developed in successive steps. First, cohesive elements properties were evaluated based on tensile testing in air. Another approach with stain gauge technique was also investigated. Then, fatigue parameters were calibrated based on fatigue tests in air. Finally, adhesive failure was simulated using additional element elimination procedure and on a damage model accumulation. Moisture diffusion was also investigated as important parameter in the fatigue-corrosion damage mechanism.

2.2.7.2.1 Cohesive Zone Model

A study has been carried out on the most up-to-date works in the bonded joints fatigue field in order to find a suitable framework in which implement the development of the bonded joints corrosion-fatigue model.

The selected framework consisted in:

- accounting of the damage cumulated during fatigue loading,
- modeling of bonding by means of Cohesive Zone Model (CZM), taking into account initiation and propagation energies.

The damage evolution law was expressed in terms of cyclic damage rate as presented in Figure 96.

$$\frac{\Delta D}{\Delta N} = \begin{cases} \alpha(\varepsilon_{\max} - \varepsilon_{th})^\beta, & \varepsilon_{\max} > \varepsilon_{th} \\ 0, & \varepsilon_{\max} \leq \varepsilon_{th} \end{cases}$$

$$\varepsilon_{\max} = \frac{\varepsilon_n}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\varepsilon_n}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_s}{2}\right)^2}$$

Figure 96: Fatigue degradation model.

where ΔD is the increment of damage, ΔN is the cycle increment, ε_{\max} is the maximum principal strain in the cohesive element which is a combination of normal and shear component of strain (ε_n and ε_s), ε_{th} is the threshold strain (a critical value of ε_{\max} below which no fatigue damage occurred) and α and β are material constants.

The CZM is a methodology to model the fatigue damage in adhesively bonded joints [7]. Hillerborg *et al.* proposed a fictitious crack model defining tractions vs. the crack opening displacement, contrary to previous works, where the cohesive zone tractions had been defined as a function of the crack tip distance [35].

The traction-separation description here employed and sketched in Figure 97 is bi-linear (i.e. both before and after damage initiation) and is defined by the initial stiffness (E_0), defined as traction divided by separation, the tripping traction (T) and the fracture energy (G) for each spatial dimension [7].

Figure 97: Schematic damage process zone and corresponding bi-linear traction-separation law in an adhesively bonded joint (figure from reference [7]).

As already explained on task T3.4, the exposed framework requires special experimental tests in order to characterize material properties in terms of Tripping traction T and fracture energy G_c .

Special measurements must therefore be conducted for both tensile tests and fatigue tests for the Single Lap Joint geometry, taking especially into account the fracture initiation phase. In order to do so, the back face technique and visual analysis were adopted.

The combination of each of the pure response along the corresponding spatial axis required a combination criterion (Figure 98): the Benzeggagh–Kenane criterion [36] was employed:

$$G_{IC} + (G_{IC} + G_{IIC}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^\eta = G_I + G_{II},$$

where:

- the C is a critical fracture energy value i.e. the value required for the failure along the corresponding axis (I or II);
- η is a material property.

Figure 98: Mixed-mode bi-linear traction–separation law (figure from reference [7]).

In all the analyses, a maximum nominal stress criterion was employed to make the damage initiation: damage was assumed to initiate when either of the normal or shear components of stress exceeded the respective critical value (tripping tractions T_I or T_{II}).

Figure 99: Finite element mesh and boundary conditions employed by Khoramishad et al. [37] while simulating the experiment detailed by Shenoy et al. [38] (figure from reference [7])– Two samples from 7075-T6 aluminum alloy (length 100mm, thickness 2.5mm, width 25mm) joined by adhesive FM 73 M (overlap length 12.5mm).

The most affirmed commercial Finite Element Softwares (e.g. ABAQUS and MSC.MARC) provided special elements that implemented this facility for both 2D for plane stress/plane strain and 3D analyses.

ABAQUS was employed by Khoramishad et al. [37] to validate the traction-separation CZM on the experimental results obtained by Shenoy et al. [38]. Khoramishad et al. simulated the behavior during static tensile test of a single lap joint made up of two substrates, cut from 2.5 mm thick sheets of 7075-T6 aluminum alloy, bonded using the toughened epoxy film adhesive FM 73 M (Figure 99).

2.2.7.2.2 Lap-shear and T-peel models

The Lap-Shear and T-Peel configurations were modeled with the commercial Finite Element Software ABAQUS [39]. The model bonded lap-shear configuration is shown in Figure 100.

Figure 100: model bonded lap-shear configuration – mesh characteristics.

The thickness of the materials was set to 1.5 mm for combination n°14 and to 1.2mm for all the other combinations.

The adhesive material was described by a layer of Cohesive Elements keeping attention to define the elements with the right connectivity so that the side of elements that has to work in the normal direction was positioned perpendicular to the materials and the side that had to work in the shear direction was positioned parallel to them. The model bonded T-peel configuration is shown in Figure 101.

Figure 101: Model bonded T-peel configuration – mesh characteristics – non uniform thickness area.

The thickness of the materials was set to 1.2 mm for all T-peel combinations.

During the calibration phase, it has been noticed a strong dependency of the peak force obtained from the simulation on the extension of the adhesive material in the non-uniform thickness area where the radii started to evolve. This fact, derived from simulations, could suggest a reason why the experimental T-Peel data were so scattered. That adhesive region was quite out of control during the adhesion process, leading finally to more or less peak load depending upon the distribution of adhesive in this region.

The adhesive material properties have been calibrated considering the extension of the adhesive in the non-uniform thickness area as reported in Figure 101.

The adhesive material was described by a layer of Cohesive Elements keeping attention to define the elements with the right connectivity so that the side of elements that had to work in the normal direction was positioned perpendicular to the materials and the side that had to work in the shear direction was positioned parallel to them.

➤ Material properties

The properties of the materials have been derived from the tensile tests carried out in task 3.3. The three curves elaborated for the three different materials and implemented in the Finite Element models are shown in Figure 102.

Figure 102: True stress-true strain curves elaborated for the three different materials.

➤ Adhesive

The cohesive elements material properties for a traction-separation response were defined by the stiffness K (that is often chosen as a penalty parameter [39]) in the normal and shear directions, the normal and shear tipping tractions and the normal and shear energies. Those last are dissipated as a result of the damage process and are also called the fracture energy. The fracture energy was equal to the area under the traction-separation curve as illustrated in Figure 103.

In addition to these parameters, the user can select more parameters and choose among different behaviors that are the viscosity, the way how the modes normal and shear are mixed in a complex state of load, the way how the damage evolution behaves (typically linear or exponential) and the max degradation that allows to set a maximum value of cumulated damage over which element elimination occurs.

Figure 103: Characteristic traction-separation response.

2.2.7.2.3 Final tuning of material and adhesive properties

For simplicity, the first approach followed for the simulation of the Lap-Shear and T-Peel tests has been based on the use of only one adhesive material properties set and to calibrate it. Indeed, the same adhesive was used in all cases and some properties were expected. However, this first approach exhibited a weak point in the fact that the interfacial behavior of the three materials and their metallic coatings (HC420LA+Z100, HCT780C+ZE and 22MnB5+Z140) with the adhesive Betamate 1460S can be different, due to several parameters such as the coating roughness, the chemical composition and affinity to moisture absorption. The failure surfaces analyzed for the different combinations showed different percentages of cohesive/adhesive failures. Therefore, even if the adhesive analyzed was one (DOW Betamate 1460S), three slightly different cohesive material parameter sets have been considered.

The final tuning of the material properties of the adhesive has been carried out by means of inverse calibration of the tensile tests in air. Parameters, considered as "initial parameters" are reported in the Table 25.

Table 25: Final calibrated adhesive material properties.

id	τ_N	τ_S	G_N	G_S	B.K. power	E_N	E_S	μ	max degrad.
	[MPa]		[kJ/m ²]			[Mpa/mm]		[N*s/mm]	
10	30	23	3	13.5	2	180	65	10 ⁻⁵	0.4
11	30	23	3	13.5	2	180	65	10 ⁻⁵	0.4
12	30	27.5	3	15.5	2	180	65	10 ⁻⁵	0.4
13	30	27.5	3	15.5	2	180	65	10 ⁻⁵	0.4
14	30	23	3	14	2	180	65	10 ⁻⁵	0.4

The results of the inverse calibrations in terms of force displacement numerical curves are reported and compared to the experimental ones in Figure 104 to Figure 108 for the different configurations.

Figure 104: Combination 10 – Lap-Shear - Final adhesive material properties calibration.

Figure 105: Combination 11 – T-Peel - Final adhesive material properties calibration.

Figure 106: Combination 12 – Lap-Shear - Final adhesive material properties calibration.

Figure 107: Combination 13 - Final adhesive material properties calibration.

Figure 108: Combination 14 - Final adhesive material properties calibration.

With a single set of materials parameter for all adhesive specimens, the correlation with experimental and numerical results of the tensile tests was not good as show in previous reports. Therefore, the differentiation of adhesive material properties has been considered for each material. Finally, the correlation with the last sets of adhesive material properties is satisfactory for all the combinations.

2.2.7.2.4 Strain gauge technique

The tensile tests on adhesive samples lap-shear combinations 10, 12 and 14 have been carried out with micro-strain gauges in order to highlight early adhesive failure conditions.

Despite an extensive activity oriented to obtain the experimental behavior, poor agreement between micro-strain gauge data and local numerical data have been obtained as illustrated in Figure 109 for combination 12.

Figure 109: Comparison between numerical local data and experimental micro-strain-gauge data for combination 12.

On the basis of the behavior of A and B micro-strain gauges, numerical results did not highlight an inversion of sign that was evident from experimental data: B micro-strain gauge started with compressive behavior while A micro-strain gauge started with traction behavior. It seems that the numerical normal stiffness of the adhesive is not so high. A higher normal stiffness could lead to a differentiation of B and A data. Some trials have been done on the model, changing the normal adhesive stiffness leading to a typical result reported in Figure 110.

Figure 110: Typical result with higher adhesive normal stiffness for combination 12.

Despite the differentiation of B and A data, the higher adhesive normal stiffness parameter led unavoidably to a poor agreement of the tensile test comparison for combination 13 (same material and T-Peel configuration), see Figure 111.

Figure 111: Comparison between numerical and experimental tensile test for combination 13 with higher adhesive normal stiffness parameter.

It must be noticed that in the literature, the adhesive stiffness for the cohesive zone model can be assumed also equal to the adhesive bulk stiffness. In this sense, the higher normal stiffness could be reasonable, but the poor agreement with the tensile test result in Figure 71 indicates that this normal stiffness parameter cannot be used with the present set of adhesive material parameters.

It has been decided to keep the initial tuned adhesive material parameters from Table 25.

2.2.7.2.5 Sensitivity and Calibration of fatigue parameters for cohesive elements model

The sensitivity analysis on fatigue material parameters a , β and ϵ_{th} described in section 2.2.7.2.1 has been carried out. Taking into account, as reference, the combination 12 the following experimental points have been considered as target for calibration of fatigue parameters:

Table 26: Reference experimental points for calibration of combination 12 fatigue parameters.

Experimental points	Number of cycles to failure	Load (kN)
Point 1	143 949	11
Point 2	708 315	9

Result on sensitivity analysis for the ϵ_{th} parameter is reported in Figure 112. Same work was also performed for the calibration of a and β parameters.

Despite the large amount of simulations and time spent of this calibration, it has not been possible to achieve to a good final calibration of the fatigue parameters. This approach cannot lead to practical methodology as expected in this project. The first conclusion that can be drawn is that cohesive elements are not suitable for the development of a practical tool for the adhesive joints design.

Further analysis have been also made considering the sensitivity on the numerical parameter related to the fatigue routine that is called every increment and where at every increment corresponds to a bunch of cycles. Depending on how many cycles are considered every increment, the solution can be more or less accurate and more or less time consuming. In the following, Figure 113 is reported the result of this sensitivity analysis.

Green and blue points showed that varying the number of cycles per increment the resulting life changes and is higher for the case that considers more cycles per increment. This is reasonable since the progressive degradation is updated "less frequently" than the case that considers less cycles per

increment. However, this approach was not fully satisfactory and another approach should be implemented in the model as described in the next paragraph.

Fatigue in air LS config 12 - FEM: $\alpha = 4 \cdot 27 = 108$; $\beta = 2 \cdot 1.12 = 2.24$

Figure 112: Sensitivity considering the parameter ϵ_{th} .

Fatigue in air LS config 12

Figure 113: Sensitivity analysis on combination 12 depending on the number of cycles per increment.

2.2.7.2.6 Adhesive failure and cohesive element approach

On the basis of the experimental results and different exposure conditions, the adhesive failure of the joint has an important contribution. The reduction of strength of the joint can be addressed to the percentage of adhesive failure. When adhesive failure occurs with a certain percentage of overlap area, one hypothesis that can be made is that the area failed adhesively has a negligible contribution to the strength of the joint. The area that reacts to the external load is basically the area that fails cohesively.

In order to describe the adhesive failure, starting from the properties tuned for the cohesive elements from the static tensile tests in air, the sensitivity to “cohesive failing” length of the joint strength after corrosion and/or fatigue test has been made. The sensitivity has been carried out eliminating from the model a certain amount of overlap cohesive elements in order to simulate only the portion of adhesive that reacts cohesively. Considering combination 12, starting from the initial overlap length of 20mm, seven cases have been considered, from 10% to 90% of reduction almost every 10%, as illustrated in Figure 114 and reported in Table 27.

Figure 114: Deformed shape and von Mises Stress on combination 12 for the different adhesive failure percentages.

Table 27: Sensitivity on adhesive failure percentage to peak load.

Overlap original length [mm]	20							
Overlap reduction [mm]	0	2	4	6	8	10	16	18
Overlap reduction [%]	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	80%	90%
Peak load [kN]	24,6	22,2	19,7	17,3	14,8	12,4	4,9	2,4

The model results have been compared in Figure 115 with all the data available within the project in terms of percentage of adhesive failure and peak load, for the cases where the static residual strength has been tested, and load level for the fatigue tests. The results of this comparison showed a good agreement with the residual strength tests for the simply corroded samples in the different conditions. For the fatigue in air, the experimental data seemed to behave better than the simulation and for the combined fatigue-corrosion, experimental data seems to behave worse.

In order to consider the degradation of cohesive properties during combined corrosion fatigue, the cohesive properties have been calibrated considering the environmental conditions, working with the model of combination 12 and a percentage of adhesive failure of 70% and 90%. In particular, 70% of adhesive failure has been used to calibrate the properties and the condition at 90% of adhesive failure was used to find the slope of the trend line in Figure 115. Only the tuned degraded cohesive parameters that were changed in comparison with those obtained from tests in air are reported in Table 28. The percentage of reduction was calculated from the initial parameters of Table 25.

Table 28: Tuned degraded cohesive properties and percentage of reduction compared to initial parameters (Table 25).

	TT _n (MPa)	TT _s (MPa)	G _n (kJ/m ²)	G _s (kJ/m ²)
	16	13	1,5	5
% of reduction	53%	47%	50%	32%

The tuned degraded cohesive properties can be used to make easier the process of tuning α , β and ϵ_{th} , the parameters that describe the fatigue evolution.

FEM results considering actual overlap length were in very good agreement with residual strength of simply corroded samples. Thus, it can be supposed that corrosion exposure led to a permanent degradation of the adhesive-substrate interface. The model considers the initial tuned cohesive properties from tests in air (Table 25) and percentage of adhesive failure modeled as element

elimination. Thus, the cohesive properties of the adhesive at the moment of the tensile testing for residual strength determination were still close to the samples tested in air, while for the adhesive-substrate interface the degradation during corrosion has been permanent. So, it is possible that there has been a restoration of the properties of the adhesive after exposure due to a progressive diffusion of moisture penetrating during corrosion test out of the adhesive during transportation and disposal time before tensile testing.

For the fatigue in air, there is an agreement between FEM and experimental data only for the slope. Percentage of adhesive failure was either slightly overestimated (5 to 10 %), or, because of the frequency of the fatigue test (high strain rate), the final failure occurred at higher load than during tensile test, because of the strain rate dependency of the mechanical properties of the adhesive, see [40] for instance.

Figure 115: Comparison between FEM results and experimental tests concerning the integration of adhesive failure in the CZM approach.

Considering the FEM data compared to the results on combined fatigue corrosion, the results were quite different. Indeed, both the adhesive-substrate interface and the cohesive properties of the adhesive were degraded during the mechanical load application. Therefore, in addition to the elimination of the elements for the description of the percentage of adhesive failure, there should be a further cohesive properties tuning in order to consider the degradation of the adhesive material, as reported, for instance, in Figure 116, from [16].

Figure 116: Degradation of the cohesive properties for the adhesive subjected to corrosion conditions [16].

Moisture diffusion plays probably a key role in the fatigue-corrosion damage mechanism of adhesive bonded specimens. Thus, a moisture diffusion model has been developed as presented in next paragraph.

The element elimination for the adhesive failure phenomenon description can be integrated in the subroutine that describes the evolution of fatigue and corrosion. It can be made by means of the UMAT ABAQUS user subroutine. In order to do so, a first analysis on the average velocity on how the

percentage of adhesive failure increases during the various simultaneous corrosion tests that was made within the project for combination 12.

The information on how the velocity of adhesive failure changes during a fatigue test, would be necessary to make a detailed model, but there would need several fatigue tests interrupted. As first data, the average velocity could give a first information on how would work the integration between adhesive failure evolution and cohesive material degradation.

Figure 117: Average velocities for different loading/corrosion conditions vs loads.

To conclude, the adhesive failure can be described in terms of element elimination. For tests with corrosion and fatigue separately, it seems that no significant degradation of cohesive properties occurs. For combined corrosion and fatigue, there is a strong influence on the cohesive properties that can have a degradation of about 50% in the tested conditions. In perspective, the ABAQUS user subroutine UMAT and USDFLD can be used to integrate the cohesive degradation due to corrosion-fatigue and adhesive failure in terms of actual reduction of the reacting adhesive overlap.

2.2.7.2.7 Model of moisture evolution

A moisture diffusion simulation was carried out on the adhesive material of a lap-shear sample, considering a 2D elements model with two planes of symmetry. One quarter of the overlap has been therefore considered (Figure 118). The equivalence between thermal diffusion and mass diffusion laws has been considered in order to simulate the moisture diffusion.

A “relative humidity” versus saturation concentration boundary condition (values ranging from 0 to 1) has been applied to the external edges of the overlap and a diffusion coefficient of a compatible adhesive has been considered from literature (about 10^{-13} m²/s). In the following Table 29 are reported diffusion coefficients and saturation contents for representative structural adhesive materials [16].

Two cases have been considered, alternated and simultaneous fatigue-corrosion conditions. The simulation takes into account the moisture evolution. The time frame considered was made by 14 weeks. For the alternating corrosion conditions, the 14 weeks were made by 7 stages of 1 week of corrosion load (applied boundary condition equal to 1) and 1 week of absence of moisture load (applied boundary condition equal to 0) at the adhesive edges. For the combined corrosion conditions, the corrosion load has been kept constant through the all simulation duration.

Figure 118: Moisture evolution adhesive domain (one quarter of overlap).

Table 29: Diffusion parameters from literature [16].

Adhesive	Relative humidity (%)	Temperature (°C)	Saturation content (%)	Diffusion coefficient ($10^{-14} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$)
FM73	Immersion	50	3.5	52.2
FM73	95.8	50	2.2	50.2
FM73	79.5	70	1.2	790.0

Figure 119 presents the final moisture distribution, in terms of ratio between relative moisture concentration and saturation content, for the two considered exposure conditions.

History plots have been collected in the centerline (see Figure 119), from the adhesive external edge every 1 mm (Figure 120). Path plots have been obtained as well as simulation results at the centerline at the end of every week (Figure 121).

By means of such a model, it is possible to understand how the moisture diffuses in the adhesive and which could be a possible threshold that leads to permanent adhesive failure in combined corrosion fatigue conditions.

Figure 119: Ratio of relative Moisture concentration respect saturation contents after the two considered exposure conditions.

Figure 120: History plot for the two considered exposure conditions. Left combined – Right alternate.

Figure 121: Path plot for the two considered exposure conditions. Left combined – Right alternate.

Considering the dependency (in absolute values or in relative) reported in literature (Figure 116) in the correlation of tipping traction and energy to failure with the relative humidity, it can be included in the model so that residual strength can be verified with the experimental tests for the most representative cases.

Additionally, it must be noted regarding the combined corrosion-fatigue condition, that the environment moisture penetrates deeper in both the adhesive and at the adhesive/substrate interface (that is not taken into account here), due to the presence of both the environment moisture load and mechanical load that, opening the gaps, could facilitate moisture penetration (other environment factors also play a role in this assumed mechanism). In the simulations of the moisture diffusion, it can be seen a basic situation in which moisture penetrates only from the adhesive edges and without interface interaction nor coupled effect with mechanical load, while for combined fatigue-corrosion can be worse in real condition.

2.2.7.2.8 Conclusions on tasks 7.2

At the end of the efforts made within the AutoFatCor project, some facts must be recognized:

- The cohesive zone approach is an elegant, rich and sophisticated way to describe phenomena and mechanisms related to adhesive joints failure
- Calibration of cohesive zone approach is very time consuming and not fully satisfactory for what concerns back-face strain technique cross-check. Fatigue properties, particularly in corrosive environment, cannot be reproduced by only an evolution of the cohesive properties of the elements with the fatigue loading.
- The scope of work of AutoFatCor project was to provide a procedure to design automotive components taking into account fatigue-corrosion data. At the end of all the work carried out trying to adopt the approach based on cohesive zone element it must be recognized that this approach needs to be extended with an additional part dedicated to the evaluation and progression of adhesive failure as it was experienced during the tests. This consideration, arrived unfortunately only at a late stage of maturity of the AutoFatCor project, resulted from these considerations exemplified on a nominal overlap length of 20 mm:
 - within the project, it has been clear the importance of percentage of adhesive failure in the different combinations of corrosion and fatigue;

- very important percentage of adhesive failures have been observed at the end of all the tests carried out, of even about 90%;
- from the model point of view, trying to calibrate cohesive properties of a 20mm long overlap that must describe the final behavior of an actual 2 mm long overlap leads to a too weak and ill-conditioned system, too far from actual conditions and with very low predicting capabilities

2.2.8 WP8 Life prediction and application guidelines

The main objectives of WP8 were:

- To analyze the experimental data produced during the project to quantify the effects of the interaction between corrosion and fatigue on durability of automotive joints.
- To summarize the most adequate laboratory testing procedures to evaluate the resistance to corrosion-fatigue of welded and adhesive bonded joints.
- To describe computational models which can help in evaluation of the automotive joints and/or in the optimization of their design.
- To summarize the results of the project, by presenting data, methods and tools which can support reliable design of automotive joints exposed to corrosion and fatigue phenomena.

2.2.8.1 Task 8.1: Life prediction

The aim of this part of project was to assess precisely service life of a real assembled component (or representative) based on evaluation of durability and robustness of resistance spot welded joints and adhesive bonded joints.

In conjunction with Tasks 3.4, 5.1 and 7.1, service life of spot-welded joints is predicted. Modified S-N curves, based on influence of corrosive environment (changes in slope and knee points of curves), delivered from Task 5.1, were used as references for interpreting of life of the real spot-welded component. Regarding adhesive bonded joints, S-N curves for shear loading samples, for peel loading samples and for mixed shear/peel loading are available. A model has been developed in task 7.2 to take into account permanent damage due to the corrosive environment. Simulations of 3D components were performed and the methodology of life prediction of adhesive bonded joints was developed.

2.2.8.1.1 Spot-weld specimens

In case of results from corrosive environments, the following approach is restricted to linear analysis only, whereas both linear and non-linear analyses were performed for fatigue in air. Large displacement analysis, especially for large structures like automotive bodies, is usually not performed in industry. In case of assessment of fatigue classes for nonlinear structural analysis, the procedure though is similar.

➤ *Analyses based on maximum principal stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$*

Data in air (grey symbols) and under corrosive conditions (other symbols) are presented in Figure 122. The effect of corrosion was not very much pronounced. Original resistance S-N curve from IIW FAT630/3 also for fatigue in corrosive environments was too conservative in the very high cycle regime and even more unsafe in the low cycle range < 100 000 cycles.

Two resistance S-N curves can be identified: either FAT820/5 or FAT945/7 was below the cloud of data points. Both curves might be usable in case of the materials investigated in the present project.

Since corrosion is a time dependent phenomenon, damage accumulation for variable amplitude loading also considering small cycles below the fatigue limit should be modified with respect to the recommendation of IIW [34]. Using S-N curve without fatigue limit ("Miner elementary") is recommended with respect to fatigue under corrosive environments if stress cycles above the knee-point of the S-N curve have to be considered. In this work, the tests have been stopped after 2 million cycles. Conclusions above this limit cannot be drawn from the results.

Figure 122: Maximum principal notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_1$, small displacement analysis; specimen 1-9 Fatigue in air (grey symbols) and in corrosive environments according to tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3.

➤ Analyses based on von Mises equivalent stress range $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$

Data in air (grey symbols) and under corrosive conditions (other symbols) are presented in Figure 123. Again, the effect of corrosion was not very much pronounced. Original resistance S-N curve from IIW FAT560/3 also for fatigue in corrosive environments was too conservative in the very high cycle regime and even more unsafe in the low cycle range < 100 000 cycles. Two resistance S-N curves can be identified: either FAT730/5 or FAT840/7 was below the cloud of data points. Both curves might be usable in case of the materials investigated in this project.

Figure 123: Von Mises notch stress range $\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$, small displacement analysis; specimen 1-9 Fatigue in air (grey symbols) and in corrosive environments according to tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3.

Analysis for notch stresses using von Mises equivalent stress yielded analogous results compared to the findings from maximum principal stress as can be seen in the following diagrams.

- *Conclusions for fatigue in air and in corrosive environment of spot-welded steel based components*

Fitting to the concept of the IIW guideline [34], the following parameters in Table 30 and Table 31 are recommended as characteristic values (FAT-class) and slopes for spot-welded joints made of steel under fatigue in air and in corrosive environments.

Table 30: Recommended parameters for resistance S-N curves for spot-welded steel in air

R [mm]	0,05	0,05	
Hypotheses	$\Delta\sigma_1$ [MPa]	$\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$ [MPa]	m_1
Linear geometric	945	840	5.0
Nonlinear geometric	820	730	5.0

Table 31: Recommended parameters for resistance S-N curves for spot-welded steel in corrosive environments

R [mm]	0,05	0,05	
Hypotheses	$\Delta\sigma_1$ [MPa]	$\Delta\sigma_{eqv}$ [MPa]	m_1
Linear geometric	820 (945)	730 (840)	5.0 (7.0)

FAT-classes as recommended by IIW showed significant conservatism in high cycle range and less conservatism in low cycle range with respect to spot welded steel structures even for conditions under corrosive environments.

Taking the above S-N curves as characteristic values for a failure probability of 2.5%, the original IIW-data can be significantly improved for better and safer design of spot-welded structures in corrosive conditions as well.

A higher slope exponent than 3 has been seen in a number of other publications [41–43] involving welded thin sheet (spot welded or laser welded). Thus, an exponent of 5, or even 7, fits well with these results. In existing recommendations, a unique slope exponent is preferable to multiple linear curves. A cut-off limit is sometimes proposed to fit experimental data. However, it cannot be derived from the results of this project, because of the lack of data at low stress ranges. Thus, a fatigue limit for a required failure probability cannot be obtained. Moreover, in corrosive environment, the existence of fatigue endurance is questionable.

2.2.8.1.2 Adhesive specimens

After the improvements on the model performed in task 7.2, i.e. accuracy derived considering the adhesive failure on the basis of the actual reacting overlap length (simulated by means of element elimination), the fatigue model has been reapplied and a further activity of calibration has been carried out. In particular, considering the combined corrosion fatigue experimental results and the calibrated degraded cohesive properties, it has been possible to help the calibration of α , β and ϵ_{th} having a first guess of arrival point of degraded cohesive material properties.

In other words, the FEM model with the user-subroutine for fatigue damage accumulation starts with the cohesive properties calibrated in initial conditions. The arrival point after damage accumulation should be close to those calibrated in degraded conditions. By means of this new data, it has been possible to define an easy way for the calibration of, at least, first guess of reliable α , β and ϵ_{th} .

The model that describes fatigue-corrosion evolution has been tested with the following data in Table 32 that were related to one of the experimental tests carried out on simultaneous fatigue corrosion (combination 12, Lap-shear joint, R=0.1, combined fatigue-corrosion, Load 3.5kN, Duration 920000 cycles):

Table 32: Parameters used for model for fatigue corrosion – Target for experimental test duration.

% Adh. Failure	70
Fmax (kN)	3,5
Alfa	62,356
Beta	12,97
Epsth	0,086
Experimental Test duration	920000

The model starts with an actual reacting overlap length of 70% and is made by two steps. A first step of ramped load application up to Fmax in which the damage accumulation is inhibited, and a second step during which the external load is kept constant, where the passing time means cycles and the damage accumulation routine takes into account the degradation of cohesive properties due to cycles and corrosion.

The resulting life was about 624750 cycles. Figure 125 presents the damage variable evolution related to one integration point of the first cohesive element of the adhesive overlap. Damage initiation variable governs energy accumulation up to Tripping Traction, while Damage evolution from Tripping Traction up to failure (Figure 124).

Damage evolution was limited to 0.4 on the basis of cohesive properties tuning (max degradation=0.4). Damage parameter "D" was calculated by the user-subroutine on the basis of equations of the fatigue degradation model presented in Figure 96 and led to a degradation of cohesive properties up to failure.

The results would need further refinement, but they demonstrate that the model can take into account adhesive failure, cohesive failure and fatigue corrosion effects.

Figure 124: Traction separation response for cohesive elements.

Figure 125: Resulting damage variable evolution for corrosion fatigue model application test.

In order to have a predicting capability, the model should include the criterion for element elimination or cohesive properties reset considering the moisture penetration results from the moisture evolution model and/or the average velocity of adhesive failure evolution observed after tests (Figure 117). For the achievement of this goal, from a technical point of view, if the strategy would be "cohesive properties reset" instead of "element elimination", the up to now developed user-subroutine could integrate the logic of the strategy, instead having to implement, for element elimination, UMAT user-subroutine.

Extension of the model to a 3D model is necessary for future industrial application. In order to evaluate the sensitivity to the mesh density and model dimension for combination 12 and 13, a 3D model has been developed and compared to the results obtained with the 2D model. The model has the adhesive material that is described with cohesive elements with the initial tuned properties. The mesh size of the 3D model has for the adhesive 0.3x0.3x0.3mm. Also, the adhesive has the same mesh size for the region of the overlap and next to the overlap. Then, towards the clamps, the mesh size increases in the clamps direction. Results are reported in Figure 126 to Figure 129.

The results in terms of peak force and plateau were rather good. The mesh of the 3D model was still too fine to be adopted in a complex structure. In addition, comparisons with shell elements for the adherents should be conducted to obtain an industrial tool.

Figure 126: Combination 12 – Force-displacement comparison between 3D and 2D models.

Figure 127: Combination 12 – progressive failure of the adhesive – Half model.

Figure 128: Combination 13 – Force-displacement comparison between 3D and 2D models.

Figure 129: Combination 13 – progressive failure of the adhesive – Half model.

2.2.8.2 Task 8.2: Application guidelines

This task aimed at describing how it can be possible to take advantage of the results of the project in the scientific and industrial practices.

2.2.8.2.1 State of the art to assess fatigue life of automotive spot welded structures

➤ Demand for improved methods

There is a great demand for improving the quality of fatigue prognoses in automotive industry as explicitly stated in [44]. The huge amount of research and literature covering this topic underline this statement impressively.

In the past and up to now, a structural stress approach is mainly used to assess the fatigue behavior of large scale spot welded structures like car bodies. Most of the literature found and most of the presentations given by the automotive industry reflect this situation. The so-called radial-stress method is one the most used methods [45,46].

But, there is also still a need for improvement using more refined simulation models [44]. Those models require refined models and concept conforming fatigue data. Many references [46–50] demonstrate the need and opportunities for such methods like the notch-stress method.

Reduction of carbon dioxide emissions requires lightweight design. Assessment of reliable structures requires reliable methods. Optimization with respect to minimizing weight might lead to dimension “right at the edge” of allowable stresses. To ensure availability and safety of future cars, improved methods to assess fatigue behavior are mandatory.

Reliably product development also requires redundant and cross-checking methods. This hold true especially for situations where the load capacity of a joint is at its end. Fast methods for full structures, like the radial stress method, need to be enriched by alternative and more detailed methods.

Klaus F. Stracke, former head of development from FORD Europe has stated in 2006 [51]:

- *Reduction of development cycles requires an approach "Road to Lab to Math"*
- *Durability is a key factor besides active and passive safety*
- *In addition to fluctuating loads environmental conditions like temperature, moisture, sun and others need to be incorporated in the methods applied*
- *"Road to Lab to Math" can only be achieved by innovative simulation methods and efficient software tools*
- *Fatigue simulation in early design stages is done by numerical simulation as supporting pillar*
- *Test hardware must and will be reduced in the future*

➤ *Lack of knowledge and data consideration corrosive environments on fatigue*

For corrosion no public available simulation methods are known to the authors. This topic is one of the main objectives of AutoFatCor. Knowledge and data to fill this is necessary to assess the criticality of corrosive environments.

There is only little information on fatigue on spot welds with corrosive environments. The methods supported by the IIW and also the publications of the German research in automotive industry do not cover this topic at all.

Surface coating of sheet metal, electrocoating, flange sealing, additional adhesive joining and conservation of cavities should avoid any corrosion in the weld flanges. The amount of means demonstrate the criticality of corrosion and large need to avoid this in any circumstances. Knowledge about the fatigue behavior of corroded structures thus brings the opportunity to think about the corrosion protection system and thus a basis for reducing production effort and cost.

2.2.8.2.2 *Supporting software for notch stress approach*

Commercial software codes available for fatigue analysis on stress or strain results from finite-element-analysis are for example:

- *feSafe™ from Dassault Systems*
- *FEMFAT® from Engineering Center Steyr GmbH & Co KG*
- *nCode™ from HBM GmbH*
- *Virtual.Lab™ from Siemens Industry Software GmbH & Co. KG*

These software products are applied in automotive industry for years and support fatigue relevant algorithms like

- *stress based concepts*
- *strain based concepts*
- *fracture mechanical approaches*
- *cycle counting*
- *multiaxial fatigue*

All programs support spot weld analysis using nominal and/or structural stress approaches. Most public presentations and marketing material of these software tools are based on those approaches. Analysis of full body structures involving more than 5000 spot weld connections and using shell elements for the sheet metal are state of the art in application of those tools (see i.e. [52]).

The notch stress approach follows the usual stress based concepts for any notched structure but using specific SN-curves. For that reason, transfer of the outcomes of the AutoFatCor projects for fatigue simulation of spot welded structures is straight forward and seamlessly embeds in existing procedures.

Future enhancements of the software codes might introduce submodel simulation of local single spot weld connections using the notch stress approach. The notch stress approach using submodels is already implemented for seam weld analysis in some of the codes available. Submodeling though is not mandatory to implement the notch stress approach for spot welds.

An appealing alternative use of the notch stress concept for spot welds is a hierarchical approach. This could be done to support two objectives:

- a) *Improving the quality of a large scale model locally: using structural stress approaches for the analysis of the full structure, critical spot welds can be identified. To get a second analysis result using a higher level method, the notch stress approach is applied for one or more critical spot welds. Using this method a redundant and diverse method is applied to give more exact information on the fatigue behavior. This approach improves the quality of the fatigue estimation.*
- b) *Deriving nominal or structural stress models by applying the notch stress concept on a single or a small group of spot weld connections. With the local concept, resistance SN-curves for any of the other concepts can be derived.*

2.2.8.2.3 Transfer of simulation concept for single spot welds to large structures

For pure spot weld joining, it was possible to derive resistance SN-curves with respect to performance in air and corrosive environments in simultaneous and alternate conditions of fatigue cycling and exposure to corrosive environments. Thus, a bridge between research and accepted simulation methods in industry could be built using the outcomes of the AutoFatCor project.

An empirical approach which is state of the art in industry was supported to establish a simulation method for fatigue of spot welds made for steel joints under exposure in air and corrosive environments. The application of the findings thus is straight forward and does not require additional software, data or creation of simulation models requiring "unusual" features.

With this in mind, the methods developed can be applied right away in industry.

2.2.8.2.4 Development of model for adhesive bonding

Concerning adhesive joining, it was highlighted that environmental conditions and increase of adhesive failure are of primary importance, with a large influence of moisture diffusion. Thus, coupling CZM approach and subroutine with element elimination could reproduce quite accurately the fatigue damage mechanism of adhesive bonded component and could provide interesting scientific contributions.

Finally, the framework presented in Figure 130 can be consolidated for the AutoFatCor project for the adhesive joints fatigue-corrosion model. In order to fully complete the implementation of the model, several experimental data should be still found for instance:

- Gravimetric evaluation of moisture contents in the adhesive after corrosion tests, in order to find the suitable threshold to be used with the moisture evolution model and use it for adhesive failure evolution
- Interrupted fatigue tests in order to obtain more data for the velocity of adhesive failure evolution.

The model up to now developed is an "uncoupled" version of the model described in the synoptic frame, since it describes the adhesive failure by means of an initial reduction of actual reacting overlap. But, it is a demonstration of what, in perspective, could be the model with its potentialities and predictive capabilities.

Figure 130: Framework of the model developed for adhesive joining in AutoFatCor project.

3 Conclusions

Cold rolled steels, high strength steels and press hardened steels were selected and supplied by Steel suppliers to produce conventional spot welded, adhesive bonded and spot-weld-bonded samples in both lap shear and T-peel designs.

The conclusions of the work performed within this project are listed hereafter:

- Metallographic inspections of the base materials revealed normal microstructure and expected metallic coating composition and thickness.
- Characterization of the spot-welds revealed good quality of the welding process with typical hardness evolutions.
- Mechanical testing under static loading showed tensile strengths which are obviously configuration and material dependent. All measured values and failure modes for spot welded specimens corresponded with earlier studies on unalloyed and high strength steels. For adhesive specimens, the maximum tensile load was systematically higher than for spot welded specimens. However, the energy absorbed until failure of the assemblies was of the same order of magnitude. As expected, TP specimens, whatever the joining techniques, showed lower mechanical properties than LS ones.
- Typical S/N curves were obtained from fatigue tests in air. Adhesive bonding led to higher fatigue life than spot welding. Highest slope, linked to lowest notch sensitivity, was also obtained for adhesive specimens. These curves were used to determine pre-fatigue load levels for WP 4 and used as references to evaluate the influence of corrosion on the fatigue resistance.
- Exposure to 12 weeks of accelerated corrosion test without any fatigue solicitations (N-VDA and some variants for studying key parameters) did not result in significant loss of mechanical properties of spot welded specimens. For adhesive bonded specimens, the sensitivity in NVDA conditions was in an intermediate range compared to other climatic conditions, without very large strength loss as it was observed in SC5-SF7 or T45 conditions. The decrease in tensile properties was imputable to a loss of adhesion at the interface adhesive/coating by a delamination process in the presence of water, oxygen and chlorides. The degradation was enhanced by increasing salt frequency and salt concentration. Raising temperature to 45°C had also a deleterious impact on adhesive samples, increasing strength loss and adhesive failure.
- Outdoor exposures were too short to induce large corrosion effects on the specimens. However, some adhesive bonded specimens showed important strength loss after tensile testing of samples exposed at the marine station, but not for specimens exposed under the vehicle. A cumulative effect of fatigue preloading and exposure to corrosive environments could be observed on the loss of mechanical properties of adhesive bonded assemblies. Relative humidity plays a key role in the degradation of the properties of these assemblies.
- The behavior of all spot welded specimens during simultaneous fatigue-corrosion was quite similar: compared to tests in air, the fatigue life was decreased at high applied loads and increased at lower loads. The variation of fatigue in corrosive environment can be explained either by corrosion products formation around the spot-weld, which changes and limits the stress and strain amplitudes at low applied load, or/and by blunting of the crack tip.
- Simultaneous fatigue loading and exposure to corrosion test (N-VDA) of adhesive bonded assemblies induced early failures compared to fatigue tests performed in air. This reduction of fatigue life was correlated with a large increase of the adhesive failure. Thus, the interface coating/adhesive is affected by the corrosive environment. The diffusion of moisture in the overlap is probably a critical parameter.
- Alternated fatigue-corrosion was much less aggressive on the spot welded and adhesive bonded specimens than simultaneous fatigue-corrosion. However, it is difficult to assess which method is more representative of the automotive car body. For adhesive specimens, the number of NVDA cycles seems to be the critical parameter, probably linked to embrittlement interface coating/adhesive by moisture/salts diffusion.
- Modeling spot weld structure is possible using the notch stress approach. Good agreement with experimental data and easy transfer in design applications makes this method suitable for the automotive industry. New FAT-classes were obtained to take into account fatigue-corrosion effects.
- The cohesive zone model for adhesive specimens remained a too complex method for design application, but can be quite accurate with additional element elimination subroutine. This new approach was validated for one combination tested in the project. More work would be necessary to obtain a tool for automotive fatigue design.

In perspective of this work, some points could be of interest for future investigations:

- Further development of coupled model with the cohesive zone approach and element elimination subroutine.

- Better understanding of the behavior of the adhesive joint, meaning evolution of the moisture and its impact mechanical properties and other downgrading factors from the corrosive environment.
- Construction of representative corrosion/mechanical loading (frequency constant or not, shape of cycles, distance equivalency relatively to the corrosion condition, variability of load –constant/variable amplitude- ...)

4 Exploitation and impact of the research results

Results from the AutoFatCor project can be useful data for the automotive industry. Indeed, a new method was obtained for the fatigue-corrosion of spot welded components and raw data was produced for adhesive bonded specimens, with better understanding of the fatigue-corrosion damage mechanism. Several papers were submitted for publication to diffuse the results:

- *Thierry D., Vucko F., Luckeneder G., Weber B., Dosdat L., Bschorr T., Rother K., Fatigue testing for spot welded joints in air and under corrosive environment, part I: materials, specimen and test results in air, **Welding in the World**, 2016.*
- *Thierry D., Vucko F., Luckeneder G., Weber B., Dosdat L., Bschorr T., Rother K., Fatigue testing for spot welded joints in air and under corrosive environment, part II: fatigue under alternating and combined corrosion and fatigue load, **Welding in the World**, 2016.*
- *Vucko F., LeBozec N., Thierry D., Weber B., Dosdat L., Luckeneder G., Bschorr T., Rother K., Sciaboni C., Szczepanski J., Combined corrosion and fatigue performance of joined materials for automotive applications, **Materials and Corrosion**, 2016.*

Results were presented, or planned to be, during conferences:

- **Eurocorr 2015 in Linz, Austria:** Simultaneous and alternated fatigue-corrosion performance of joined materials for automotive applications
- **6th International Seminar In The Field Of Automotive Corrosion (May 2016) in Stockholm, Sweden:** Corrosion fatigue properties of joined materials for the automotive industry
- **"Affidabilità e tecnologie" 2014 in Turin, Italy:** Characterization of the properties of adhesive materials for automotive joints by reverse calibration based on simple T-Peel and Lap-Shear tests for Cohesive Approach Zone Model

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7 List of acronyms and abbreviations

Adh	Adhesive bonding
AHSS	Advanced high-strength steel
Conc.	Concentration
Cond.	Conductivity
CZM	Cohesive Zone Model
FAT-class	Fatigue class
FE	Finite Element
FEM	Finite Element Modeling
Fmax	Maximum load
Freq.	Frequency of the salt spray phases
HSS	High-strength steel
IIW	International Institute of Welding
k	Slope of the Wöhler curve
LS	Lap-shear
N	Number of load cycles
NVDA	(Verband Der Automobilindustrie) for New VDA 233-102
PHS	Press-hardened steel
RH	Relative humidity
S-N curve	stress amplitude versus number of cycles to failure
RSW	Resistance spot-welding
T	Task
Temp	Temperature
ToW	Time of wetness (RH>80%, Temp > 0°C)
TP	T-peel
WP	Work Package
YS	Yield strength

8 References

- [1] L. Dosdat, J. Petitjean, T. Vietoris, O. Clauzeau, Corrosion resistance of different metallic coatings on press-hardened steels for Automotive, in: SCT, Salzburg, Austria, 2011.
- [2] EN ISO 1183-1, Plastics - Methods for determining the density of non-cellular plastics - Part 1: Immersion method, liquid pycnometer method and titration method, 2004.
- [3] ISO 527-2, Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 2: Test conditions for moulding and extrusion plastics., 2012.
- [4] G. Weber, H. Thommes, H. Gaul, O. Hahn, M. Rethmeier, Mechanical properties of welded joints of advanced high strength steels, *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* 25 (2011) 2369–2389.
- [5] DVS bulletin 1935-1, Resistance spot welding of sheet metal of low alloyed steels – cold rolled high strength (in German), 2004.
- [6] DVS bulletin 2935-2, Resistance spot welding of sheet metal of low alloyed steels – cold rolled multiphase steels (AHSS) (in German), 2007.
- [7] H. Khoramishad, A.D. Crocombe, K.B. Katnam, I.A. Ashcroft, Predicting fatigue damage in adhesively bonded joints using a cohesive zone model, *Int. J. Fatigue.* 32 (2010) 1146–1158.
- [8] B. Rendahl, N. LeBozec, Corrosion resistance of automotive materials: from laboratory to field exposures, in: EUROCORR, Stockholm, 2011.
- [9] T. Prosek, D. Thierry, C. Taxén, J. Maixner, Effect of cations on corrosion of zinc and carbon steel covered with chloride deposits under atmospheric conditions, *Corros. Sci.* 49 (2007) 2676–2693. doi:10.1016/j.corsci.2006.11.004.
- [10] F. Rossillon, A. Galtier, Effect of welding cycle on the fatigue behaviour of resistance spot welded dual phase steels, *Weld. World.* 52 (2008) 30–41.
- [11] C. Lewis, Fatigue performance of fusion welded automotive high strength steels, *Weld. Met. Fabr.* 64 (1996) 275–278.
- [12] J. Bonnen, H. Agrawal, M. Amaya, R. Iyengar, Fatigue of Advanced High Strength Steel Spot-Welds, in: SAE Tech. Pap. 2006-01-0978, 2006.
- [13] DVS Merkblatt 2935-2, Resistance spot welding of sheet metal of low alloyed steels – cold rolled multiphase steels (AHSS), 2007.
- [14] N. LeBozec, N. Blandin, D. Thierry, Accelerated corrosion tests in the automotive industry: a comparison of the performance towards cosmetic corrosion, *Mater. Corros.* 39 (2008) 889–894.
- [15] N. LeBozec, D. Thierry, Influence of climatic factors in cyclic accelerated corrosion test: towards the development of a reliable and repeatable accelerated corrosion test for the automotive industry, *Mater. Corros.* 61 (2010) 845–851.
- [16] C.D.M. Liljedahl, A.D. Crocombe, M.A. Wahab, I.A. Ashcroft, Modelling the environmental degradation of adhesively bonded aluminium and composite joints using a CZM approach, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* 27 (2007) 505–518. doi:10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2006.09.015.
- [17] X. He, A review of finite element analysis of adhesively bonded joints, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* 31 (2011) 248–264. doi:10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2011.01.006.
- [18] A. Hobbacher, Recommendations for fatigue design of welded joints and components - IIW document XIII-2151r1-07 / XV-1254r1-07, International Institute of Welding IIW, 2007.
- [19] A. Hobbacher, Database for the Effective Notch Stress Method at Steel. IIW Joint Working Group Doc. JWG-XIII-XV-197-08, International Institute of Welding IIW, 2008.
- [20] D. Radaj, C.M. Sonsino, W. Fricke, Fatigue assessment of welded joints by local approaches, 2nd editio, Woodhead Publishing Ltd., 2006.
- [21] R. Olivier, V. Köttgen, T. Seeger, Schweißverbindungen I, FKM-Forschungsheft 143, Frankfurt/M, Forschungskuratorium Maschinenbau, 1989.
- [22] V. Köttgen, R. Olivier, T. Seeger, Schwingfestigkeitsanalyse für Schweißverbindungen auf der Grundlage örtlicher Beanspruchungen. Expert `91 – Berechnung, Gestaltung und Fertigung von Schweißkonstruktionen im Zeitalter der Expertensysteme. DVS-Bericht 133, Ed. D. Radaj, 75-84, Düsseldorf, , 1991.
- [23] R. Olivier, V. Köttgen, T. Seeger, Schweißverbindungen II, Schwingfestigkeitsnachweise FKM-Forschungsheft 180, Frankfurt/M, Forschungskuratorium Maschinenbau, 1994.

- [24] T. Seeger, H. Amstutz, Betriebsfestigkeitsnachweise für Schweißverbindungen auf der Grundlage örtlicher Konzepte. In: Fortschritte bei der Konstruktion und Berechnung geschweißter Bauteile. DVS-Berichte Band 187, DVS-Verlag, Düsseldorf, 190-208, 1997.
- [25] D.-B.B. 256, Festigkeit geschweißter Bauteile. DVS Media GmbH, Düsseldorf, 2009.
- [26] W. Fricke, Round-Robin Study on Stress Analysis for the Effective Notch Stress Approach. IIW-Doc.:XIII-2129-06/XV-1223-06, International Institute of Welding, 2006.
- [27] C.M. Sonsino, A consideration of allowable equivalent stresses for fatigue design of welded joints according to the notch stress concept with reference radii $r_{ref} = 1.00$ and $0,05\text{mm.}$, Weld. World. 53 (2009) 64–75.
- [28] Stoerzel, Baumgartner, Bruder, Hanselka: Festigkeitskonzepte für schwingbelastete geschweißte Bauteile. MT 53, 2011.
- [29] FAT-Bericht 179, Dünnblechschweißen, n.d.
- [30] C.M. Sonsino, Notch stress concepts for the fatigue assessment of welded joints, Int. J. Fatigue. 34 (2012) 2–16.
- [31] DVS-Berichte Band 256, Festigkeit geschweißter Bauteile. Anwendbarkeit lokaler Nachweiskonzepte bei Schwingbeanspruchung, 2009.
- [32] K. Rother, Finite-Element-Model, Notch Stress Analysis – Lap Shear Specimen. Doc.No.: RotherCONSULT SLV14-02-2.TB0. Issued 9/27/2014, 2014.
- [33] K. Rother, Finite-Element-Model, Notch Stress Analysis – T-Peel Specimen. Doc.No.: RotherCONSULT SLV14-02-5.TB0. Issued 1/18/2015, 2015.
- [34] A. Hobbacher, Recommendations for fatigue design of welded joints and components. IIW document IIW-xxx-13 ex XIII-2460-13/XV-1440-13. International Institute of Welding IIW, 2014.
- [35] A. Hillerborg, M. Modeer, P.E. Petersson, Analysis of crack formation and crack growth in concrete by means of fracture mechanics and finite elements, Cem. Concr. Res. 6 (1976) 773–781.
- [36] M.L. Benzeggagh, M. Kenane, Measurement of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with mixedmode bending apparatus, Compos. Sci. Technol. 56 (1996) 439–449.
- [37] H. Khoramishad, A.D. Crocombe, K.B. Katnam, I.A. Ashcroft, Fatigue damage modelling of adhesively bonded joints under variable amplitude loading using a cohesive zone model, Eng. Fract. Mech. 78 (2011) 3212–3225.
- [38] V. Shenoy, I.A. Ashcroft, G.W. Critchlow, A.D. Crocombe, Fracture mechanics and damage mechanics based fatigue lifetime prediction of adhesively bonded joints subjected to variable amplitude fatigue, Eng. Fract. Mech. 77 (2010) 1073–1090.
- [39] ABAQUS, Analysis Users' Manual – 32.5.6 Interpretation of material properties, n.d.
- [40] T. Iwamoto, T. Nagai, T. Sawa, Experimental and computational investigations on strain rate sensitivity and deformation behavior of bulk materials made of epoxy resin structural adhesive, Int J Solids Struct. 47 (2010) 175–185.
- [41] C. Sonsino, T. Bruder, J. Baumgartner, SN-curves for welded thin joints – suggested slopes and FAT-values for applying the notch stress concept, IIW doc. XIII-2280-09, n.d.
- [42] B. Kranz, C.M. Sonsino, Verification of the notch stress concept for the reference radii of $r_{ref} = 1.00$ and 0.05 mm , Document IIW-XIII-2274–09/XV-1312-09, 2009.
- [43] T. Wang, D. Wang, L. Huo, Y. Zhang, Discussion on fatigue design of welded joints enhanced by ultrasonic peening treatment (UPT), Int. J. Fatigue. 31 (2009) 644–650. doi:10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2008.03.030.
- [44] Lohse, Bruder, Lebensdauerberechnung von Schweißpunkten mit Hilfe von Kerbfinelementen. DVM Workshop Numerische Simulation, 2014.
- [45] Lee, Pan, Hathaway, Barkey, Fatigue testing and analysis, Elsevier Butterworth Heinemann, 2005.
- [46] R. Chmielewski, F. de Bruyne, P. Heuler, M. Waltz, Numerical assessment of welded body structures by a submodelling technique, Fügen und Betriebsfestigkeit, DVM Report 132, Darmstadt, Germany., 2005.
- [47] W. Fricke, IIW Recommendations for the Fatigue Assessment by Notch Stress Analysis for Welded Structures. IIW-Doc. XIII-2240r2-08/XV-1289r2-08, 2010.

- [48] DVM-Bericht 132, Fügen und Betriebsfestigkeit. 32. Tagung des DVM-Arbeitskreises Betriebsfestigkeit. DVM e.V. Berlin, 2005.
- [49] Stoerzel, Baumgartner, Bruder, Hanselka, Festigkeitskonzepte für schwingbelastete geschweißte Bauteile. MT 53, 2011.
- [50] W. Fricke, Guideline for the Fatigue Assessment by Notch Stress Analysis for Welded Structures. IIW-Doc.:XIII-2240-08/XV-1289-08, 2008.
- [51] Stracke, Automobiltechnik 2015 – Ein Ausblick. 32. Tagung des DVM-Arbeitskreises Betriebsfestigkeit. DVM e.V. Berlin, DVM-Bericht 132, 2005.
- [52] Dannbauer, Gaier, Hofwimmer, Fatigue Analysis of Welding Seams and Spot Joints in Automotive Structures. SAE paper 2005-01-1323, 2004.

Appendix

8.1 Appendix 1: Spot weld characteristics

Table 33: Minimum and measured nugget diameter, welding range and type of failure of configurations 1 to 9 (RSW), 15 and 16 (Adhesive+RSW).

Config.	Combinations	Minimum nugget diameter $4\sqrt{t}$ (mm)	Measured nugget dia. in cross section (mm)	Lower welding current (kA)	Upper welding current ⁽¹⁾ (kA)	Welding range (kA)	Failure type ⁽²⁾ lower current	Failure type ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾ upper current
1	1a+1a	3.35	5.1	4.5	7.5	3	PF	PF
2	1a+1d	3.46	5.6	5.5	8.5	3	PF	PF
3	1d+1d	3.46	5.6	6.8	8.8	2	PF	PF
4	1b+1b	3.46	4.9	6.5	8.2	1.7	PF	PF
5	1c+1c	3.51	4.8	6.1	8.1	2	PF	PF
6&7	2+2	4.31	5.2 & 5.0	Not defined	7.6	Not defined	Not defined	PF
8	4a+4a	4.90	4.7	Not defined	5.8	Not defined	Not defined	PIF
9	4b+4b	4.90	6.4	5.2	6.8	1.6	PIF	PIF
15&16	2+2	4.31	6.3	Not defined	Not defined	Not defined	Not defined	PF

⁽¹⁾ When the welding range has not been defined, the values correspond to the used welding current

⁽²⁾ PF: Plug Failure PIF: Plug Interfacial Failure IF: Interfacial Failure

8.2 Appendix 2: Cosmetic corrosion results (T5.2)

Cosmetic corrosion and mechanical results from task 5.2 are shown in this section.

Figure 131: cosmetic corrosion results – creepage from vertical edges.

Figure 132: cosmetic corrosion results – creepage from overlap.

Figure 133: perforating corrosion results – extent of red rust in overlaps after exposure to corrosion.

Figure 134: perforating corrosion results – maximal pitting in overlaps after exposure to corrosion.

Figure 135: tensile strength results – peak load before and after exposure to corrosion.

Figure 1.36: tensile strength results – strength loss vs. reference in air.

8.3 Appendix 3: Environmental data - vehicle and field exposure

Figure 137: Evolution of the average, maximum and minimum temperatures per day on the vehicle driving in Munich area.

Figure 138: Evolution of the average, maximum and minimum relative humidity per day on the vehicle driving in Munich area.

Table 34: Average corrosivity measured on steel and zinc exposed on the vehicle driving in Munich area

Exposure site	Mass loss	Steel	Zinc
On-vehicle (600 days)	g/m ²	800	97
	µm	102	13.6

Table 35: Physical data of marine site of Brest.

Name of the site	Latitude	Longitude
Sainte Anne du Portzic – Brest (France 29)	48°21'30.9" North	4°33'03.3" West
Characteristics		
Distance to the seashore	From 2 to 5 m	
Altitude	From 2 to 3 m upon the tide	
Dominating winds	South-West	
Exposure racks for AutoFatCor	45° South	

Table 36: Climatic and corrosivity data of Brest field site for 2013.

Period	Temp	Rel. Hum.	ToW	Sun Irradiation (global)		Precipitation
	(°C)	(%)	(h)	(h)	(MJ/m ²)	(mm)
Jan	7,7	87	581	40	94	128
Feb	6,1	79	336	94	170	58
March	7,1	79	374	97	285	79
April	9,2	79	382	159	450	78
May	11,2	78	380	191	579	61
June	14,2	84	492	135	529	71
July	18,7	80	403	276	706	28
Aug.	17,7	80	416	203	552	28
Sept	16,7	83	487	153	366	57
Oct	14,9	86	549	109	227	147
Nov	10	81	375	55	104	116
Dec	8,7	84	509	74	88	168
Mean	11,9	82	/	/	/	/
Sum	/	/	5284	1586	4151	1019

Period	Chlorides (mg/m ² , day)	Precipitation		
	Ste Anne	pH	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	Cond. (mS/m)
Jan	3332	5,2	50,3	9,3
Feb	73	5,2	34,8	7,9
March	337	5,3	22,2	5,6
April	341	5,2	30,5	8,1
May	52	5,3	22,8	6,4
June	144	5,3	32,9	9,2
July	69	5,5	229,2	56,3
Aug.	20	5,8	106,2	24,3
Sept	26	5,4	14,5	4,8
Oct	7666	5,5	59,3	14,0
Nov	247	5,1	13,1	4,2
Dec	6738	N.A	168,1	40,8
Mean	1 587	5,3	65,3	15,9

Corrosivity data

Brest Ste Anne 45°S		Steel	Zinc	Copper	Aluminium
Metal loss after 1 year of exposure	g/m ² /y	682 ± 14	11 ± 0.5	16.6 ± 0.4	0.6 ± 0.1
	µm/y	87 ± 2	1.5 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
Corrosivity category (ISO9223)		C5	C3	C4-	C3

Table 37: Climatic and corrosivity data of Brest field site for 2014.

Period	Temp	Rel. Hum.	ToW	Sun Irradiation (global)		Precipitations
	(°C)	(%)	(h)	(h)	(MJ/m ²)	(mm)
Jan	8,6	86	572	59	98	235
Feb	8,3	81	351	79	161	232
March	9,2	84	506	116	304	70
April	11,3	80	419	175	458	55
May	12,9	79	367	196	594	111
June	16,5	75	323	257	715	33
July	18,3	81	442	194	591	39
Aug.	16,4	82	461	154	488	109
Sept	18,2	81	429	214	447	3
Oct	15,1	84	515	118	240	89
Nov	11,2	87	581	78	126	191
Dec	8,7	83	468	45	75	70
Mean	12,9	82	/	/	/	/
Sum	/	/	5434	1684	4297	1237

Period	Chloride (mg/m ² , day)		Precipitations (Ste Anne)		
	Ste Anne	Base Navale	pH	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	Cond. (mS/m)
Jan	3098	15303	5,8	47,0	7,4
Feb	25367	22981	6,0	293,2	45,0
March	601	796	5,8	94,8	10,6
April	5529	6856	6,0	142,0	16,5
May	271	958	5,9	62,2	4,8
June	93	202	5,5	43,2	5,8
July	24	74	6,0	8,6	4,5
Aug.	96	788	5,9	14,2	4,6
Sept	15	20	6,0	-	-
Oct	605	1763	5,8	34,0	14,2
Nov	1358	2525	6,0	33,0	10,1
Dec	1517	561	5,8	26,3	10,7
Mean	3 214	4 402	5,9	72,6	16,0

Exposure Site	Angle	Metal loss	Steel	Zinc	Copper	Aluminium
Brest Ste Anne	45°S	g/m ² , an	1137 ± 62	11.0 ± 1.3	20.7 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0
		µm/an	145 ± 8	1.5 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.0	-
	90°N	g/m ² , an	1172 ± 34*	8.3 ± 0.7	44.3 ± 2.7	1.4 ± 0.1
		µm/an	149 ± 4	1.2 ± 0.0	5.0 ± 0.3	-

8.4 Appendix 4: Simultaneous Fatigue-corrosion results (task 6.2)

Figure 139: Results of simultaneous fatigue-corrosion for spot weld combinations 1 to 5.

Figure 140: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 6.

Figure 141: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 7.

Figure 142: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 8.

Figure 143: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 9.

Figure 144: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 10.

Figure 145: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 11.

Figure 146: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 12.

Figure 147: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 13.

Figure 148: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 14.

Figure 149: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 15.

Figure 150: Fatigue life in NVDA condition for configuration 16.

8.5 Appendix 5: Alternated Fatigue-corrosion results (task 5.3)

8.5.1 Method 1 vs. air

Figure 151: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 10.

Figure 152: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 12.

Figure 153: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 14 (in blue the wrong reference curve in air).

Figure 154: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 7 (arrows indicate specimens that did not fail during alternated-corrosion tests).

Figure 155: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 11.

Figure 156: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 13 (in blue the wrong reference curve in air).

Figure 157: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 1 for configuration 16.

8.5.2 Method 2 vs. Method 1

Figure 158: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 10.

Figure 159: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 12.

Figure 160: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 14.

Figure 161: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 7.

Figure 162: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 11.

Figure 163: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 13.

Figure 164: Alternated fatigue-corrosion method 2 for configuration 16.

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The main aim of the project was to evaluate the influence of fatigue and corrosion on the resistance of joined coated steel based materials. The industrial aim was to obtain a useful method to predict fatigue life of automotive components under atmospheric weathering conditions.

Steel panels were assembled by conventional resistance spot welding, adhesive bonding and combination of the two processes in both lap-shear and T-peel designs. Panels were exposed on a vehicle, at a field station and in various accelerated corrosion tests.

Fatigue-corrosion tests were performed following two procedures, alternated and simultaneous modes. Additional simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests were also performed on a restricted number of configurations for 4 different climatic conditions to study the influence of climatic parameters.

Spot-welded lap-shear specimens were not sensitive to alternated fatigue-corrosion, whereas a decrease of the fatigue life at high load amplitude and an increase at lower load levels was observed in simultaneous fatigue-corrosion conditions. For adhesive bonded specimens, a large effect of the corrosive environment was reported, even higher for the simultaneous fatigue-corrosion tests than for alternated fatigue-corrosion conditions. No beneficial effect from adhesive and spot weld bonded specimens was noticed in comparison with only adhesive bonded specimens.

Specimens were more affected by twelve weeks in accelerated corrosion test than almost two years of outdoor exposure.

Modeling based on notch stress approach was successfully developed for spot weld specimens. For adhesive specimens, the cohesive zone model required further development to accurately predict the life duration during fatigue-corrosion.

